

“FACE RECOGNITION USING HYBRID TECHNIQUE”

A Report

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This is to certify that entitled **“FACE RECOGNITION USING HYBRID TECHNIQUE”** submitted by **Dr. LAKSHMI PATIL** bearing **Registration Number: 21SUPDR009** to **SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY** for the award of the Post-Doctoral Fellow is a Bonafide record of the research work carried out by her under my supervision and guidance. The content of the Report, in full or parts have not been submitted to any other institute or university for the award of any degree or diploma.

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ABSTRACT

The main purpose of the presented work demonstrates about Face Recognition System initiated by using GA (Genetic algorithm). This research carried out the use of normal GA and improved GA and is applicable for the problems of face recognition or pattern recognition systems. Still in modern days, a whole effective machinery to elaborate these features in systemic ways is not possible. Mentioning the facial expression of images, and its recognition in a duplicate image is a problem that involves a scrupulous examination because of its extraordinary complication. In this work, the primary purpose is to implement a robust algorithm for face detection on unconstrained background images using a neural network. In this regard the types of recognition involved in the image processing discipline are pattern recognition, Face recognition, object recognition, speech recognition, analyzing the data, etc. The basic concepts, structure, and ideas involved in this recognition are discussed in this section. In the last two decades, object detection and recognition have become the most interesting and challenging research field for researchers.

Design methodology of proposed work consists of dependable face recognition system method constructed on the normal GA and improved GA procedure. Originally, conceivable face regions remain produced by revenues of the inherent algorithm and the convenient appreciation of the similar process that was done by genetic algorithm.

The main finding is about Face Recognition System is initiated by using genetic algorithm. This scheme approaches and entails for brilliance advantage popular audiovisual effects, displaying, piece mining, arrangement, documentation, etc. For face appreciation systems the proportion of society is strong virtually and perfect stability is more than 85%. It has been found and arranged for a further research study for face recognition applications systems. Based on the developed model, the resultant efficiency of the selected algorithm can be predictable based on Specificity, Accuracy & Sensitivity the result of the evaluation is very high. An experimental study was conducted on the famous WIDER Face and FDDB databases. The obtained results proved the efficiency as well as the feasibility of the proposed method to deal with multi-scale face detection problems.

Some reasons like background, head movement & neural network, or inappropriate training. The efficiency of the selected algorithm can be predictable based on Specificity, Accuracy & Sensitivity. The estimated values are 95.3%, 88.6% & 89.2% correspondingly. In this proposed novel approaches replicas remain predictable to covenant by delinquent resolving in a manner with various ways of conservative computing. Dissimilarity has been made between data and the pattern to accentuate the necessity for proposing the pattern systems that report pattern recognition tasks.

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ABBREVIATIONS

GA	Genetic algorithm
HMM	Hidden Markov Model
ANN	Artificial Neural Network
AWGN	Additive White Gaussian Noise
NCC	Normalized Cross-Correlation
SAD	Sum of Absolute Differences
OSAD	OptimizedSum of Absolute Differences
IGA	Immune Genetic Algorithm
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
SVM	Support vector machine
DCT	Discrete Cosine Transform
LDA	Linear Discriminant Analysis
DBC	Directional Binary Code
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
HRPSM_CNN	Hybrid Robust Point Set Matching Convolution Neural Network
HCI	Human-Computer Interface

Chapter-1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Face recognition is one of the areas in computer vision which is gaining a great deal of attention from the research community to develop faster and efficient algorithms. Computer vision has three main components, namely, image processing, pattern recognition and face recognition. Of all three components, face recognition is a very crucial task and is important in the image analysis. Face recognition becomes difficult when the background is different in the video sequence especially when the face recognition system is used for commercial or law enforcement applications. It is also difficult to apply the face recognition methods in dealing with real life situations in which there is a change in the pictures, shapes, illumination, occlusion or motion of the subject [1-3]. There are mainly three stages involved in face recognition system as shown in Fig. 1.1. They are:

1.1.1 Face detection

Face detection is a computer technology being used in a variety of applications that identifies human faces in digital images.[1] Face detection also refers to the psychological process by which humans locate and attend to faces in a visual scene.[2]

Face detection can be regarded as a specific case of object-class detection. In object-class detection, the task is to find the locations and sizes of all objects in an image that belong to a given class. Examples include upper torsos, pedestrians, and cars. Face detection simply answers two questions, 1. Are there any human faces in the collected images or video? 2. Where is the located?

Face-detection algorithms focus on the detection of frontal human faces. It is analogous to image detection in which the image of a person is matched bit by bit. Image matches with the image stores in database. Any facial feature changes in the database will invalidate the matching process.

Firstly, the possible human eye regions are detected by testing all the valley regions in the gray-level image. Then the genetic algorithm is used to generate all the possible face regions which include the eyebrows, the iris, the nostril and the mouth corners.[3]

Each possible face candidate is normalized to reduce both the lighting effect, which is caused by uneven illumination; and the shirring effect, which is due to head movement. The fitness value of each candidate is measured based on its projection on the Eigen-faces. After a number of iterations, all the face candidates with a high fitness value are selected for further verification. At this stage, the face symmetry is measured and the existence of the different facial features is verified for each face candidate. Figure 1.2 shows that major steps in automatic face recognition and Figure 1.2 shows that major steps in automatic face recognition.

Figure 1.1: Major steps in automatic face recognition

Figure 1.2: Major steps in automatic face recognition

1.1.2 Face tracking

Face Tracking Technology detects and tracks the presence of a human face in a digital video frame. This technology can be incorporated into computer and mobile applications, and can even be used in robotics. Face Tracking Technology can be used online or offline. Figure 1.3 shows those facial expression recognition techniques: a comprehensive survey.

Figure 1.3: Facial expression recognition techniques: a comprehensive survey

1.1.3 Face Recognition.

Figure 1.4: Face Recognition System

Figure 1.5: Face Recognition System Structure

There are two approaches in face detection. They are: model based approach and feature based approach. In the model based approach, the whole face is treated as one single unit, where as in case of feature based approach, the face is considered as a collection of various features on the faces. The features can be point, line based or region based. Figure 1.4 shows that face recognition system.

Face tracking is matching the sequences of the images on the time scale. Face recognition is very important step among all the three stages. It involves, matching or identifying the face of the person under consideration with the images present in the database. There are some challenges one would encounter when indentifying the face from the database of images. They are: Illumination, Pose, Ageing, Facial expression, Occlusion, Background. Illumination plays an important role in determining the pixel intensity magnitudes in the images. As there is variation in the illumination, pixel intensity changes. For a same face expression, if the illumination is different, then it becomes difficult to correctly match the images with each other. The variation to illumination is not only caused by the external lighting, but also by reflectance characteristics of the face and settings on the camera being used. The algorithms perform well when there is a moderate change in the illumination, but the recognition rates suffer significantly when there is a significant change in the pose or variation in the facial expression [4-7]. Generally, the databases capture the images with only frontal views of the faces, though there are some exceptions. In a real life scenario, the face is captured from a video sequence, for example in an airport, which is not necessarily a frontal

view. It can be a pose. Hence, it becomes difficult to identify the person by comparing the frontal view of the face in the database with the actual pose that is captured live by an automatic face recognition system. Also, the facial images stored in the database and the one that is captured live may have different appearances of the face and also there may be some environment changes. Figure 1.5 shows that Face Recognition System Structure.

Effect of ageing becomes significant when there is a huge gap between age of the person when the image was captured for database and the age when image was captured live for identification. The impact gets compounded when there is change in pose as well as variation in illumination.

Facial expression also play important role to undermine the recognition rates. As the variation in the facial expressions are significant, the recognition rates fall down drastically. But there is already a significant research going on in this area and all the present algorithms work well when there is a variation in the facial expressions. However, it becomes difficult when the facial expressions have huge variation like scream [8-9]. Recognition rates are severely affected when some part of the face is covered with beard, spectacles or scarf. This problem is popularly known as Occlusion. This still remains as one of the challenges to be addressed by the researchers. Other important issue is the back ground of the face image. If there is huge difference in the back ground of the database image and the probe image, then it is possible that face recognition system may identify the background as face. This problem can be addressed by extracting only the facial part from the image and then comparison is made between the database and probe images [10-11].

1.2 Scopus of Further Research

1) Purpose: In this work, the primary purpose is to implement a robust algorithm for face detection on unconstrained background images using a neural network. In this regard the types of recognition involved in the image processing discipline are pattern recognition, Face recognition, object recognition, speech recognition, analyzing the data, etc. The basic concepts, structure, and ideas involved in this recognition are discussed in this section. In the last two decades, object detection and recognition have become the most interesting and challenging research field for researchers.

2) Purpose: The presented work demonstrates, Face Recognition System initiated by using GA (Genetic algorithm). This scheme approaches and entails for brilliance advantage popular audiovisual effects, displaying, piece mining, arrangement, documentation, etc. This paper also suggests the use of normal GA and improved GA and is applicable for the problems of face recognition or pattern recognition systems. An image file consists of a large number of evidence and individualities. Still in modern days, a whole effective machinery to elaborate these features in systemic ways is not possible. Mentioning the facial expression of images, and its recognition in a duplicate image is a problem that involves a scrupulous examination because of its extraordinary complication. In this work, an attempt was made to scrutinize the characteristics of GA in face recognition applications. GA is considered to be one of the best possible search methods encouraged by the theory of Darwin Evolutionist.

1.3 Robust Algorithm

The first work on this subject started in the 1950s in psychology Bruner et al. (1954)[1]. The research came out with issues like expression, emotion analysis, and gestures. The actual research on face recognition started in the 1960s. Woodrow W. Bledsoe along with other researchers did the majority of work related to AI-related for different intelligence agencies[2][3]. During 1964-65 Bledsoe continued his work end to end with Helen Chan & Charles Bisson by using computers to identify the face of humans. Later Bledsoe planned and applied a semi-automatic system. Bledsoe discussed a few challenges faced by face recognition systems, after 50 years the problems continue- variations in illuminations, aging, head rotation, face expression [4]. In 1970, few researchers defined geometric parameters which perform pattern recognition. In 1973, Kanade established an automatic face identification system which was demonstrated on a computer and he observed a 45-75% correct identification rate [6]. In the 1980s researchers came out with new approaches to improve face recognition systems such as Template matching with "deformable templates" and ANN [7]. The year 1990 saw a broad face recognition approach using Eigen faces, ICA, PCA, LDA & their derivatives. Face detection is a process of extracting faces positively from the input image scenes or video stream [8][9]. Feature extraction such as face regions, variations, angles; eye spacing is done in the next step. The last step performs face recognition by comparing it with an image database.

The challenges faced by most face recognition systems are:

1.3.1 Pose Variation: Frontal images would be a condition for a face recognition system but this is an uncontrolled condition. Pose variation is one of the major research issues and this drops the performance of face detection systems. Pose variation depends on the image acquisition system and position which changes spatial coordinates in an acquired image leading to distortion. This variation affects traditional appearance-based face recognition methods like Eigen faces and fisher faces [11][14].

1.3.2 Face Occlusion: The presence of spectacles, beards or hats may cause problems in face detection. This is another main problem in face detection and identification systems [12][13][24].

1.3.3 Facial Expression: Facial features vary due to facial gestures and become difficult to identify. Facial expressions represent the feelings, tempers, and emotions of human beings. The variation in expression results in a change in spatial coordinates but also changes the shape of the face [15][16].

1.3.4 Illumination: Imaging systems and environmental variations affect the image quality. The illumination changes are being discussed in some face detection and identification systems. This variation is caused by different lighting conditions [17][18].

1.3.5 Clustering: The above four parameters make changes in original image facial appearances; hence it is necessary to consider the presence of all conditions and backgrounds around a person in acquired images. Avoiding these parameters affects face detection algorithms and reduces performance. Yan, Kriegman, and Ahuja divided face recognition techniques into four categories that may overlap, developing another algorithm that may consist of two or more categories [20][21].

The four categories are:

- (i) Knowledge-dependent Process: Identify faces based on information about humanoid faces.
- (ii) Invariant Feature Methods: Methods developed under this category recognize faces based on invariant features.

(iii) **Template Matching Methods:** These methods try to correlate original images with database pattern images.

(iv) **Appearance Based Methods:** This recognizes faces based on a set of training pictures.

1.3.6 Knowledge Depending Process: These use some knowledge about faces like ellipse shape and triangle features. Another set of rules which can be used, the face usually has two symmetric eyes and eyes are darker than cheeks. It measures the distance between eyes or intensity between eye areas. Knowledge-based methods can reduce the computation cost but they are rotation limited. If rules set are too universal, there could be more false rejections. The solution to overcome this problem is to develop hierarchical knowledge-based techniques. But these methods are limited and unable to find faces in complex images [26][27].

1.3.7 Feature-Invariant Methods: This makes use of features like edge, complexion, texture, and shape for face detection. These methods are rotation independent, scale-independent and fast. The method which is scale-independent, rotation independent can reduce computational cost. Building Face identification systems depend on skin complexion as a feature, the researcher has three major issues, which complexion space to choose, modeling of skin complexion distribution, and a way to process skin complexion[29][30].

In image/vision processing, the complexion is used as a powerful tool to identify objects or features such as computer graphics, Colorimetry& video signal communication standards that have given many complexion spaces with dissimilar properties [31] [32].

(a) **RGB:** This cloudspace originated from CRT, it is defined as a mixture of Greenish color, Reddish color, and Blue color. This complexion space is the very extensively used information for saving image data. Combining luminance &chrominance with RGB is the unfavorable choice for complexion space [33].

(b) **Normalized RGB:** This is obtained from RGB by normalizing, $r=R/(R+G+B)$, $g=G/(R+G+B)$, $b=B/(R+G+B)$. The 'b' component has no significance, hence neglected. The remaining two components are called pure complexion, and normalized RGB does not vary due to light source. This property made this complexion space gain popularity among researchers [34].

(c) **HSV, HSL- Hue, HSI, Saturation Value (Lightness, Intensity):** Dominant complexion like red, purple, yellow is represented as Hue. Complexion brightness is measured using Saturation. Intensity, Lightness, and Value are related to luminance [35].

(d) **TSL- Tint(T), Saturation(S), and Lightness(L):** This complexion space is a transformation of normalized RGB, close to hue and saturation. Normalization of TSL within RGB is the advantage of TSL complexion space transform. Normalized values of r and g for TSL space are more effective during the skin segmentation approach. This normalization reduces the variability of skin complexion sensitivity and improves skin complexion detection rate. TSL complexion space is more efficient and robust after normalization. No complexion correction algorithms are existing for image acquisition devices. Despite all these efforts, detection of dark skin complexion is an open challenge to researchers [36].

(e) **YCbCr:** This complexion space is nonlinear encoded RGB, mostly used in European television for compressing images without loss of information. It is constructed by weighted sum RGB, Cr, and Cb, and complexion is represented as luminance. Cr is luminance difference red and Cb is luminance difference blue components. The luminance separation and components property of chrominance make this color space beautiful for skin colormodeling. The main objective of skin color segmentation is to separate the skin from the non-skin region. Human skin occupies a small region in a color space; hence it is best to build a classifier that classifies skin from non-skin regions. In 1999, Yang and Ahuja used Luv color space with Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM), the authors concluded that the method worked for different types of skin but they failed to discuss intensity and true positive rate (TPR) and false-positive rate (FPR). In the year 1990, RGB color space with Bayes SPM achieved a TPR of 80% and FPR of 8.4% Mason made use of three different color spaces: RGB with Bayes Skin Probability Map (SPM) classifier, YIQ with I-axis threshold classifier & RGB with threshold ratios classifier [37]. The TPR of these three methods are 19.8%, 30.2% & 32.3% respectively. In 2000, another researcher used HSV color space with Max. Likelihood estimation which worked on different skin types, an attractive study on skin color spreading under different conditions of lighting was proposed which showed 125 individuals to lie inside a definite color space locus, writers used scatter matrices of non-skin & skin clusters [38]. The conclusions drawn were, separating skin and non-skin in RGB space & falling luminance will worsen the separation. In 2005, authors used five color space models with different classifiers but failed to achieve a TPR of more than 90%. In 2009, the authors

used YCgCb + YCgCr with thresholding as a classifier and achieved 92.1% TPR with 6% of FPR. In 2010, YCbCr with 2D Gaussian Model and Bayesian Network (BN) achieved 96% of TPR with 15% of FPR. With the Literature Survey on Face detection using Skin Segmentation, it is concluded that a good classifier must distinguish between the skin and non-skin pixels of several persons having different skin hues like white, wheat, black & brown.

To expand the accuracy of the classifier, it is better to take into consideration other features such as motion, shape & size. If skin detection is a pre-processing step in any application, the authors concluded that it yields better results with 1D RGB colorspace. Other authors concluded that results can be improved using Hybrid color space i.e., a combination of different color spaces such as HSV+YCbCr, HSV+rgb, HSV+TSL+rgb. Meeting real-time application requirements such as computational and storage are extremely important [39][40].

1.3.8 Template Matching Methods: Template matching is one of the widest used methods for face identification because they are strong to noise, easy to use & take less time. In this method, the forward face images are already defined and kept in the system database. An Image processing algorithm is developed where the correlation between input and the stored image is performed to detect the face. But face detection algorithms suffer from illumination and variation of face feature shapes. One simple method to resolve this problem is to receive the usual face from the face examples & then keep them in the database, then the input picture with a high association score is the position of the face. This process is known as the filter match process. The filter match process accepts Additive White Gaussian Noise (AWGN), which is not good for an image like variation, illumination, and expression. AWGN is noise added to images to investigate the performance of the proposed system. To reduce this high variation Appearance-based methods have been used by various authors. The association between input image and face template is similar to Normalized Cross-Correlation (NCC). But NCC is exaggerated by clutter background and illumination. This problematic situation can be resolved using Sum of Absolute Differences (SAD), but it is mostly cast-off for compression and tracking the object, hence SAD needs optimization. In 2012, authors proposed face detection using Optimized SAD (OSAD) instead of NCC to reduce the illumination effect. The results showed that OSAD is unaffected by variation of the pose but affected through the clutter as objects exist in it.

1.4 Problem Statement

From the exhaustive literature review conducted in the last chapter, it has been observed that there has been a significant research progress in the area of face recognition. Face recognition have been attempted with statistical methods like PCA, LBP, ICA etc, which are considered as traditional methods , sequence based hidden markov models (HMM) and of later with deep learning methods. Sequence based modeling methods offer very simple flow in the algorithm and is fast in execution time compared to other methods. While deep learning methods bring in more advancement in general into the face recognition algorithms. The computational time for execution of deep learning model is challenging but, with today's advancement in technology in cloud computing and programming languages like Tensor flow, PyTorch, Mxnetetc, it is becoming more and more demanding in the industry to develop solutions in deep learning so that it can be integrated easily with other machine learning model.

Integration of deep learning methods with the sequence based modeling is not found to be given enough importance by the research community to avail the benefits of both the techniques. Though there were some methods to build hybrid models by using the output probability of ANN into the HMMs, it is not taking all the features and advantages of using deep learning methods. Therefore, it is required to build a HMM model which takes the inputs from the deep learning models as observational vectors to leverage the benefits of both HMM and Deep learning methods. In this work, an attempt is made to integrate the solution methodologies of deep learning method and HMM to improve the accuracies. The objectives for this research work are set with this idea and following are the list of the objective to be achieved as part of this research work.

1.5 Research Objectives

The main research focused on “**FACE RECOGNITION USING HYBRID TECHNIQUE**” In previous research has been found and arranged for a further research study for face recognition applications systems. This work also key pointed the problems and challenges' in existing works. These are as follows:

- (1) The normal GA are not applicable for the problems of face recognition or pattern recognition systems. An image file consists of a large number of evidence and individualities.

- (2) In existing system predictable to covenant by delinquent resolving in a manner with various ways of conservative computing was not highlighted .
- (3) Dissimilarity has been made between data and the pattern to accentuate the necessity for proposing the pattern systems that report pattern recognition tasks.
- (4) The Face recognition system consists of an identical massive Heap-space that includes time-intense tasks therefore GA based methodology was being used to identify the unaccusable copy inside a specific period.
- (5) To feed the constructed neural network, to train several general facial expressions.
- (6) To obtain high efficiency as well as the feasibility of the proposed method to deal with multi-scale face detection problems.
- (7) To introduce a technique that is employed by different studies like matching the template, Hough Transform, and Eigenvectors. HSV for eliminating all unnecessary pixels in the picture excluding Face & Neural Network, categorize the picture as Face / non-Face.
- (8) Propose methods to improve the accuracy of the HMM model and compare the performance of the proposed method with the existing methods. Measure the performance of the deep learning model and compare it with traditional methods and improved HMM models.

1.6 Thesis Organization

Proposed “**Face Recognition Using Hybrid Technique**” organized into six chapters.

Chapter –1: Discuss the introduction and motivation, research objectives,

Chapter -2: The presents a detailed literature survey on Face Recognition System by using Genetic Algorithm and Robust Algorithm for Face Detection.

Chapter- 3: Discussed the Design and Execution of Face Recognition System by using Genetic Algorithm.

Chapter -4: Provides Basic concepts a Robust Algorithm for Face Detection on Unconstrained Background Images using Neural Network.

Chapter- 5: Results and Discussions.

Chapter- 6: Conclusion and future scope.

Chapter-2

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

We have reviewed several research papers of different journals and conferences published on this research area. Research has been categorized “**Face Recognition System by using Genetic Algorithm and Robust Algorithm for Face Detection on Unconstrained Background Images using Neural Network**”.

2.1 Related Research on Face Recognition System By Using Genetic Algorithm

There are many various recognition approaches and we now recapitulate some of them. Various authors in their proposed worked defined some different approaches by using a face recognition system on mobile phones based on the input image, by using Viola-Jones algorithm. The primary goal of the system is to save time and make ac cooler access for penetrating pictures. Some authors also discussed a new application for face appreciation on mobile devices based on Bridge based Approach (BA) to improve the speed up the treating and it permits using the arrangement in any setting where an internet is accessible. Face detection and article abstraction are executed using Open library, nonetheless the face recognition is performed in GA algorithm. The expansion and implementation of a face recognition system for the platform by including face and eye detection and applying a set of preprocessing for using normal GA and Improved GA algorithms.

Zhi et al. (2019) The development of computer technology has led to the development of face recognition technology. Nowadays, face recognition technology has been successfully applied in many fields with the help of computer technology and network technology. This paper establishes an effective face recognition model based on principal component analysis, genetic algorithm and support vector machine, in which principal component analysis is used to reduce feature dimension, genetic algorithm is used to optimize search strategy, and support vector machine is used to realize classification. Through the simulation experiment on the face database of the Institute of Technology of Chinese Academy of Sciences in 2003, the results show that the model can achieve face recognition with high efficiency, and the highest accuracy rate is 99%.

Jondhale et al. (2019) discussed about face recognition is one of the most challenging aspect in the field of image analysis. Face recognition has been a topic of active research since the 1980's, proposing solutions to several practical problems. Face recognition is probably the biometric method that is used to identify people mainly from their faces. However, the recognition process used by the human brain for identifying faces is very challenging. In this paper, a Genetic Algorithm (GA) based approach is proposed for face recognition. The proposed algorithm recognizes an unknown image by comparing it with the known training images stored in the database and gives information regarding the person recognized. The proposed algorithm is then compared with other known face recognition algorithms viz: Principal Component Analysis(PCA) and Linear Discriminate Analysis (LDA) algorithms. It has been observed that the recognition rate of the proposed algorithm is better.

Agrawal et al. (2013) This paper presents an efficient method of recognition of facial expressions in a video. The works proposes highly efficient facial expression recognition system using PCA optimized by Genetic Algorithm .Reduced computational time and comparable efficiency in terms of its ability to recognize correctly are the benchmarks of this work. Video sequences contain more information than still images hence are in the research subject now-a-days and have much more activities during the expression actions. We use PCA, a statistical method to reduce the dimensionality and are used to extract features with the help of covariance analysis to generate Eigen –components of the images. The Eigen-components as a feature input is optimized by Genetic algorithm to reduce the computation cost.

Karungaru et al. (2019) discussed system that can automatically detect and recognise frontal faces are proposed. Three methods are used for face recognition; neural network, template matching and distance measure. One of the main problems encountered when using neural networks for face recognition is insufficient training data. This problem arises because, in most cases, only one image per subject is available. Therefore, amongst the objectives is to solve this problem by "increasing" the data available from the original image using several preprocesses, for example, image mirroring, colour and edges information, etc. Moreover, template matching is not trivial because of differences in the template shapes and sizes. In this work, template matching is aided by a genetic algorithm to automatically test several positions around the target and automatically adjust the size of the template as the

matching process progresses. Distance measure method depends heavily on good facial feature extraction results. The image segmentation method applied matches such demand. The face colour information is represented using YIQ and the XYZ colour spaces. The effectiveness of the proposed method is verified by performing computer simulations. Two sets of databases were used. Database1 consists of 267 faces from the Oulu university database and database (for comparison purposes) consists of 250 faces from the ORL database.

Alsmadi et al. (2017) In various real-world face recognition applications such as forensics and surveillance, only partial face image is available. Hence, template matching and recognition are strongly needed. In this paper, a genetic algorithm to match a pattern of an image and then recognize this image by this pattern is proposed. This algorithm can use any pattern of an image such as eye, mouth or ear to recognize the image. The proposed genetic algorithm uses a small length chromosome to decrease the search space, and hence the results could be obtained in a short time. Two datasets were used to test the proposed method which are AR Face database and LFW database of face, the overall matching and recognition accuracy were calculated based on conducting sequences of experiments on random sub-datasets, where the overall matching and recognition accuracy was 91.7% and 90% respectively. The results of the proposed algorithm demonstrate the robustness and efficiency compared with other state-of-the-art algorithms.

Tomar et al. (2019) proposed In this framework, we proposed a framework for enhancing the features of face recognition system. We are doing Image pre-processing basically for features enhancement of an input image that provides efficient image recognition. Some changes in every phase are important to improve the recognition results. A similar approach has been applied. A schema has been proposed for better face recognition system. Enhancing image contrast and then rotating the image by some degrees to get different view perspectives of the image, cropping the face in proper region for exact feature selection continued by a hybrid approach of ant colony optimization and genetic algorithm for face detection.

Wasu et al. (2013) Face detection is one of the challenging problems in the image processing. This project, introduce a face detection and recognition system to detect (finds) faces in images from galleries of known people. Human skin color is an effective feature used to detect faces, although different people have different skin color, several studies have

shown that the basic difference based on their intensity rather than their chrominance. Textures of human faces have a special texture that can be used to separate them from different objects. An important task to be carried out in the Systems of Recognition of Faces is to detect the presence of a face in a determined region of the image. To detect the face before trying to recognize it saves a lot of work, as only a restricted region of the image is analyzed, opposite to many algorithms which work considering the whole image. This system is capped with three steps. The first step is to classify each pixel in the given image as a skin pixel or a non-skin pixel. The second step is to identify different skin regions in the skin detected image. The last step is to decide whether each of the skin regions identified is a face or not. Finally recognition is done by using Genetic Algorithm. As the genetic algorithm is computationally intensive, the searching space is reduced and the required timing is greatly reduced.

Kumar et al. (2014) Face detection is one of the challenging problems in the digital image processing. Digital images have an enormous information and characteristics measures. But until today, a complete capable mechanism to extract these characteristics in an automatic way is so far unknown. Referring to facial images, its detection in an image is a problem that requires a thorough investigation due to its high complexity. Face detection is an important application of visual object detection and it is one of the main components of face analysis and understanding with face localization and face recognition. Here the investigation aspects of genetic Algorithms (GA's) in face recognition are characterized as one of search technique. GA is efficient technique in reducing computational time for a huge stack space. Face recognition from a very huge stack space is a time consuming job hence GA based approach is used to recognize the unidentified image within a short duration of time. This work analyzes the work done by distinguished authors previously and throws light on what next is to be done. Though they don't give exact and accurate results but are very efficient in time bound recognition for very huge databases. For promptness on a random pickup base it gives fastest result. GA is used when user has no time or less time for giving results without going for check related to each database containing facial images. Feature extraction along with GA will prove better for quicker face recognition. The basic plan of face detection is to determine if there is any face in an image and then locate a position of face in an image. Human face detected in an image can represent the presence of a human in a place. Obviously, face detection is the first step towards creating an automated system, which may involve other face processing. A novel face detection system is presented in this

work. Early face-detection algorithms focused on the detection of frontal human faces, whereas newer algorithms attempt to solve the more general and difficult problem of multi-view face detection. That is, the detection of faces that is either rotated along the axis from the face to the observer or rotated along the vertical or left-right axis or both. The newer algorithms take into account variations in the image by factors such as face appearance, lighting, and pose. The goal of face detection is to detect human faces in still images or videos, in diverse situations. A global overview focuses on a detector which processes images very quickly while achieving high detection rates. In certain applications face detection may require advanced classification methods that would precisely identify the faces even if the face visibility measure is less. This work proposes two methods, first is an edge detection technique. Where it establishes a pheromone matrix that represents the edge information at each pixel based on the routes formed by the Ant Colony Genetic Algorithm (ACOG) dispatched on the image [1, 2]. Second one is face detection based on usage of GA for advance classification of cases and objects of the input image. This work is based on preliminary segmentation of images into regions that contain non face objects and face objects. This idea may greatly accelerate the efficiency of face detection.

Mathusoothana et al. (2018) the task of face recognition in real-world scenarios is still a challenging one. There exist many techniques for the recognition of faces in videos. The recognition task may be computationally easier, but is susceptible to pose variations, lighting conditions etc. This paper focuses on recognition of faces from multi-view videos using the combination of particle filtering with Immune Genetic Algorithm (IGA) and HSH, which is insensitive to pose variations. Particle filtering along with the IGA efficiently track the target using immune system mechanism and then the recognition phases are carried out using HSH. For recognition of video, the ensemble feature similarity calculated which can be measured with the limiting Bhattacharyya distance of features in the Reproducing Kernel Hilbert space. The proposed system with HSH provides better performance than using Spherical Harmonics (SH) for recognizing the face of the target and the performance are analyzed with existing techniques for recognition of face.

Satone et al. (2014) designed, many events, such as terrorist attacks, exposed serious weaknesses in most sophisticated security systems. So it is necessary to improve security data systems based on the body or behavioral characteristics, called biometrics. With the growing interest in the development of human and computer interface and biometric identification,

human face recognition has become an active research area. Face recognition offers several advantages over other biometric methods. Nowadays Principal Component Analysis (PCA) has been widely adopted for the face recognition algorithm. Yet still, PCA has limitations such as poor discriminatory power and large computational load. This paper proposed a novel algorithm for face recognition in which a low frequency component of the wavelet is used for PCA representation. Best features of PCA are selected using the genetic algorithm (GA). Support vector machine (SVM) and nearest neighbor classifier (ND) are used for classification. Classification accuracy is examined by changing number of training images, number of features and kernel function. Results are evaluated on ORL, FERET, Yale and YaleB databases. Experiments showed that proposed method gives a better recognition rate than other popular methods.

Mousaa et al. (2018) In the field of image processing and recognition, discrete cosine transform (DCT) and principal component analysis (PCA) are two widely used techniques. In this paper we present a face recognition approach based on them. Feature selection (FS) is a global optimization problem in machine learning, which reduces the number of features, removes irrelevant, noisy and redundant data, and results in acceptable recognition accuracy. It is the most important step that affects the performance of a face recognition system. Genetic Algorithms (GA), one of the most recent techniques in the field of feature selection, are a type of evolutionary algorithms that can be used also to solve this issue. The application of a GA in the resolution of a problem requires the coding of the potential solutions to this problem in finite bit chains in order to constitute the chromosomes coming from a population formed by candidate points. The aim is to find a selective function allowing good discrimination between chromosomes and to define the genetic operators that will be used. In this sense, this approach seeks to develop a system of face recognition using Genetic Algorithm and a DCT-PCA combination for feature selection and dimensionality reduction, to be applied to an archive of images of human faces. The proposed approach is applied on various Face Databases. Experimental results demonstrate the effectiveness of this approach compared to state of the art in face recognition.

Several face recognition methods have been proposed in recent years, based on two main axes: recognition from fixed images [38] and recognition from image sequences [29]. Studies in this field, under different lighting conditions, facial expressions and orientations, can be classified into two distinct categories depending on whether they relate to a geometric

approach or to a global approach. We particularly emphasize the dimensional reduction methods which are part of the global approaches. Into a space with reduced dimensionality methods fall within the broader framework of data processing in general and object recognition. Global approaches take the image of the face as a whole and use well-known statistical analysis techniques. The idea is generally to project the input image of the face, previously vectorized, into a space of smaller dimensions, where recognition is supposed to be easier. The projection is often designed to select only the important features and sufficiently discriminating to differentiate the people between them. One of the advantages of global methods is that they are quick to implement, and their calculations are based on relatively simple matrix operations. However, since they consider the face as a whole, they are sensitive to the conditions of luminosity, pose or facial expression. The global methods can be broken down into two types of techniques: linear techniques and nonlinear techniques. The linear techniques realize a linear projection of the faces on a space of smaller dimension. The best known among these approaches is the technique known as Eigenfaces presented by Turk and Pentland in [34]. A PCA is performed on a training set of images of faces. The main eigenvectors resulting from the PCA define the new space. The images of faces are then projected onto this space, and the vectors obtained are used for classification. Many works have been carried out on the choice of the vectors to retain to define the new space. Thus, Kirby et al. [16] propose a criterion based on the energy of the eigenvalues associated to the eigenvectors. The eigenvectors corresponding to the greatest eigenvalues are retained until the sum of the eigenvalues exceeds a certain threshold of the total energy. Martinez et al. show in [23] that the recognition rates can be improved by ignoring the first eigenvectors (those whose associated eigenvalues are the largest), which often encodes the variations of illumination. Another well-known approach presented by Ming et al. [20] performs a Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA), often called Fisher faces. Indeed, this technique consists in maximizing on a learning set the Fisher criterion, namely the quotient of the interclass variance by the intra-class variance. Thus, contrary to the technique of Eigenfaces where the best representation (that maximizes the variance) is sought, the goal here is a better separation of the classes. However, since the number of images is often smaller than their dimension, the intra-class variance matrix may be singular, and its inversion is therefore problematic. Other linear techniques have also been used for the computation of feature vectors such as Independent Component Analysis in [11], the factorization of non-negative matrices in [9], the bilinear discriminate analysis in [35]. Other global non-linear techniques have been

developed, often using linear techniques. Thus, the Kernel-PCA analysis and the Kernel-LDA [15], [10] use the mathematical notion of kernels to extend the linear PCA and LDA techniques. Genetic algorithms have also successfully demonstrated their great ability to solve optimization problems. They have also been used in the field of feature selection [18]. Many of the studies reported in the literature have shown that methods that use GAs as a research technique have yielded better results compared to other methods of selection [12], [32]. The application of GAs on selection problems of subsets of feature was put in place by **Ferri et al.** [6]. They showed that the use of GAs is well suited for selection on sets of medium-sized features. Kudo et al. [17] demonstrated the possibility of using GAs for selection on large-scale sets by adjusting the number of generations, the size of the population.

2.2 Related Research on Robust Algorithm for Face Detection on Unconstrained

In Bruner, J. (1954) has written the perception of people which is hand book of social psychology where perception of people is clearly mention in [1].Bledsoe et al. (1964)has designed the model method in facial recognition, panoramic research in which feature of facial recognition was highlights[2]. Chan et al. (1965) have proposed a man-machine facial recognition system where some preliminary results explained [3]. Bledsoe (1965) designed Man-machine facial recognition in which recognition was very effective modeled [4]. Bledsoe (1968) talked about semiautomatic facial recognition [5]. Kanade et al. (1974) explored picture processing systems by computer complex and recognition of human faces[6].Nixon et al. (1985) explained eye spacing measurement for facial recognition in applications of digital image processing international society for optics and photonics[7].Stonham et al(1986) gave practical face recognition and verification with WIZARD in aspects of face processing[8].Kirby et al. (1990) discussed the application of the karhunen-love procedure for the characterization of human faces [9].Lee et al.(1997) have developed human factors guidelines for advanced traveler information systems (atis) and commercial vehicle operations (CEO)[10].In Yuille et al.(1992). Feature extraction from faces using deformable templates [11].Saito et al. (1992) explored does fatigue exists in a quantitative measurement of eye movements [12].Ebisawa et al.(1993) conducted the effectiveness of the pupil area detection technique using two light sources and the image difference method[13].Calcagnini et al.(1994, November) analyzed of heart rate variability signal during sleep stages of patients[14].Klein et al.(Biological psychology. Macmillan

[15]. Pentland et al. (1994) proposed view-based and modular eigenspaces for face recognition [16]. Vanoli et al. (1995) found heart rate variability during specific sleep stages: a comparison of healthy subjects with patients after myocardial infarction. Wylie et al. (1996) proposed commercial motor vehicle driver fatigue and alertness study [18]. In [20] Wylie et al. have presented a study on the alertness of motor drivers when they are at various levels of fatigue. These findings of the research in [20] can be amply justified by the work of Toscani et al. in [19] which studies the different sleep stages of men and their heart rates. Much of these studies have been done and the conclusions have been drawn by following the concepts of pattern recognition as invented by Woody Bledsoe [21]. Pigeon et al. (1997, March) have designed the M2VTS multimodal face [21]. Deng et al. (1997) have the region-based template deformation and masking for eye-feature extraction and description [22][23]. Reinders et al. (1996) have located facial features in image sequences using neural networks [24][25]. Huang et al. (1998) posted discrimination and eye detection using Support Vector Machines (SVM) [26]. Feng et al. (xxx) developed variance projection function and its application to eye detection for human face recognition [27]. Ebisawa et al. (1998) have improved the video-based eye-gaze detection method [28]. Elsenbruch, et al. (1999) proposed heart rate variability during waking and sleep in healthy males and females [29]. Jones et al. (2002) have developed statistical color models with application to skin detection [30]. Meng, et al. (1999) have frontal face localization using linear discriminant [31]. In [32] Peters et al. have discussed the effects of partial and total sleep deprivations on driving performance. In [33] Yang et al. have developed a mixture model for various skin colors and used these models in evaluating images in various databases and of image and video files. In [34], Sigal, et al. presented a research on estimation and prediction of evolving color distributions for skin segmentation. In [35], Brand et al. have presented a comparative assessment of three approaches to pixel-level human skin-detection. The work of Jain et al. [36] on Statistical pattern recognition needs to be noted here for presenting the concepts of pattern recognition in a single treatise. In [37], Haro et al. presented a study of detecting and tracking eyes by using their physiological properties, dynamics, and appearance. In [38] another research on dual-state parametric eye-tracking has been presented by Dang et al. In [39] a technique is introduced for multi-cues eye detection on gray intensity image. The paper in [40] studies the effects of light and sleep stages on heart rate variability in humans. The paper in [42] introduces a mixture model for face-color modeling and segmentation [41]. The article in [42] gives us basis functions of the color signals of skin under different illuminants. Ji et al. in [43],

presented real-time visual cues extraction for monitoring driver vigilance. Viola et al. (2001) have rapid object detection using a boosted cascade of simple features [44]. Vijayalaxmi et al. (2020). Image processing-based eye detection methods a theoretical review [45]. Vijayalaxmi et al. (2020). Implementation of the face and eye detection on DM6437 board using Simulink model [46]. Biradar, et al. (2018) have hardware prototyping for video and signal processing applications using dm 6437 texas instrument evaluation board [47]. Biradar, et al. (2018) have DM3730 Processor Hardware Debugging on Linux Platform [48]. Motwani et al. (2004) have eye detection using wavelets and ANN [49]. Chaudhry et al. (2017) have face detection and recognition in an unconstrained environment for the mobile visual assistive system. Mliki et al. (2020) have an improved multi-scale face detection using a convolutional neural network [51]. Ganapathi, et al. (2020) have unconstrained ear detection using an ensemble-based convolutional neural network model [52]. Nada, et al. (2018) have pushed the limits of unconstrained face detection: a challenge dataset and baseline results [53]. Zhou et al. (2018) in [54] have presented a survey of face detection on low-quality images. Sahu et al. (2018) have the modeling of attacks in sigma-delta ADC for hardware security [54]. Zhang et al. (2019) have fareboxes: A CPU real-time and accurate unconstrained face detector [55]. Yang et al. (2017) have faceless-net: Face detection through deep facial part responses [56]. Ravidas et al. (2019) have deep learning for pose-invariant face detection in the unconstrained environment [57]. Lu et al. (2017) have feature extraction and fusion using deep convolutional neural networks for face detection [58]. Sawat et al. (2020) have pixel encoding for unconstrained face detection [59]. Kneis, et al. (2018) explored face detection for crowd analysis using deep convolutional neural networks [60]. Oloyede et al. (2018) discussed Improving face recognition systems using a new image enhancement technique, hybrid features, and the convolutional neural network [61]. Bekhet, et al. (2022) have gender recognition from unconstrained selfie images: a convolutional neural network approach [62]. Ranjan, et al. (2019) designed a fast and accurate system for face detection, identification, and verification [63]. Salman et al. (2020) have automatic fish detection in underwater videos by a deep neural network-based hybrid motion learning system [64].

Malusare et al. (2017) The main challenge in recognizing person in facial feature. The use of Multi view data to handle the pose unconstrained video is exploiting the identity information in variation and its challenges. Multi-camera networks commonly multiple frames and the follow dynamic signature. These identity used for biometric and surveillance system, multiple view sign include face, body, and motion. In this paper, face detection point

overcome the drawback of single view point. For is necessary first-step in face recognition systems, with the purpose of localizing and extracting face region from the example multiple view point increases the position of the background. The human face is a dynamic in nature and also person in different poses has high degree of changeability in its appearance, which results face detection a difficult problem in computer vision. The method we have developed combines approaches from computer vision, for face detection and pose estimation, with those from machine learning for classification. We show that the identification of a target face can be determined by first proposing faces with similar pose, and then classifying the target face as one of the recognized faces or not. Faces at poses differing from those of the training data are rendered using a coarse 3-D model with multiple texture maps. Furthermore, the texture maps of the model can be automatically updated as new poses and expressions are detected.

Tyagi et al. (2016) Face-recognition is becoming common among the section of study in computer-vision, while it is also one of the very effective programs of comprehension and image-analysis. It may be employed for both ID and confirmation. At the moment, there are lots of means of front watch face-recognition. Nicely when just one instant picture per course can be obtained nevertheless, a handful of them can perhaps work. In this paper, we discuss the different face recognition techniques and find a better method for pose variation, non-uniform motion blur and Illumination by using a Reference face graph for face recognition. One example image' problem and two generalized Eigen face algorithms are proposed. Face-recognition has been analyzed thoroughly; nevertheless, real world face recognition stays a job that is difficult. The interest in unconstrained useful face recognition is increasing using the surge of online media, for example, video-surveillance video, and internet sites wherever encounter evaluation is of substantial significance. Face-recognition is approached by us within data theory's framework. We identify an unfamiliar encounter utilizing an exterior Reference Face Graph (RFG). There is an RFG produced by evaluating it towards the encounters within the built RFG and acknowledgement of the given encounter is attained. Centrality steps are used to recognize encounters that were unique within the Reference Face Graph.

Faizal et al. (2018) this addresses the difficulty of unconstrained face recognition from vaguely acquired images. The main factors that make this difficulty challenging are image dilapidation due to blur and appearance variations due to illumination and pose. In this

paper, we deal with the problems of blur and illumination. We demonstrate the set of all images obtained by blurring a given image forms a convex set. Based on this set theoretic classification, we suggest a blur-robust algorithm whose main step involves solving simple convex optimization troubles. We do not suppose any parametric form for the blur kernels, however, if this information is obtainable, it can be simply integrated into our algorithm.

Tamilselvi et al. (2021) Face recognition is an emerging technology that divulges various applications in diverse fields like medical image analysis, surveillance, personal identification, and security related cases. In order to effectively recognize the images from the known data sets, there are a number of face recognition algorithms which are in practice. However, a few problems are encountered in effective recognition with a satisfied parameter. Even though there are various algorithms like Local Binary pattern(LBP), Directional Binary Code(DBC), Multi Support Vector Machine(Multi- SVM), and Convolutional Neural Network(CNN)which are being used for face recognition, still the face recognition is not achieved satisfactorily especially for the large databases as the images are affected due to poor lighting and also owing to occlusion occurring in the stagnant pictures. Hence, a new approach called Hybrid Robust Point Set Matching Convolution Neural Network (HRPSM_CNN) is proposed to effectively recognize the faces from the data sets over the unconstrained situations. This proposed method shows enhanced receiver operating characteristics when compared to the traditional algorithms. This HRPSM_CNN provides 97 % of accuracy rate for ORL and AR database and 96 % for LFW face database which are significantly higher than the existing traditional algorithms. The proposed algorithm is implemented in visually impaired assistive device and the results show better recognition under difficult situations like various lighting and weather conditions.

Klare et al. (2015) Rapid progress in unconstrained face recognition has resulted in saturation in recognition accuracy for current benchmark datasets. While important for early progress, a chief limitation in most benchmark datasets is the use of a commodity face detector to select face imagery. The implication of this strategy is restricted variations in face pose and other confounding factors. This paper introduces the IARPA Janus Benchmark A (IJB-A), a publicly available media in the wild dataset containing 500 subjects with manually localized face images. Key features of the IJB-A dataset are: (i) full pose variation, (ii) joint use for face recognition and face detection benchmarking, (iii) a mix of images and videos, (iv) wider geographic variation of subjects, (v) protocols supporting both open-set

identification (1:N search) and verification (1:1 comparison), (vi) an optional protocol that allows modeling of gallery subjects, and (vii) ground truth eye and nose locations. The dataset has been developed using 1,501,267 million crowd sourced annotations. Baseline accuracies for both face detection and face recognition from commercial and open source algorithms demonstrate the challenge offered by this new unconstrained benchmark.

Seshaiah et al. (2021) Now a days, security based applications are developed widely and these systems are adopted in various real-time applications. Visual surveillance is considered as a most promising technique where certain objects can be detected, tracked and recognized using computer vision based approaches. In this field, face detection and recognition is considered as the important part of surveillance system. Several approaches have been developed for face recognition but existing approaches are applied on the face data. Recently, video face detection techniques are also introduced which provides more information to improve the security system.

Deep learning achieves substantial improvements in face detection. However, the existing methods need to input fixed-size images for image processing and most methods use a single network for feature extraction, which makes the model generalization ability weak. In response to the above problems, our framework leverages a cascaded architecture with three stages of deep convolutional networks to improve detection performance. The network can predict face in a coarse-to-fine manner. The proposed method takes the Three-Patch Local Binary Pattern (TPLBP) texture feature which has excellent performance in face analysis as the input of the network. The learning process is developed using Bayesian learning approach is developed. The proposed approach is implemented on benchmark datasets such as IARPA Janus Benchmark A (IJB-A), the YouTube Face dataset and the Celebrity-1000 dataset. A comparative performance is carried out which shows the robust performance of proposed approach.

Huang et al. (2020) Face recognition has benefitted greatly from the many databases that have been produced to study it. Most of these databases have been created under controlled conditions to facilitate the study of specific parameters on the face recognition problem. These parameters include such variables as position, pose, lighting, expression, background, camera quality, occlusion, age, and gender. While there are many applications for face recognition technology in which one can control the parameters of image acquisition, there are also many applications in which the practitioner has little or no control over such

parameters. This database is provided as an aid in studying the latter, unconstrained, face recognition problem. The database represents an initial attempt to provide a set of labeled face photographs spanning the range of conditions typically encountered by people in their everyday lives. The database exhibits “natural” variability in pose, lighting, focus, resolution, facial expression, age, gender, race, accessories, make-up, occlusions, background, and photographic quality. Despite this variability, the images in the database are presented in a simple and consistent format for maximum ease of use. In addition to describing the details of the database and its acquisition, we provide specific experimental paradigms for which the database is suitable. This is done in an effort to make research performed with the database as consistent and comparable as possible.

Khan et al. (2016) Existing techniques for performing face recognition within the presence of blur depend on the convolution model and that can't deal with non-uniform blurring circumstances that habitually emerge from tilts and pivots close by hand-held cameras. In this paper, we propose a methodology for face acknowledgment within the sight of space shifting movement obscure. We display the blurred face as a convex mix of geometrically changed occasions of the focused gallery face, and demonstrate that the arrangement of all pictures got by non-consistently blurring a given picture frames a raised set. We first propose a non-uniform blur-robust algorithm by making utilization of the supposition of a scanty camera direction in the camera movement space to manufacture a vitality work on the camera movement. The structure is then stretched out to handle light varieties by exploiting the way that the arrangement of all images obtained from a face image by non-uniform blurring and changing the illumination forms of a bi-convex set. At last, we propose a rich augmentation to likewise represent varieties in pose.

Casado et al. (2021) Face alignment is a crucial component in most face analysis systems. It focuses on identifying the location of several keypoints of the human faces in images or videos. Although several methods and models are available to developers in popular computer vision libraries, they still struggle with challenges such as insufficient illumination, extreme head poses, or occlusions, especially when they are constrained by the needs of real-time applications. Throughout this article, we propose a set of training strategies and implementations based on data augmentation, software optimization techniques that help in improving a large variety of models belonging to several real-time algorithms for face alignment. We propose an extended set of evaluation metrics that allow novel evaluations to

mitigate the typical problems found in real-time tracking contexts. The experimental results show that the generated models using our proposed techniques are faster, smaller, more accurate, more robust in specific challenging conditions and smoother in tracking systems. In addition, the training strategy shows to be applicable across different types of devices and algorithms, making them versatile in both academic and industrial uses.

Wagner et al. (2020) many classic and contemporary face recognition algorithms work well on public data sets, but degrade sharply when they are used in a real recognition system. This is mostly due to the difficulty of simultaneously handling variations in illumination, image misalignment, and occlusion in the test image. We consider a scenario where the training images are well controlled, and test images are only loosely controlled. We propose a conceptually simple face recognition system that achieves a high degree of robustness and stability to illumination variation, image misalignment, and partial occlusion. The system uses tools from sparse representation to align a test face image to a set of frontal training images. The region of attraction of our alignment algorithm is computed empirically for public face datasets such as Multi-PIE. We demonstrate how to capture a set of training images with enough illumination variation that they span test images taken under uncontrolled illumination. In order to evaluate how our algorithms work under practical testing conditions, we have implemented a complete face recognition system, including a projector-based training acquisition system. Our system can efficiently and effectively recognize faces under a variety of realistic conditions, using only frontal images under the proposed illuminations as training.

Table 2.1: Summary of literature review of 1D- HMM and 2D HMM in Face recognition

Reference No	Authors	Year	Features
21	Baum & Petrie	1966	Original mathematical formulation for the HMM
22	Baum et al.	1970	Mathematical formulation for the HMM
23	Baum	1972	Mathematical formulation for the HMM
24	Jelinek et al.	1975	Practical application of HMM
25	Levinson et al.	1983	Tutorials on HMM
26	Juang	1984	Tutorials on HMM
27	Rabiner & Juang	1986	Tutorials on HMM
28	Rabiner	1989	Comprehensive tutorials on HMM
29	Juang & Rabiner	2005	HMM in continuous speech processing
30	Park & Le	1998	Two Dimensional HMM
31	Samaria & Fallside	1993	One dimensional HMM to solve a face recognition problem
32	Samaria & Harter	1998	Recognition rate of the HMM was determined by three parameters in a top to bottom HMM
33	Nefian & Hayes	1998a	2D-DCT coefficient features in HMM, ORL Data base, 84% accuracy
34	Nefian & Hayes	1998b	KLT coefficient features in HMM, ORL Data base, 86% accuracy
35	Kohir & Desai	1998a	2D-DCT coefficient features extracted in zig-zag fashion for HMM, ORL Data base, 74.5% to 99.5% accuracy
36	Kohir & Desai	1998b	2D-DCT coefficient features extracted in zig-zag fashion for

			HMM, ORL Data base, 74.5% to 99.5% accuracy
37	Kohir & Desai	1998c	2D-DCT coefficient features extracted in zig-zag fashion for HMM, ORL Data base, 74.5% to 99.5% accuracy
38	Bicego et al.	2003	Gaussian parameters in HMM, accuracy 54% to 100%
39	Bicego et al.	2003	2D-DCT coefficients and Wavelets for HMM, ORL Data base, 97.4% to 99.6% accuracy
40	Martinez	1999	PCA features for HMM, ORL Data base, 72% to 98.5% accuracy
41	Wallhoff et al.	2001	HMM combined with ANN, 70%-80% accuracy
42	Samaria	1994	Pseudo 2D-HMM, ORL Database, 94.5%
43	Nefian & Hayes	1999	P2D-HMM in optical character recognition analysis, ORL database, 86%
44	Eickler et al.	2000	Better initialization techniques were used in the HMM model, ORL database, 90% to 95% accuracy

Table 2.2: Summary of literature review of Deep learning methods

Reference No	Authors	Year	Features
53	McCulloch & Pitts	1943	Turing machine that was based on the neurons
54	Rosenblatt	1958	Perceptron model
55	Minsky and Papert	1969	Slowdown of further research in the area of development of models based on neural networks
56	Ackley, David H and Geoff Hinton	1985	development of back propagation algorithm
57	Kunihiko	1988	Neural network in the area of face and pattern recognition
58	Yan LeCun	1998	Convolutional Neural Networks was proposed
59	Hinton et al	2006	More hidden layers in NN
62	Alex Krizhevsky	2012	Deeper and Wider LeNet
63	Simonyan, Karen, and Andrew Zisserman	2014	VGG (Visual Geometry Group) Net
64	Lin, Min, Qiang Chen, and Shuicheng Yan	2013	Network in Network (NiN)
65	Springenberg, Jost Tobias, et al	2014	All Conv Nets
66	Szegedy, Christian, et al	2015	GoogLeNet-inception nets
67	Szegedy, Christian, Sergey Ioffe, and Vincent Vanhoucke	2016	GoogLeNet-inception nets
68	Kaiming et al.	2015	Residual Nets
69	Huang et al.	2016	Dense Convolutional Neural Nets
70	Larsson et al.	2016	Fractal Nets
71	Mathew Zeiler and Rob Fergus	2013	ZFNets
72-76	Zagoruyko et al.	2016	ResNets – Variants
77	Ioffe et al.	2015	Batch Normalization in Neural Networks
78	Sabour et al.	2017	CapsNet
79	Ren et al.	2015	Fast Region based CNN
80	Chollet	2016	Xception
81	Liang et al.	2015	Recurrent CNN

82	Alom et al.	2017	Inception Recurrent CNN (IRCNN)
83	Li et al.	2015	Visual Phase Guided CNN
84	Bagherinezhad et al.	2016	Look up based CNN
85-87	Huang et al.	2015, 2016	Deeply supervised networks
88	Github	2018	Image processing deep learning approaches
89	Jia et al.	2017	Single image super-resolution CNN
90	Ahn et al.	2017	Image de-noising and block-matching CNN
91	Ma et al.	2017	Adaptive Layout-Aware Multi-Patch Deep CNN
92	Cao et al.	2017	DCNN for hyper spectral imaging for segmentation with Markov Random Field
93	de Vos et al.	2017	Image registration with CNN
94	Wang et al.	2016	Hierarchical Deep CNN for Fast Artistic Style Transfer
95	Babaei et al.	2017	Background segmentation with DCNN
96	Alom et al.	2017	Handwritten character recognition with DCNN
97	Alom et al.	2017	Optical image classification with DL
98	Alom et al.	2017	Object recognition with simultaneous recurrent networks and CNN

Table 2.3: Face databases. This table shows some of the face databases available at the time of writing and Face Recognition Homepage,” maintained by Mislav Grgic and Kresimir Delac (<http://www.face-rec.org/>).

Database	# of people	Total images	Highlights	References
AR Face Database, Purdue University, USA	126	4000	frontal pose, expression, illumination, occlusions, eye glasses, scarves	[21]
AT&T Database (formerly ORL Database)	40	400	variation of time, lighting, facial expression, eye glasses	[29]
BioID Face Database	23	1521	real world conditions, gray scale, background, lighting, expression, eye positions given	[17]
Caltech Faces	27	450	lighting, expression, background	
Caltech 10000 Web Faces	≈ 10000	10000	wide variability, facial features annotated	[1]
CAS-PEAL Face Database	1040	99,594	very large, expression, accessories, lighting, simultaneous capture of multiple poses, Chinese	[10]
Cohn-Kanade AU-Coded Facial Expression Database	100	500 sequences	dynamic sequences of facial expressions	[6]
EQUINOX HID Face Database	?	?	non-visible light modalities	
Face Video Database of the Max Planck Institute for	?	246 video	6 simultaneous viewpoints, carefully synchro-	[18]

Bi- ological Cybernetics		sequences	nized, video data	
Facial Actions and Expressions	24	≈ 7000	expression, color, grayscale	
Face Recognition Grand Challenge Databases	>466	>50,000 images and 3D scans	very large, lighting, expression, background, 3D, sequences	[28]
FERET Database, Color	1199	14126	color images, changes in appearance through time, controlled pose variation, facial expression	[23]
Georgia Tech Face Database	50	750	expression, illumination, scale, orientation	[26]
Indian Face Database	40	>440	frontal, Indian subjects	[16]
Japanese Female Facial Expression (JAFFE) Database	10	213	rated for emotional content, female, Japanese	[19]
MIT-CBCL Face Recognition Database	10	>2000	synthetic images from 3D models, illumination, pose, background	[37]
M2VTS Multimodel Face Database (Release 1.00)	37	185	large pose changes, speaking subjects, eye glasses, time change	[30]
M2VTS, Extended, Univ. of Surrey, UK	295	1180 videos	rotating head, speaking subjects, 3D models, high quality images	[22]
NIST Mugshot ID	1573	3248	front and side views	[36]
NLPR Face Database	≈ 22	450	lighting, expression, backgrounds	[24]

PIE Database, CMU	68	41368	very large database, pose, illumination, expression	[33]
Psychological Image Collection at Stirling (PICS)	?	?	targeted at psychology experiments	[13]
UCD Colour Face Image Database for Face Detection	≈ 299	299	targeted at detection applications, highly varied, color	[32]
UMIST Face Database	20	564	pose, gender, race, grayscale	[12]
University of Essex, UK	395	7900	racial diversity, eye glasses, beards, college age	[34]
University of Oulu Physics-Based Face Database	125	>2000	highly varied illumination, eye glasses	[20]
VALID Database	106	530	highly variable office conditions	[9]
Vid TIMIT Database	43	multiple videos per person	video, audio, reading, head rotation	[31]
Yale Face Database	15	165	expressions, eye glasses, lighting	[2]
Yale Face Database B	10	5760	pose, illumination	[11]

2.3 Problem Identification and Formulation

In previous research has been found and arranged for a further research study for face recognition applications systems. This research work also key pointed the problems and challenges' in existing works. These are as follows:

- (1) The normal GA are not applicable for the problems of face recognition or pattern recognition systems. An image file consists of a large number of evidence and individualities.
- (2) In existing system predictable to covenant by delinquent resolving in a manner with various ways of conservative computing was not highlighted .
- (3) Dissimilarity has been made between data and the pattern to accentuate the necessity for proposing the pattern systems that report pattern recognition tasks.
- (4) The Face recognition system consists of an identical massive Heap-space that includes time-intense tasks therefore GA based methodology was being used to identify the unaccusable copy inside a specific period.
- (5) Designing of fast and accurate system for face detection were challenges using existing methods.
- (6) The real challenge in neural network-based approaches is training and representing images not containing faces.
- (7) Recognizing human faces under different conditions like 5year old boy, grandma's wedding photo, face occluded, and a person with a beard are trivial but not impossible.
- (8) As the classifier complexity increases, a large amount of training examples is required.
- (9) The correctness of the classifier depends on the number of features selected while training the classifier.
- (10) A CPU real-time and accurate unconstrained face detector is still need be in investigation and design implements.

2.4 Research Agenda

2.4.1 Objectives

The main research focused on “**FACE RECOGNITION USING HYBRID TECHNIQUE**” In previous research has been found and arranged for a further research study for face recognition applications systems. This works also key pointed the problems and challenges’ in existing works. These are as follows:

- (1) The normal GA are not applicable for the problems of face recognition or pattern recognition systems. An image file consists of a large number of evidence and individualities.
- (2) In existing system predictable to covenant by delinquent resolving in a manner with various ways of conservative computing was not highlighted.
- (3) Dissimilarity has been made between data and the pattern to accentuate the necessity for proposing the pattern systems that report pattern recognition tasks.
- (4) The Face recognition system consists of an identical massive Heap-space that includes time-intense tasks therefore GA based methodology was being used to identify the unaccusable copy inside a specific period.
- (5) To feed the constructed neural network, to train several general facial expressions.
- (6) To obtain high efficiency as well as the feasibility of the proposed method to deal with multi-scale face detection problems.
- (7) To introduce a technique that is employed by different studies like matching the template, Hough Transform, and Eigenvectors. HSV for eliminating all unnecessary pixels in the picture excluding Face & Neural Network, categorize the picture as Face / non-Face.
- (8) Propose methods to improve the accuracy of the HMM model and compare the performance of the proposed method with the existing methods. Measure the performance of the deep learning model and compare it with traditional methods and improved HMM models.

2.5 Summary

- Reviewed several research papers of different journals and conferences published on this research area.
- Research has been categorized “Face Recognition System by using Genetic Algorithm and Robust Algorithm for Face Detection on Unconstrained Background Images using Neural Network.
- In previous research has been found and arranged for a further research study for face recognition applications systems. This research work also key pointed the problems and challenges in existing works.
- Problem Identification and Formulation and research agenda has clearly discussed in details.

Chapter-3

A ROBUST ALGORITHM FOR FACE DETECTION ON UNCONSTRAINED BACKGROUND IMAGES USING NEURAL NETWORK

3.1 Overview:

In this chapter, the primary purpose is to implement a robust algorithm for face detection on unconstrained background images using a neural network. In this regard the types of recognition involved in the image processing discipline are pattern recognition, Face recognition, object recognition, speech recognition, analyzing the data, etc. The basic concepts, structure, and ideas involved in this recognition are discussed in this section. In the last two decades, object detection and recognition have become the most interesting and challenging research field for researchers. Developing a theoretical concept based on model building using the Face recognition method and analysis to obtain a high efficiency as well as the feasibility of the proposed method to deal with multi-scale face detection problems. Face detection is one such application. The need for Face recognition and detection arises due to the demand for automatic surveillance systems, Human-Computer Interface (HCI), etc. A fast processor is required in the real-time implementation of implanted image processing applications. For these systems, an accurate and fast real-time implementation of face selecting is essential. Therefore, a novel approach for tracking and determining the face on a live and unmoving image is projected in chapter. Based on the developed model, the resultant efficiency of the selected algorithm can be predictable based on Specificity, Accuracy & Sensitivity the result of the evaluation is very high. An experimental study was conducted on the famous WIDER Face and FDDB databases. The obtained results proved the efficiency as well as the feasibility of the proposed method to deal with multi-scale face detection problems. Some reasons like background, head movement & neural network, or inappropriate training. The efficiency of the selected algorithm can be predictable based on Specificity, Accuracy & Sensitivity. The estimated values are 95.3%, 88.6% & 89.2% correspondingly. A novel approach for tracking and determining the face on a live and unmoving image is projected in this work. This projected process is applied and efficiently tested in the laboratory for different original images with glasses and without glasses taken by the camera (specification of camera is Logitech USB, 30fps, 1600 x 1200 pixels). This process is built in a processor named open multimedia applications platform of 1 GHz and by OpenCV libraries, the proposed algorithm is developed. The rate of success in this

selected algorithm is very high as the hardware is very much accurate and works at high speed which is best used for real-time. The rate of success on selected algorithms is ninety-eight percent; the two percent unsuccessful rate in results is for some reason like background, head movement & due to neural network/ inappropriate training.

3.2 Overviews:

The first work on this subject started in the 1950s in psychology Bruner et al. (1954)[1]. The research came out with issues like expression, emotion analysis, and gestures. The actual research on face recognition started in the 1960s. Woodrow W. Bledsoe along with other researchers did the majority of work related to AI-related for different intelligence agencies[2][3]. During 1964-65 Bledsoe continued his work end to end with Helen Chan & Charles Bisson by using computers to identify the face of humans. Later Bledsoe planned and applied a semi-automatic system. Bledsoe discussed a few challenges faced by face recognition systems, after 50 years the problems continue- variations in illuminations, aging, head rotation, face expression [4]. In 1970, few researchers defined geometric parameters which perform pattern recognition. In 1973, Kanade established an automatic face identification system which was demonstrated on a computer and he observed a 45-75% correct identification rate [6]. In the 1980s researchers came out with new approaches to improve face recognition systems such as Template matching with "deformable templates" and ANN [7]. The year 1990 saw a broad face recognition approach using eigenfaces, ICA, PCA, LDA & their derivatives. Face detection is a process of extracting faces positively from the input image scenes or video stream [8][9]. Feature extraction such as face regions, variations, angles; eye spacing is done in the next step. The last step performs face recognition by comparing it with an image database.

The challenges faced by most face recognition systems are:

Pose Variation: Frontal images would be a condition for a face recognition system but this is an uncontrolled condition. Pose variation is one of the major research issues and this drops the performance of face detection systems. Pose variation depends on the image acquisition system and position which changes spatial coordinates in an acquired image leading to distortion. This variation affects traditional appearance-based face recognition methods like Eigen faces and fisher faces [11][14].

Face Occlusion: The presence of spectacles, beards or hats may cause problems in face detection. This is another main problem in face detection and identification systems.

Facial Expression: Facial features vary due to facial gestures and become difficult to identify. Facial expressions represent the feelings, tempers, and emotions of human beings. The variation in expression results in a change in spatial coordinates but also changes the shape of the face [15][16].

Illumination: Imaging systems and environmental variations affect the image quality. The illumination changes are being discussed in some face detection and identification systems. This variation is caused by different lighting conditions [17][18].

Clustering: The above four parameters make changes in original image facial appearances; hence it is necessary to consider the presence of all conditions and backgrounds around a person in acquired images. Avoiding these parameters affects face detection algorithms and reduces performance. Yan, Kriegman, and Ahuja divided face recognition techniques into four categories that may overlap, developing another algorithm that may consist of two or more categories [20][21].

The four categories are:

- (i) Knowledge-dependent Process: Identify faces based on information about humanoid faces.
- (ii) Invariant Feature Methods: Methods developed under this category recognize faces based on invariant features.
- (iii) Template Matching Methods: These methods try to correlate original images with database pattern images.
- (iv) Appearance Based Methods: This recognizes faces based on a set of training pictures.

Knowledge Depending Process: These use some knowledge about faces like ellipse shape and triangle features. Another set of rules which can be used, the face usually has two symmetric eyes and eyes are darker than cheeks. It measures the distance between eyes or intensity between eye areas. Knowledge-based methods can reduce the computation cost but they are rotation limited. If rules set are too universal, there could be more false rejections. The solution to overcome this problem is to develop hierarchical knowledge-based techniques. But these methods are limited and unable to find faces in complex images [26][27].

Feature-Invariant Methods: This makes use of features like edge, complexion, texture, and shape for face detection. These methods are rotation independent, scale-independent and fast. The method which is scale-independent, rotation independent can reduce computational cost. Building Face identification systems depend on skin complexion as a feature, the researcher

has three major issues, which complexion space to choose, modeling of skin complexion distribution, and a way to process skin complexion[29][30].

In image/vision processing, the complexion is used as a powerful tool to identify objects or features such as computer graphics, Colorimetry& video signal communication standards that have given many complexion spaces with dissimilar properties [31] [32].

(a) RGB: This cloudscape originated from CRT, it is defined as a mixture of Greenish color, Reddish color, and Blue color. This complexion space is the very extensively used information for saving image data. Combining luminance &chrominance with RGB is the unfavorable choice for complexion space [33].

(b) Normalized RGB: This is obtained from RGB by normalizing, $r=R/(R+G+B)$, $g=G/(R+G+B)$, $b=B/(R+G+B)$. The 'b' component has no significance, hence neglected. The remaining two components are called pure complexion, and normalized RGB does not vary due to light source. This property made this complexion space gain popularity among researchers [34].

(c) HSV, HSL- Hue, HSI, Saturation Value (Lightness, Intensity): Dominant complexion like red, purple, yellow is represented as Hue. Complexion brightness is measured using Saturation. Intensity, Lightness, and Value are related to luminance [35].

(d) TSL- Tint(T), Saturation(S), and Lightness(L): This complexion space is a transformation of normalized RGB, close to hue and saturation. Normalization of TSL within RGB is the advantage of TSL complexion space transform. Normalized values of r and g for TSL space are more effective during the skin segmentation approach. This normalization reduces the variability of skin complexion sensitivity and improves skin complexion detection rate. TSL complexion space is more efficient and robust after normalization. No complexion correction algorithms are existing for image acquisition devices. Despite all these efforts, detection of dark skin complexion is an open challenge to researchers [36].

(e) YCbCr: This complexion space is nonlinear encoded RGB, mostly used in European television for compressing images without loss of information. It is constructed by weighted sum RGB, Cr, and Cb, and complexion is represented as luminance. Cr is luminance difference red and Cb is luminance difference blue components. The luminance separation and components property of chrominance make this color space beautiful for skin colormodeling. The main objective of skin color segmentation is to separate the skin from the non-skin region. Human skin occupies a small region in a color space; hence it is best to build

a classifier that classifies skin from non-skin regions. In 1999, Yang and Ahuja used Luv color space with Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM), the authors concluded that the method worked for different types of skin but they failed to discuss intensity and true positive rate (TPR) and false-positive rate (FPR). In the year 1990, RGB color space with Bayes SPM achieved a TPR of 80% and FPR of 8.4% Mason made use of three different color spaces: RGB with Bayes Skin Probability Map (SPM) classifier, YIQ with I-axis threshold classifier & RGB with threshold ratios classifier [37]. The TPR of these three methods are 19.8%, 30.2% & 32.3% respectively. In 2000, another researcher used HSV color space with Max. Likelihood estimation which worked on different skin types, an attractive study on skin color spreading under different conditions of lighting was proposed which showed 125 individuals to lie inside a definite color space locus, writers used scatter matrices of non-skin & skin clusters [38]. The conclusions drawn were, separating skin and non-skin in RGB space & falling luminance will worsen the separation. In 2005, authors used five color space models with different classifiers but failed to achieve a TPR of more than 90%. In 2009, the authors used YCgCb + YCgCr with thresholding as a classifier and achieved 92.1% TPR with 6% of FPR. In 2010, YCbCr with 2D Gaussian Model and Bayesian Network (BN) achieved 96% of TPR with 15% of FPR. With the Literature Survey on Face detection using Skin Segmentation, it is concluded that a good classifier must distinguish between the skin and non-skin pixels of several persons having different skin hues like white, wheat, black & brown.

To expand the accuracy of the classifier, it is better to take into consideration other features such as motion, shape & size. If skin detection is a pre-processing step in any application, the authors concluded that it yields better results with 1D RGB colorspace. Other authors concluded that results can be improved using Hybrid color space i.e., a combination of different color spaces such as HSV+YCbCr, HSV+rgb, HSV+TSL+rgb. Meeting real-time application requirements such as computational and storage are extremely important [39][40].

H. Template Matching Methods: Template matching is one of the widest used methods for face identification because they are strong to noise, easy to use & take less time. In this method, the forward face images are already defined and kept in the system database. An Image processing algorithm is developed where the correlation between input and the stored image is performed to detect the face. But face detection algorithms suffer from illumination and variation of face feature shapes. One simple method to resolve this problem is to receive the usual face from the face examples & then keep them in the database, then the input

picture with a high association score is the position of the face. This process is known as the filter match process. The filter match process accepts Additive White Gaussian Noise (AWGN), which is not good for an image like variation, illumination, and expression. AWGN is noise added to images to investigate the performance of the proposed system. To reduce this high variation Appearance-based methods have been used by various authors. The association between input image and face template is similar to Normalized Cross-Correlation (NCC). But NCC is exaggerated by clutter background and illumination. This problematic situation can be resolved using Sum of Absolute Differences (SAD), but it is mostly cast-off for compression and tracking the object, hence SAD needs optimization. In 2012, authors proposed face detection using Optimized SAD (OSAD) instead of NCC to reduce the illumination effect. The results showed that OSAD is unaffected by variation of the pose but affected through the clutter as objects exist in it.

3.3 Related Works:

In Bruner, J. (1954) has written the perception of people which is hand book of social psychology where perception of people is clearly mention in [1]. Bledsoe et al. (1964) has designed the model method in facial recognition, panoramic research in which feature of facial recognition was highlights [2]. Chan et al. (1965) have proposed a man-machine facial recognition system where some preliminary results explained [3]. Bledsoe (1965) designed Man-machine facial recognition in which recognition was very effective modeled [4]. Bledsoe (1968) talked about semiautomatic facial recognition [5]. Kanade et al. (1974) explored picture processing systems by computer complex and recognition of human faces [6]. Nixon et al. (1985) explained eye spacing measurement for facial recognition in applications of digital image processing international society for optics and photonics [7]. Stonham et al. (1986) gave practical face recognition and verification with WIZARD in aspects of face processing [8]. Kirby et al. (1990) discussed the application of the Karhunen-Loeve procedure for the characterization of human faces [9]. Lee et al. (1997) have developed human factors guidelines for advanced traveler information systems (ATIS) and commercial vehicle operations (CEO) [10]. In Yuille et al. (1992). Feature extraction from faces using deformable templates [11]. Saito et al. (1992) explored does fatigue exists in a quantitative measurement of eye movements [12]. Ebisawa et al. (1993) conducted the effectiveness of the pupil area detection technique using two light sources and the image difference method [13]. Calcagnini et al. (1994, November) analyzed of heart rate variability signal during sleep stages of patients [14]. Klein et al. (Biological psychology.

Macmillan[15]. Pentland et al.(1994) proposed view-based and modular eigenspaces for face recognition [16]. Vanoli et al.(1995) found heart rate variability during specific sleep stages: a comparison of healthy subjects with patients after myocardial infarction. Wylie et al.(1996) proposed commercial motor vehicle driver fatigue and alertness study[18]. In [20] Wylie et al. have presented a study on the alertness of motor drivers when they are at various levels of fatigue. These findings of the research in [20] can be amply justified by the work of Toscani et al. in [19] which study the different sleep stages of men and their heart rates. Much of these studies have been done and the conclusions have been drawn by following the concepts of pattern recognition as invented by Woody Bledsoe [21]. Pigeon et al. (1997, March) have designed the M2VTS multimodal face [21]. Deng et al. (1997) have the region-based template deformation and masking for eye-feature extraction and description [22][23]. Reinders et al.(1996) have located facial features in image sequences using neural networks [24][25]. Huang et al.(1998) posted discrimination and eye detection using Support Vector Machines (SVM) [26]. Feng et al (xxx) developed variance projection function and its application to eye detection for human face recognition [27]. Ebisawa et al. (1998) have improved the video-based eye-gaze detection method [28]. Elsenbruch, et al. (1999) proposed heart rate variability during waking and sleep in healthy males and females [29]. Jones et al.(2002) have developed statistical color models with application to skin detection[30]. Meng, et al.(1999) have frontal face localization using linear discriminant [31]. In [32] Peters et al have discussed the effects of partial and total sleep deprivations on driving performance. In [33] Yang et al. have developed a mixture model for various skin colors and used these models in evaluating images in various databases and of image and video files. In [34], Sigal, et al. presented a research on estimation and prediction of evolving color distributions for skin segmentation. In [35], Brand et al. have presented a comparative assessment of three approaches to pixel-level human skin-detection. The work of Jain et al.[36] on Statistical pattern recognition needs to be noted here for presenting the concepts of pattern recognition in a single treatise. In [37], Haro et al. presented a study of detecting and tracking eyes by using their physiological properties, dynamics, and appearance. In [38] another research on dual-state parametric eye-tracking has been presented by Dang et al. In [39] a technique is introduced for multi-cues eye detection on gray intensity image. The paper in [40] studies the effects of light and sleep stages on heart rate variability in humans. The paper in [42] introduces a mixture model for face-color modeling and segmentation[41]. The article in [42] gives us basis functions of the color signals of skin under different illuminants. Ji et al. in [43], presented real-time visual cues extraction for monitoring driver vigilance. Viola et al. (2001)

have rapid object detection using a boosted cascade of simple features [44]. Vijayalaxmi et al. (2020). Image processing-based eye detection methods a theoretical review [45]. Vijayalaxmi et al. (2020). Implementation of the face and eye detection on DM6437 board using Simulink model [46]. Biradar, et al. (2018) have hardware prototyping for video and signal processing applications using dm 6437 texas instrument evaluation board [47]. Biradar, et al. (2018) have DM3730 Processor Hardware Debugging on Linux Platform [48]. Motwani et al. (2004) have eye detection using wavelets and ANN [49]. Chaudhry et al. (2017) have face detection and recognition in an unconstrained environment for the mobile visual assistive system. Mliki et al. (2020) have an improved multi-scale face detection using a convolutional neural network [51]. Ganapathi, et al. (2020) have unconstrained ear detection using an ensemble-based convolutional neural network model [52]. Nada, et al. (2018) have pushed the limits of unconstrained face detection: a challenge dataset and baseline results [53]. Zhou et al. (2018) in [54] have presented a survey of face detection on low-quality images. Sahu et al. (2018) have the modeling of attacks in sigma-delta ADC for hardware security [54]. Zhang et al. (2019) have fareboxes: A CPU real-time and accurate unconstrained face detector [55]. Yang et al. (2017) have faceless-net: Face detection through deep facial part responses [56]. Ravidas et al. (2019) have deep learning for pose-invariant face detection in the unconstrained environment [57]. Lu et al. (2017) have feature extraction and fusion using deep convolutional neural networks for face detection [58]. Sawat et al. (2020) have pixel encoding for unconstrained face detection [59]. Kneis, et al. (2018) explored face detection for crowd analysis using deep convolutional neural networks [60]. Oloyede et al. (2018) discussed Improving face recognition systems using a new image enhancement technique, hybrid features, and the convolutional neural network [61]. Bekhet, et al. (2022) have gender recognition from unconstrained selfie images: a convolutional neural network approach [62]. Ranjan, et al. (2019) designed a fast and accurate system for face detection, identification, and verification [63]. Salman et al. (2020) have automatic fish detection in underwater videos by a deep neural network-based hybrid motion learning system [64].

Methods Based on Appearance: These templates are learned from images examples. These procedures depend on statistics and machine learning face characteristics. In 1986 & 1990, face recognition systems were developed efficiently using PCA where the face is represented as a vector coordinate system. These vectors are known as eigenvectors (Kirby, M., and Sirovich, L. (1990)) [8][9]. In 1997, few researchers developed a neural network-based face recognition system. The detection system consisted of 2 classes, non-face and face class. The real challenge in neural network-based approaches is training and representing

images not containing faces. Support Vector Machines (SVMs) are used to increase the margin between decision and training hyperplanes because they are considered linear classifiers (Pigeon, S., and Vandendrope, L., 1997)[65]. Recognizing human faces under different conditions like 5year old boy, grandma's wedding photo, face occluded, and a person with a beard is trivial but not impossible. So, they are a challenge to computers. The core problem in the recognition stage is feature selection. This feature selection process is described as a method of removing applicable information from the original image. This data is given as input to the next step with minimum error. While developing a classifier, care should be taken such that the FPR of the classifier should not increase. The TPR and FPR depend on training samples, if the training samples are relatively smaller in number when compared to features then a problem called "peaking phenomenon" occurs which can be avoided by considering training samples ten times per class of several features. As the classifier complexity increases, a large number of training examples is required. The correctness of the classifier depends on the number of features selected while training the classifier.

3.4 Objectives:

The objectives of the proposed work are as follow:

- (1) To feed the constructed neural network, to train several general facial expressions.
- (2) To obtain high efficiency as well as the feasibility of the proposed method to deal with multi-scale face detection problems.
- (3) To introduce a technique that is employed by different studies like matching the template, Hough Transform, and Eigenvectors. HSV for eliminating all unnecessary pixels in the picture excluding Face & Neural Network, categorize the picture as Face / non-Face.

3.5 Proposed Algorithm:

The selected algorithm consists of two stages. The first stage is the training stage and the second stage is the detection stage. The executed stage is divided by neural network and preprocessing steps through the Gabor filter. Otherwise, the manual separation of the interest region and most important feature selection through color model happens in training. In the initial stage, the automatic removal of the eyes region by color model and eye candidate's separation is performed by morphological operation.

3.5.1 Database:

Some databases are used in both stages such as GATV, VITS, Face expression, and Math Works. This stage is performed by different conditions like hairstyle, various facial expressions, condition of illumination, etc. This preformation happens by including up to five hundred grayscale images and five hundred color images of dissimilar sizes. This work used thousands of images for training purposes and approximately a thousand numbers of images for testing.

Fig.3.1: Block Diagram of Database Image

3.6 Training Methodology:

For training the neural network a huge number of no face and face images are required in the first step. Approximately two hundred faces are cropped from several pictures and gathered. That image contains different sizes of face, position, orientation, with glass, with occlusion, etc. These pictures were used to control every face at a similar scale, same position, same alignment, etc. The stages are given below:

- (1) Reset FF which is a vector and will be the normal position of every feature labeled for entire faces with the location of the feature in the 1st face.
- (2) These features synchronize in FF by rotation, translation, and scaling. For this step, the face location averagely appears at a determined location with a 32 x 20-pixel window. In this stage, 40 face specimens are generated from an image by circulating the image at their center up to a hundred scaling in between 90% - 100%, interpreting up to $\frac{1}{2}$ pixel and reflecting for training. Normally, all images can work as a non-eye specimen because the non-eye image space is ample larger than the eye image space. Though, representative collection for non-eye computer sets and information technology is very problematic. Instead of image collection

before the training starts, the image can be collected in the training period in the following manner, taken from [13].

(a) By producing fifty random images, make a preliminary group of non-face images. After that apply the above steps in all of these images.

(b) Train the neural network for producing the input 1 for face image and 0 for non-face image.

(c) Run the system on the set of images that consist of no face. Gather the sub-images in which the network improperly specifies the face (the activation output > 0).

(d) For example, select approximately 40 sub-images randomly, put on the previous steps and add all selected faces into the set of training. For the second step, some non-face examples are collected at the time of training as shown in figure 3.2. It should be reserved in mind that the face which is not very close is the positive example which is shown in figure 3.3. This example precisely gives the boundary between non-face images and faces images. Here we used two hundred sets of images for gathering the negative examples as per the above description. For training neural networks, the non-face and face images are used which is shown in the following figure.

Figure 3.2: Examples of eye shapes from the test & training sets.

Figure 3.3: Examples of non-face shapes from the testand training sets.

3.6.1. Gabor filters:

Daugman gives a proposal on a two-dimensional Gabor function to structure the properties of spatial summation (of accessible field) for modest cells in the graphic cortex. They are largely used in computer vision, image dispensation, psychophysics, and neuroscience. Functions visualization of Gabor use Gabor filter for some purposes like removal of texture feature by detection of edge, by simulate complex and simple cell (visual cortex), by simulation of non-classical open field inhibition/edge suppression & use this for detection of object outline, describe certain effects (visual perception). The image examples are applied in the following Gabor function of equation (3.1),(3.2),(3.3) which is two-dimensional:

$$g(x,y) = \exp\left(-x' + \frac{y^2y'}{2\sigma^2}\right) \cos\left(\frac{2\pi x}{\lambda} + \phi\right) \dots\dots\dots (3.1)$$

Where

$$x' = x \cos \theta + y \sin \theta \dots\dots\dots (3.2)$$

$$y' = -x \sin \theta + y \cos \theta \dots\dots\dots (3.3)$$

The definite value parameters of the Gabor function are orientation, wavelength, aspect ratio, bandwidth, and phase offset. These functions are estimated and shown as image map intensity in the production window. Light grey colors represent positive function value and dark grey color represents negative function value. The output image and input image size are the same. By altering various parameters, the set of training data produced by Gabor Filter Kernel such as orientation, wavelength, angle of rotation, etc. which are shown below in the following figure 3.4.

Figure 3.4: Gabor Filter Kernel by various alignment, angle, and wavelength

3.6.2 Neural network:

The networks will collect 960 actual values in a 960-pixel image as an input (size of image approximately= 32 x 20). Then it is essential to detect the face by replying by an output vector [25]. The output of the vector represents a non-face and face. For correct operation, the network should give 1 if the face is present and otherwise the network should give 0 in [25]. Additionally, the network must be able to manage the non-face image. Practically the network will not detect the faultless image of the eye which is denoted by the input vector.

3.6.3 Neural network Architecture:

To identify the eyes, the neural network required 960 output & input layers to point out the eyes. This network is like a 2-layer log-sigmoid network. The log-sigmoid transfer function had been taken as the range of output is 0 to 1 which is an exact range for the study of Boolean standards output [25]. The secret layer has two hundred neurons [25]. These numbers were collected through experience and guesswork. If this network feels distressed in education, then neurons may be an addition to this layer. These networks are skilled based on 1 as output & 0 like non-eye recognition. Through, the non-eye images may give a network that does not create one and zero perfectly. After making the network skilled, the output will be sent by the modest transfer function shown in figure 3.5.

Figure 3.5: Architecture of Neural Network

3.7 Testing Methodology:

At the time of testing, the neural network reliability is estimated by network testing by a hundred numbers of images (input) of several circumstances. In this work, an algorithm is produced for separating eyes from the images (input) which are given. The selected algorithm is shown in the following figure. By extracting the skin region, the algorithm works with face removal by transforming the color space structure. The face is sensed by removing unnecessary space using color space (HSV) and to remove extra areas Morphological operation is used. The selected algorithm is given below in figure 3.6.

Figure 3.6: Selected Algorithm.

The 1st step is detecting the face separating the human face from the sequence of images. A simple search procedure in the video will not assist to select the face in between the additional organizational face components like mustache, beard, etc. Those problems become complicated by live images like video, as the available time for searching in every image is limited. An effective face selection feature is human skin color.

Many different color places have been used to pixels stage as skin with RGB, regularized RGB, HSV [18], [24], [20], [19], YIQ, XYZ, & YCbCr [21]. The proposed method in this paper includes skin recognition to remove the background of components tracked through the detection of the eye.

Skin area removal assists in estimating the estimated location of the eye by removing a huge number of wrong eye candidates. The additional expansion was made on the algorithm which is based on skin color. For color description, RGB color space is an efficient algorithm and it is used terribly. Therefore, every coordinate such as green, red & blue does not give necessary related data about whether a specific picture has skin or not as that image has luminance effects from image intensity. To improve the color representation, a Lab color model is used. It has a three-dimensional color space in which color alterations are perceived to be similarly large and also have the same distance between them. For face segmentation, a Lab color model is applied. In the selected algorithm, the model of lab color is useful subsequently for applying the color space of HSV and forgetting the actual region of the eye.

It has been noticed that this does not eliminate the entire skin from the picture but the minor image portion stays in it. As this is a Morphological operation, it is considered as a benefit. These remaining skin areas can be efficiently eliminated by this Morphological Operation. Lastly, the eyes are separated from the removed face image by HSV structure & Morphological operations which are shown in the following figure. The extracted features of the above algorithm are given into sorting by the skilled SVM. After the execution step, the consequences are estimated by some measurements like specificity, accuracy, and sensitivity. Specificities are denoted by $TN / (FP + TN)$, accurateness is denoted by $(TN + TP) / (TN + TP + FN + FP)$ and sensitivity is denoted by $TP / (FN + TP)$, Where TN stands for true-negative, FP stands for false-positive, FN stands for false-negative and TP stands for true-positive.

3.8 Contribution and Highlights of Finding:

The selected algorithm is applied on some databases like GATV, VITS, MATH WORK, and FACE EXPRESSION. That algorithm is applied on more than 500 images in the automatic extraction stage on the face region. In figure 3.7(a) a successfully detected face image is shown. Also, in figure 3.7(b) a detected failed image is shown. It has been observed that maximum errors arise due to the face position, especially when the image of a face is moving aside, a distance of face and eye closer. The maximum efficiency of the selected algorithm is estimated on 500 pictures on which the detected region of eyes flourished. The result of the evaluation is very high like sensitivity is 88.7%, specificity is 95.3% & accuracy is 89.3%. Figure 7 shows the picture of the non-face region. It is concluded that the error arise if the region of eyes were dark, similarities with eyebrows and background region & hair.

Input Image	Face Detected Image
(a)	

(b)

Figure 3.7 (a): Showing successful detection of Face; **(b):** Failure images

3.9 Summary:

Face detection nowadays has become a very essential issue for various applications. In this process, the face should be separated after removing unnecessary portions such as skin, background, & other human parts of the selected image. Many techniques are employed by different studies like matching the template, Hough Transform, and Eigenvectors. The proposed method includes Lab color spaces as well as HSV for eliminating all unnecessary pixels in the picture excluding Face & Neural Network categorize the picture as Face / non-Face. These experiments were performed by taking 100 pictures of various head persons, taken from the available standard databases & VITS database made in the time of the research work. The rate of success on selected algorithms is ninety-eight percent; the two percent unsuccessful rate in results is for some reason like background, head movement & due inappropriate training. The efficiency of the selected algorithm can be predictable based on Specificity, Accuracy & Sensitivity. The estimated values are 95.2%, 88.6% & 89.2% correspondingly. For up-gradation, the authors remain the work on the subject.

Chapter - 4

DESIGN AND EXECUTION OF FACE RECOGNITION SYSTEM BY USING GENETIC ALGORITHM

4.1 Overview

The presented work demonstrates, Face Recognition System initiated by using GA (Genetic algorithm). This scheme approaches and entails for brilliance advantage popular audiovisual effects, displaying, piece mining, arrangement, documentation, etc. This paper also suggests the use of normal GA and improved GA and is applicable for the problems of face recognition or pattern recognition systems. An image file consists of a large number of evidence and individualities. Still in modern days, a whole effective machinery to elaborate these features in systemic ways is not possible. Mentioning the facial expression of images, and its recognition in a duplicate image is a problem that involves a scrupulous examination because of its extraordinary complication. In this work, an attempt was made to scrutinize the characteristics of GA in face recognition applications. GA is considered to be one of the best possible search methods encouraged by the theory of Darwin Evolutionist. GA is well-organized in the terms of sinking calculation time for a huge headspace. For face appreciation systems the proportion of society is strong virtually and perfect stability is more than 85%. It has been found and arranged for a further research study for face recognition applications systems. GA can be also observed as calculating prototypes that may be encouraged by the functional and structural of the normal and improved algorithm techniques; however this process's techniques do not contain a single call to the preparation of function but are accomplished numerous times dealing with various images and inputs which contents face. In this proposed replicas remain predictable to covenant by delinquent resolving in a manner with various ways of conservative computing. Dissimilarity has been made between data and the pattern to accentuate the necessity for proposing the pattern systems that report pattern recognition tasks. The Face recognition system consists of an identical massive Heap-space that includes time-intense tasks therefore GA based methodology is being used to identify the unaccusable -copy inside a specific period. Design and Execution of Face Recognition System by using Genetic Algorithm. Face Recognition System is initiated by using genetic algorithm. This scheme approaches and entails for brilliance advantage popular audiovisual effects, displaying, piece mining, arrangement, documentation, etc. For face appreciation systems the proportion of society is strong virtually and perfect stability is more than 85%. It has been found and arranged for a further research study for face recognition applications

systems. This paper also suggests the use of normal GA and improved GA (Genetic Algorithm) and applicable for the problems of face recognition or pattern recognition systems. An image file consists of a large number of evidence and individualities. This proposed research has been found and arranged for a further research study for face recognition applications systems. This paper also suggests the use of normal GA and improved GA (Genetic Algorithm) and applicable for the problems of face recognition or pattern recognition systems. An image file consists of a large number of evidence and individualities. In this proposed replicas remain predictable to covenant by delinquent resolving in a manner with various ways of conservative computing. Dissimilarity has been made between data and the pattern to accentuate the necessity for proposing the pattern systems that report pattern recognition tasks. The Face recognition system consists of an identical massive Heap-space that includes time-intense tasks therefore GA based methodology is being used to identify the unaccusable -copy inside a specific period.

4.2 Overviews:

There are various ongoing identifications being used for face recognition technology which is primarily focusing in terms of significant research direction. The procedure for the recognition of face technology is modest, and faster recognition technology which is having various advantages of decent intuition and stealthiest. These primary features are similarly more to additional biometric machinery. Besides, the FRS is thoroughly connected through some additional approaches on the biometric substantiation and manmade computer communication for research awareness. The face recognition system contains some basic preparation and testing. This training and testing unit contains the face recognition, face position, retesting, image mining, image assortment, deceitful classifications etc. Primary method of techniques essentially contains expression recognition besides, pre-define, abstraction, medley then decoration sorting. (1-5)

The Expression discovery then locating remains in primary focus for appreciation and secondary story are insertion which both are achievement of documentation. Proposal process of cataloging is central for all recognition. So as to recompense for those imperfections around the impulsive merging of GA which progress the correctness of that process. Herein proposed work, a normal GA and improved GA algorithm are incorporated to variations of suitability utility & GA operatives that vary the technique for appropriate boundary and transformation prospect. This proposed algorithm not only permits exploration for the finest

distinct nearby towards the international finest elucidation, nevertheless it decreases the searching period of systems. (6-8)

The Numeral Images are consuming such enormous evidence and appearances as these remain supplementary multifaceted, so till nowadays, a widespread well-organized appliance to cutting these features which are yet to be discoverable. Mentioning facial recognition, the aforementioned recognition in an image which has a specific problem that involves tons of examination due to its great complexity and indiscretions. The tradition of these images is actually wide and inclusive, for example the security schemes case, wherever it is targeted for distant conference, exploration in folder, people documentation etc. Now a day's situation has upsurge of terrorist attacks, stimulates uncountable mechanisms in this range. Security cameras are located like; in superstores, subways, downtown shopping centers, parks, buses, and many more places, demanding support for the documentation of awkward people, moreover sinking crimes and illegal belongings that are trendy in the neighborhood. Inappropriately, up till now, security systems need to be modernized in terms of human management that sources important disasters. In this present paper, to overcome the present scenario, recommend an examination of the GA method algorithm application for facial recognition, so that it will resolve the one stage for appearance appreciation. Permitting to the GA algorithm remains considered as one of the primary search methods stimulated by the theory of Darwin Evolutionary. The designed exhausting certain variety of mechanisms used in Nature, rendered by those entities who are capable in a populace to take additional survival opportunities, once familiarizing themselves further simply to the vagaries that happen in their surroundings. Mortal problematic resolving is fundamentally a shape dispensation difficult but purely a data processing delinquent. In some recognition task humans observe decorations in the involvement data and operate the pattern openly. So here we endeavor at emerging computing representations constructed on normal GA algorithms which deal with numerous pattern recognition circumstances in actual natural life through the assistance of advance GA. (9-13)

4.3 Research Methodology:

This chapter consists of dependable face recognition system method constructed on the normal GA and improved GA procedure. Originally, conceivable face regions remain produced by revenues of the inherent algorithm and the convenient appreciation of the similar process that was done by genetic algorithm. In this technique exists additional vigor that seemly suitable for stumpy resolve, mutable illumination and dissimilar facial terminologies which is More Applicable for Actual Solitary, Various Aspects.

4.4 Interim Objectives:

The interim objectives of this chapter are dependable face recognition system method constructed on the normal GA and improved GA procedure.

(1) To get capability by means of improved look searching, greatest method of scrabbling plus efficient method for verge discovery, piece abstraction for copy. Obtained outcome for proposed scheme is created to be enhanced one.

(2) To PESTLE analysis is a tool used to gain a macro picture of an industry environment. PESTLE stands for Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Legal and Environmental factors which allow forming an impression of the factors that might impact new methods for development.

4.5 Related Works:

There are many various recognition approaches and we now recapitulate some of them. Various authors in there proposed worked defined some different approaches by using a face recognition system on mobile phones based on the input image, by using Viola-Jones algorithm. The primary goal of the system is to save time and make cooler access for penetrating pictures. Some authors also discussed a new application for face appreciation on mobile devices based on Bridge based Approach (BA) to improve the speed up the treating and it permits using the arrangement in any setting where an internet is accessible. Face detection and article abstraction are executed using Open library, nonetheless the face recognition is performed in GA algorithm. The expansion and implementation of a face recognition system for the platform by including face and eye detection and applying a set of preprocessing for using normal GA and Improved GA algorithms.

Table 4.1: Recognition Methods and Recognition Rate with its Approaches

Recognition Method	Recognition rate (%)	Approaches Reference
PCA	82.10%	[35]
Eigen Faces	83.20%	[36]
Fishers Faces	85%	
WIKI library	80%	[37]
PCA	83.50%	[38]
LDA	84.20%	
Correlation coefficient for the 1 st system	83.20%	[39]
Correlation coefficient for the 2 nd system	84.60%	
Normal GA	85%	Our Proposed Work
Improved GA	92.12%	

4.6 Proposed Model

This proposed system model figure 4.1, supported of Recognition of Faces which is identify the manifestation of a face for resolute region of the image. To identify the face previously exasperating to identify it and avoids a lot of exertion, however now merely a constrained section of the image is evaluated, which is contrary different to many algorithms that exertion bearing in mind the entire image. Proposed system project then employment of the FRS is segmented to double foremost portions. Firstly it treating images and the secondly it has acknowledgement Performances. The image treating part contains of Face image acquirement concluded scanning, development, feature, Sifting, the Edge detection and abstraction. The additional quantity contains of the Artificial Intelligence that algorithm will resolve the persistence of recognition measure which is specified in the figure1.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4.1: Schematic representation of (a) face detection system and Normalization

(1) GA Process Steps

GA Process is considered through a pursuit procedure that encouraged in the theory of Darwin by Evolutionist, which uses particular arrangement mechanism. Somewhere characters that are the chromosomes additional improved of a population that have more existence probabilities, by receiving used of simply to variations that arise in its atmosphere. This procedure creates the

algorithm in a solid and fast, existence term to a resolute type of optimization; somewhere the explorationinterplanetaryremains too immense and the predictable approaches become incompetent. Additional GA is essential to distinguishing is that outcome a set of explanations and not merely one result.

FLOW CHART OF PROPOSED GA METHODS:

This flowchart of the suggested GA process is in the subsequent phases:

Step 1: Beginning a populace of N-size, by genetic material produced arbitrarily.

Step 2: Spread over appropriateness to each chromosome of populace.

Step 3: To make an oval genetic material concluded in trisections of designated of this inhabitants for spread over combination and transformation in that process.

Step 4: Eradicate participants of old populace, in direction of these new chromosomes and observance the inhabitants through the similar N-genetic material.

Step 5: To spread on the appropriateness in these genetic material and enclosure them for populace.

Step 6: Inultimateexplanation it will be initiate or not if the peer’s number exhausted and yield the chromosome. Else, come back to the **Step 3**.

Above statement is represented in the flowchart in figure 2.

Figure 4.2: Flow Chart of Planned GA

(2) Analysis of GA algorithm

The investigation of basic GA (genetic algorithm) and enhancedGA on the foundation of the proposed systems. (14-24) this paper depicts confirmed the form of the conjunction of the restatement, iteration time, and this recognition rate and dimensions. This segment picked the process that computing the data appreciation value which has constructed happening sustenance trajectory apparatus uses mixed verification. (25-39).In conjunction in between procedures is presented in the Fig. 4.3 & 4.4.

Figure 4.3: Schematic consequence of conjunction of the elementary normal GA.

Figure 4.4: Schematic outcome for conjunction for simple improved GA.

In figure 4.3 and figure 4.4 depicts, red camber signifies the beyond current cohort for finest specific ability arc and navy color curve signifies the typical suitability of fashionable arc. The elementary GA is informal to reduction made about native optimum elucidation. Through the growth in quantity of repetitions, the operative cannot products novel GA beings to make certain the variety of the population, it is also been reserved to the greatest characters in the afterward group. In diagram 4, subsequently the enhanced GA process takes upgraded genetic machinist and suitability utility, which greatest distinct continually has modernized near invention of worldwide ideal elucidation.

For enactment Evaluation on repetition period, physiognomies measurements as well as appreciation value about two methods is depicts in tabular 4.2. Obtained value is 25 intervals approximately the exam value.

Table 4.2: Enactment relationship between GA processes.

	Unique Piece Measurement	Piece Measurement after Assortment	Progressed (%)	Reiteration period (sec)
Improved GA	640	310	98	122.27
Normal GA	640	321	97	126.57

Source: Figure 4.3 & Figure 4.4. In this tabular, enhanced GA takes enlarged gratitude amount as associates a simple GA (genetic algorithm), meanwhile the international penetrating of enhanced better for simple algorithm; for periodic some time released in together steps is very dissimilar. For enhanced this steps guarantees the appreciation value contains significantly decrease repetition phase, rather than actual essential concurrent applications. For enhanced data flow which upgraded GA process is portrayed in graph 5.

Figure 4.5: Movement plan of enhanced GA process.

4.7 Result And Simulation

The obtained results for FR are shown in Figure 4.6 & 4.7 respectively (by using standard lenna image).

Figure 4.6: FR results constructed by upgraded GA value.

Figure 4.7: FR results constructed by normal GA methods.

Figure 4.6&4.7, represents the improved GA and usualGA which is having a good performance picture whereas a solo picture has a convinced crack for ultimate pic extents. Comparatively, enhanced GA decreases preparation period.

Procedure for obtaining the face location:

For obtaining the Face Recognition, permitting to the stages of normal and improved genetic algorithm and then remove and inferior the feature of the selected image (here we use lenna image). Then after, consumption vector machine organization. Detailed organization process is depicted in Figure 8 as given below.

Figure 4.8: Steps for obtaining the face location

(2) Test Analysis:

This segment examines to verify data from the successive pieces, covered or not covered which depends on the concentration of light, variations of the facial expression, face positivity and side of the face. Every test has six different curriculums which has every person was tested more than 40 times. Lastly optimum results were analyze recognition rate .Here1 women (lenna) has black and white casing inclines, which takes4 variable represents gradients dark. Final optimum outcomesforexaminationsdepicts in tabular 4.3 and tabular 4.4 given below;

Table 4.3: Face performance observance

	Face Obscured	FR Value (%)	FR Disguised value	Appreciation value (%)
1	44	92	48	92
2	45	94	47	95
3	46	98	45	96
4	48	96	44	93
5	46	95	43	94
6	45	93	42	93
Average	45.66	94.66	44.83	93.83

Table 4.4: Face performance observance in under intensity of light.

	Normal	R(%)	Bright	R(%)	Dim	R(%)
1	44	92	46	92	43	96
2	42	93	44	94	44	93
3	45	96	47	96	42	94
4	46	98	43	92	41	96
5	42	93	43	96	46	93
6	46	91	44	91	46	91
Average	44.1	93.83	44.5	93.5	43.66	93.83

**Here, R: recognition rate

From Table 3, it has been seen that when the face is thwarted a slight consequence on recognizing the face. The reason behind this, once the taster reference reading room takes covered of facial, then its determination precisely remain recognized. From reduction, an acknowledgment frequency is predominantly less owing to an impediment once particular stimulus on the social face detection. In table 4, when light intensity consumes an important control of FRs arrangement then it is also durable or else feeble, however it has an immoral consequence on recognition.

FINDINGS:

Proposed System is initiated by using genetic algorithm. This scheme approaches and entails for brilliance advantage popular audiovisual effects, displaying, piece mining, arrangement, documentation, etc. For face appreciation systems the proportion of society is strong virtually and perfect stability is more than 85%. It has been found and arranged for a further research study for face recognition applications systems. This paper also suggests the use of normal GA and improved GA (Genetic Algorithm) and applicable for the problems of face recognition or pattern recognition systems. An image file consists of a large number of evidence and individualities.

4.8 Suggestions:

In this technique exists additional vigor that seemly suitable for stumpy resolve, mutable illumination and dissimilar facial terminologies which is more applicable for actual solitary, various aspects. The capability canister is better than earlier by means of improved look searching, greatest method of scrabbling plus efficient method for verge discovery, piece abstraction for copy. Obtained outcome for proposed scheme is created to be enhanced one. In addition to this it is really applicable and suitable for improved face recognition systems that are able to be considered for multi-layer detection.

4.9 Summary:

This proposed work, we have demonstrated a supplementary dependable face recognition system method constructed on the normal GA and improved GA procedure. Initially, conceivable face regions remain produced by revenues of the inherent algorithm and the convenient appreciation of the similar process that was done by genetic algorithm. In this

technique exists additional vigor that seemly suitable for stumpy resolve, mutable illumination and dissimilar facial terminologies which is more applicable for actual solitary, various aspects. The capability canister is better than earlier by means of improved look searching, greatest method of scrabbling plus efficient method for verge discovery, piece abstraction for copy. Obtained outcome for proposed scheme is created to be enhanced one. In addition to this it is really applicable and suitable for improved face recognition systems that are able to be considered for multi-layer detection. However, this paper also established that FRS conventions are a normal genetic process and provides an improved GA algorithm which phases by consuming a grouping of sorting processes .Finally; this one provides a stage for better genetic and adjacent national FR solicitation. Even though a further study development in this chapter has a certain limitation on values, this paper also needs significant development till to mark additional investigation that occurs practical to repetition. Continuation demands are also prepared for features: communal amalgamation for variability based on man making revealing techniques and emerging application of real-time procurement device that will be suitable for concurrent progress of FRS.

Chapter -5

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE SCOPE

5.1 Conclusions

- Face detection now a day has become a very essential issue for various applications. In this process, the face should be separated after removing unnecessary portions such as skin, background, & other human parts of the selected image.
- Many techniques are employed by different studies like matching the template, Hough Transform, and Eigenvectors.
- The proposed method includes Lab color spaces as well as HSV for eliminating all unnecessary pixels in the picture excluding Face & Neural Network categorize the picture as Face / non-Face.
- These experiments were performed by taking 100 pictures of various head persons, taken from the available standard databases & VITS database made in the time of the research work.
- The rate of success on selected algorithms is ninety-eight percent; the two percent unsuccessful rate in results is for some reason like background, head movement & due inappropriate training.
- The efficiency of the selected algorithm can be predictable based on Specificity, Accuracy & Sensitivity. The estimated values are 95.2%, 88.6% & 89.2% correspondingly.
- This proposed work, we have demonstrated a supplementary dependable face recognition system method constructed on the normal GA and improved GA procedure.
- Initially, conceivable face regions remain produced by revenues of the inherent algorithm and the convenient appreciation of the similar process that was done by genetic algorithm. In this technique exists additional vigor that seemly suitable for stumpy resolve, mutable illumination and dissimilar facial terminologies which is more applicable for actual solitary, various aspects.
- The capability canister is better than earlier by means of improved look searching, greatest method of scrabbling plus efficient method for verge discovery, piece abstraction for copy. Obtained outcome for proposed scheme is created to be enhanced one.

- In addition to this it is really applicable and suitable for improved face recognition systems that are able to be considered for multi-layer detection. However, this work also established that FRS conventions are a normal genetic process and provides an improved GA algorithm which phases by consuming a grouping of sorting processes.
- Finally, this one provides a stage for better genetic and adjacent national FR solicitation. Even though a further study development in this chapter has a certain limitation on values, this also needs significant development till to mark additional investigation that occurs practical to repetition.
- Continuation demands are also prepared for features: communal amalgamation for variability based on man making revealing techniques and emerging application of real-time procurement device that will be suitable for concurrent progress of FRS.

5.2 Future Scope:

- The efficiency of the selected algorithm will be predictable based on Specificity, Accuracy & Sensitivity.
- FRS conventions will be normal genetic process and provides an improved GA algorithm which phases by consuming a grouping of sorting processes.
- Many techniques will employed by different studies like matching the template, Hough Transform, and Eigenvectors.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Ballantyne, M., Boyer, R. S., & Hines, L. (1996). Woody bledsoe: His life and legacy. *AI magazine*, 17(1), 7-7. Google Scholar Link
- [2]. Bekhet, S., Alghamdi, A. M., & Taj-Eddin, I. (2022). Gender recognition from unconstrained selfie images: a convolutional neural network approach. *International Journal of Electrical & Computer Engineering* , 12(2), 2245-2257. Google Scholar Link
- [3]. Biradar, V., Reddy, B. M., & Anumandla, K. K. (2018). Hardware prototyping for video and signal processing applications using dm 6437 texas instrument evaluation board. *International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics*, 20(6), 4127-4138. Google Scholar Link
- [4]. Biradar, V., Reddy, B. M., & Anumandla, K. K. (2018, October). DM3730 Processor Hardware Debugging on Linux Platform. In *2018 4th International Conference for Convergence in Technology (I2CT)* (pp. 1-4). IEEE. Google Scholar Link
- [5]. Black, M. J., & Yacoob, Y. (1997). Recognizing facial expressions in image sequences using local parameterized models of image motion. *International Journal of Computer Vision*, 25(1), 23-48. Google Scholar Link
- [6]. Bledsoe, W. W. (1964). *The model method in facial recognition, panoramic research inc., Palo Alto*. CA, Technical Report, Technical Report PRI: 15(1), 23-45. Google Scholar Link
- [7]. Bledsoe, W. W. (1965). Man-machine facial recognition: Report on a large scale experiment. *Technical report print 22, Panoramic Research, Inc., Palo Alto, California*, 3(2), 234-256. Google Scholar Link
- [8]. Bledsoe, W. W. (1968). Semiautomatic facial recognition. *Technical reportsriproject6693*. [https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=en&as_sdt=0%2C5&q=Semiautomatic+facial+recognition.+Technical+report+sri+project+6693.&btnG date of visit 3 April 2022] Google Scholar Link

- [9]. Brand, J., & Mason, J. S. (2000, September). A comparative assessment of three approaches to pixel-level human skin-detection. In *Proceedings 15th International Conference on Pattern Recognition. ICPR-2000* (Vol. 1, pp. 1056-1059). IEEE. Google Scholar Link
- [10]. Bruner, J. (1954). The perception of people. *Handbook of social psychology*. (pp. 123-145). Google Scholar Link
- [11]. Calcagnini, G., Biancalana, G., Giubilei, F., Strano, S., & Cerutti, S. (1994, November). Spectral analysis of heart rate variability signal during sleep stages. In *Proceedings of 16th Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society* (Vol. 2, pp. 1252-1253). IEEE. Google Scholar Link
- [12]. Chan, H., & Bledsoe, W. W. (1965). A man-machine facial recognition system: some preliminary results. *Panoramic Research Inc., Palo Alto, CA, USA 1965*. Google Scholar Link
- [13]. Chaudhry, S., & Chandra, R. (2017). Face detection and recognition in an unconstrained environment for mobile visual assistive system. *Applied Soft Computing*, 53, 168-180. Google Scholar Link
- [14]. Deng, J. Y., & Lai, F. (1997). Region-based template deformation and masking for eye-feature extraction and description. *Pattern recognition*, 30(3), 403-419. Google Scholar Link
- [15]. Ebisawa, Y. (1998). Improved video-based eye-gaze detection method. *IEEE Transactions on instrumentation and measurement*, 47(4), 948-955. Google Scholar Link
- [16]. Ebisawa, Y., & Satoh, S. I. (1993, October). Effectiveness of pupil area detection technique using two light sources and image difference method. In *Proceedings of the 15th Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society* (pp. 1268-1269). IEEE. Google Scholar Link

- [17]. Elsenbruch, S., Harnish, M. J., & Orr, W. C. (1999). Heart rate variability during waking and sleep in healthy males and females. *Sleep*, 22(8), 1067-1071. [Google Scholar Link](#)
- [18]. Feng, G. C., & Yuen, P. C. (1998). Variance projection function and its application to eye detection for human face recognition. *Pattern Recognition Letters*, 19(9), 899-906. [Google Scholar Link](#)
- [19]. Feng, G. C., & Yuen, P. C. (2001). Multi-cues eye detection on gray intensity image. *Pattern recognition*, 34(5), 1033-1046. [Google Scholar Link](#)
- [20]. Ganapathi, I. I., Prakash, S., Dave, I. R., & Bakshi, S. (2020). Unconstrained ear detection using ensemble- based convolutional neural network model. *Concurrency and Computation: Practice and Experience*, 32(1), 5197-5205. [Google Scholar Link](#)
- [21]. Greenspan, H., Goldberger, J., & Eshet, I. (2001). Mixture model for face-color modeling and segmentation. *Pattern Recognition Letters*, 22(14), 1525-1536. [Google Scholar Link](#)
- [22]. Haro, A., Flickner, M., & Essa, I. (2000, June). Detecting and tracking eyes by using their physiological properties, dynamics, and appearance. In *Proceedings IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition. CVPR 2000 (Cat. No. PR00662)* (Vol. 1, pp. 163-168). IEEE. [Google Scholar Link](#)
- [23]. Salman, A., Siddiqui, S. A., Shafait, F., Mian, A., Shortis, M. R., Khurshid, K., Schwanecke, U. (2020). Automatic fish detection in underwater videos by a deep neural network-based hybrid motion learning system. *ICES Journal of Marine Science*, 77(4), 1295-1307. [Google Scholar Link](#)
- [24]. Jain, A. K., Duin, R. P. W., & Mao, J. (2000). Statistical pattern recognition: A review. *IEEE Transactions on pattern analysis and machine intelligence*, 22(1), 4-37. [Google Scholar Link](#)
- [25]. Ji, Q., & Yang, X. (2001, July). Real time visual cues extraction for monitoring driver vigilance. In *International Conference on Computer Vision Systems* (pp. 107-124). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg. [Google Scholar Link](#)

- [26]. Jones, M. J., &Rehg, J. M. (2002). Statistical color models with application to skin detection. *International journal of computer vision*, 46(1), 81-96. Google Scholar Link
- [27]. Kanade, T. (1974). Picture processing system by computer complex and recognition of human faces, [https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=en&as_sdt=0%2C5&q=%5B27%5D%09Kanade%2C+T.+%281974%29.+Picture+processing+system+by+computer+complex+and+recognition+of+human+faces.&btnG=date of visit on 3 April 2022]. Google Scholar Link
- [28]. Kirby, M., &Sirovich, L. (1990). Application of the Karhunen-Loeve procedure for the characterization of human faces. *IEEE Transactions on Pattern analysis and Machine intelligence*, 12(1), 103-108. Google Scholar Link
- [29]. Klein, S. B., & Thorne, B. M. (2006). *Biological psychology*. Macmillan. [of visit on 3 April 2022] Google Scholar Link
- [30]. Kneis, B. (2018, September). Face Detection for Crowd Analysis Using Deep Convolutional Neural Networks. In *International Conference on Engineering Applications of Neural Networks* (pp. 71-80). Springer, Cham. Google Scholar Link
- [31]. Lee, J. D., Morgan, J., Wheeler, W. A., Hulse, M. C., & Dingus, T. A. (1997). *Development of Human Factors Guidelines for Advanced Traveler Information Systems (ATIS) and Commercial Vehicle Operations (CVO): Description of ATIS/CVO Functions* (No. FHWA-RD-95-201). Google Scholar Link
- [32]. Lu, X., Duan, X., Mao, X., Li, Y., & Zhang, X. (2017). Feature extraction and fusion using deep convolutional neural networks for face detection. *Mathematical Problems in Engineering*, 2017,2(1), 203-208. Google Scholar Link
- [33]. Martinkauppi, B., & Soriano, M. (2001, June). Basis functions of the color signals of skin under different illuminants. In *3rd Intl conference on Multispectral Color Science* (pp. 21-24)7(1), 13-18. Google Scholar Link
- [34]. Meng, L., & Nguyen, T. Q. (1999, October). Frontal face localization using linear discriminant. In *Conference Record of the Thirty-Third Asilomar Conference on*

Signals, Systems, and Computers (Cat. No. CH37020) (Vol. 1, pp. 745-749).
IEEE.Google Scholar Link

- [35]. Mliki, H., Dammak, S., &Fendri, E. (2020). An improved multi-scale face detection using convolutional neural network. *Signal, Image and Video Processing*, 14(7), 1345-1353.Google Scholar Link
- [36]. Motwani, M., Motwani, R., & Harris, F. (2004, September). Eye detection using wavelets and ANN. In *Proc. of GSPx*.Google Scholar Link
- [37]. Nada, H., Sindagi, V. A., Zhang, H., & Patel, V. M. (2018, October). Pushing the limits of unconstrained face detection: a challenge dataset and baseline results. In *2018 IEEE 9th International Conference on Biometrics Theory, Applications and Systems (BTAS)* (pp. 1-10). IEEE.Google Scholar Link
- [38]. Nixon, M. (1985, December). Eye spacing measurement for facial recognition. In *Applications of Digital Image Processing VIII* (Vol. 575, pp. 279-285). International Society for Optics and Photonics.Google Scholar Link
- [39]. Oloyede, M. O., Hancke, G. P., &Myburgh, H. C. (2018). Improving face recognition systems using a new image enhancement technique, hybrid features and the convolutional neural network. *Ieee Access*, 6, 75181-75191.Google Scholar Link
- [40]. Pentland, A., Moghaddam, B., &Starner, T. (1994). View-based and modular eigenspaces for face recognition.Google Scholar Link
- [41]. Peters, R. D., Kloeppe, E., Alicandri, E., Fox, J. E., Thomas, M. L., Thorne, D. R., &Balwinski, S. M. (1999). *Effects of partial and total sleep deprivation on driving performance* (No. FHWA-RD-94-046). Turner-Fairbank Highway Research Center.Google Scholar Link
- [42]. Pigeon, S., &Vandendorpe, L. (1997, March). The M2VTS multimodal face database (release 1.00). In *International Conference on Audio-and Video-Based Biometric Person Authentication* (pp. 403-409). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.Google Scholar Link

- [43]. Ranjan, R., Bansal, A., Zheng, J., Xu, H., Gleason, J., Lu, B., ...&Chellappa, R. (2019). A fast and accurate system for face detection, identification, and verification. *IEEE Transactions on Biometrics, Behavior, and Identity Science*, 1(2), 82-96. [Google Scholar Link](#)
- [44]. Ravidas, S., & Ansari, M. A. (2019). Deep learning for pose-invariant face detection in unconstrained environment. *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering*, 9(1), 577. [Google Scholar Link](#)
- [45]. Reinders, M. J., Koch, R. W. C., &Gerbrands, J. J. (1996, October). Locating facial features in image sequences using neural networks. In *Proceedings of the Second international conference on Automatic Face and Gesture Recognition* (pp. 230-235). IEEE. [Google Scholar Link](#)
- [46]. Russ, J. C. (2006). *The image processing handbook*. CRC press. = date of visit on 3 April 2022] [Google Scholar Link](#)
- [47]. Sahu, A. K., &Jaiswal, A. (2018, October). Modeling of Attacks in Sigma Delta ADC for Hardware Security. In *2018 3rd International Conference on Communication and Electronics Systems (ICCES)* (pp. 422-426). IEEE. [Google Scholar Link](#)
- [48]. Saito, S. (1992). Does fatigue exist in a quantitative measurement of eye movements?. *Ergonomics*, 35(5-6), 607-615. [Google Scholar Link](#)
- [49]. Salman, A., Siddiqui, S. A., Shafait, F., Mian, A., Shortis, M. R., Khurshid, K., &Schwanecke, U. (2020). Automatic fish detection in underwater videos by a deep neural network-based hybrid motion learning system. *ICES Journal of Marine Science*, 77(4), 1295-1307. [Google Scholar Link](#)
- [50]. Sawat, D. D., Hegadi, R. S., Garg, L., &Hegadi, R. S. (2020). Pixel encoding for unconstrained face detection. *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, 79(47), 35033-35054. [Google Scholar Link](#)
- [51]. Sigal, L., Sclaroff, S., &Athitsos, V. (2000, June). Estimation and prediction of evolving color distributions for skin segmentation under varying illumination.

- In *Proceedings IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition. CVPR 2000 (Cat. No. PR00662)* (Vol. 2, pp. 152-159). IEEE. [Google Scholar Link](#)
- [52]. Stonham, T. J. (1986). Practical face recognition and verification with WISARD. In *Aspects of face processing* (pp. 426-441). Springer, Dordrecht. [Google Scholar Link](#)
- [53]. Tian, Y. L., Kanade, T., & Cohn, J. F. (2000, March). Dual-state parametric eye tracking. In *Proceedings Fourth IEEE International Conference on Automatic Face and Gesture Recognition (Cat. No. PR00580)* (pp. 110-115). IEEE. [Google Scholar Link](#)
- [54]. Toscani, L., Gangemi, P. F., Parigi, A., Silipo, R., Ragghianti, P., Sirabella, E., ...&Zaccara, G. (1996). Human heart rate variability and sleep stages. *The Italian Journal of Neurological Sciences*, 17(6), 437-439. [Google Scholar Link](#)
- [55]. Tsunoda, M., Endo, T., Hashimoto, S., Honma, S., & Honma, K. I. (2001). Effects of light and sleep stages on heart rate variability in humans. *Psychiatry and clinical neurosciences*, 55(3), 285-286. [Google Scholar Link](#)
- [56]. Vanoli, E., Adamson, P. B., Ba-Lin, Pinna, G. D., Lazzara, R., & Orr, W. C. (1995). Heart rate variability during specific sleep stages: a comparison of healthy subjects with patients after myocardial infarction. *Circulation*, 91(7), 1918-1922. [Google Scholar Link](#)
- [57]. Vijayalaxmi, B., Anuradha, C., Sekaran, K., Meqdad, M. N., & Kadry, S. (2020). Image processing based eye detection methods a theoretical review. *Bulletin of Electrical Engineering and Informatics*, 9(3), 1189-1197. [Google Scholar Link](#)
- [58]. Vijayalaxmi, B., Sekaran, K., Neelima, N., Chandana, P., Meqdad, M. N., & Kadry, S. (2020). Implementation of face and eye detection on DM6437 board using simulink model. *Bulletin of Electrical Engineering and Informatics*, 9(2), 785-791. [Google Scholar Link](#)
- [59]. Viola, P., & Jones, M. (2001, December). Rapid object detection using a boosted cascade of simple features. In *Proceedings of the 2001 IEEE computer society*

conference on computer vision and pattern recognition. CVPR 2001 (Vol. 1, pp. I-I).
Ieee.Google Scholar Link

- [60]. Wylie, C. D., Shultz, T., Miller, J. C., Mitler, M. M., & Mackie, R. R. (1996). Commercial motor vehicle driver fatigue and alertness study: Technical summary.Google Scholar Link
- [61]. Yang, M. H., & Ahuja, N. (1998, December). Gaussian mixture model for human skin color and its applications in image and video databases. In *Storage and retrieval for image and video databases VII* (Vol. 3656, pp. 458-466). International Society for Optics and Photonics.Google Scholar Link
- [62]. Yang, S., Luo, P., Loy, C. C., & Tang, X. (2017). Faceness-net: Face detection through deep facial part responses. *IEEE transactions on pattern analysis and machine intelligence*, 40(8), 1845-1859.Google Scholar Link
- [63]. Yuille, A. L., Hallinan, P. W., & Cohen, D. S. (1992). Feature extraction from faces using deformable templates. *International journal of computer vision*, 8(2), 99-111.Google Scholar Link
- [64]. Zhang, S., Wang, X., Lei, Z., & Li, S. Z. (2019). Faceboxes: A CPU real-time and accurate unconstrained face detector. *Neurocomputing*, 364, 297-309.Google Scholar Link
- [65]. Zhou, Y., Liu, D., & Huang, T. (2018, May). Survey of face detection on low-quality images. In *2018 13th IEEE international conference on automatic face & gesture recognition (FG 2018)* (pp. 769-773). IEEE.Google Scholar Link
- [66]. Grant, P. M. (1989). Artificial neural network and conventional approaches to filtering and pattern recognition, *Electronics & Communications Engineering Journal*, 1(6), 225-232. [Google scholar](#)↗
- [67]. Rowley, H. A., Baluja, S., & Kanade, T. (1998). Neural Network Based Face Detection, *IEEE Trans. On Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, 20(1), 23-38.[Google scholar](#)↗

- [68]. Yang, F., & Paindavoine, M. (2003). Implementation of an RBF Neural Network on Embedded Systems: RealTime Face Tracking and Identity Verification, *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks*, 14(5), 1162 – 1175. [Google scholar](#)↗
- [69]. Dijck, G. Van., Van Hulle, M.M., & Wevers, M. (2004). Genetic Algorithm for Feature Subset Selection with Exploitation of Feature Correlations from Continuous Wavelet Transform: a real-case Application, *International Journal of Computational Intelligence*, 1(1), 1-12. [Google scholar](#)↗
- [70]. Kailash J., Sanjay, K., & N. Talbar. (2009). Independent Component Analysis of Edge Information for Face Recognition, *International Journal of Image Processing*, 3(3), 120 -131. [Google scholar](#)↗
- [71]. Dianhai, H.U., Xuliang, L.V., & Liuqiang, WEN. (2012) .Image Enhancement Method Using Improved Histogram Equalization[J], *Electro-Optic Technology Application*, 27(3), 65-68. [Google scholar](#)↗
- [72]. Yongjie, Ma., & Wenxia, Yun. (2012). Research progress of genetic algorithm [J], *Application Research of Computers*, 29 (4), 1201-1206. [Google scholar](#)↗
- [73]. Arshad, N. Moon, K. & Kim, J. (2013). A Secure Face Cryptography for Identity Document Based on Distance Measures, *Journal of Korea Multimedia Society*, 16(10), 1156-1162. [Google scholar](#)↗
- [74]. Kwon, S. (2013). Face Detection Algorithm Using Color Distribution Matching, *Journal of Korea Multimedia Society*, 16(8), 927-933. [Google scholar](#)↗
- [75]. Kim, D. Jeon, I. Lee, S. Rhee, P. & D. Chung. (2006). Embedded Face Recognition based on Fast Genetic Algorithm for Intelligent Digital Photography, *IEEE Transactions on Consumer Electronics*, 52(3), 726-734. [Google scholar](#)↗

- [76]. Song, S. &Park, S.(2011). Design of a Wide Tuning Range DCO for Mobile-TV Applications, *Journal of Korea Multimedia Society*, 14 (5), 614-621.[Google scholar](#)↗
- [77]. Haghghat, M. Abdel-Mottaleb, M. &Alhalabi, W.(2016). Fully automatic face normalization and single sample face recognition in unconstrained environments, *Expert Systems with Applications*, 47(1), 23–34.[Google scholar](#)↗
- [78]. Shifei, Ding.,Bingjuan, Qi., &Hongyan. Tan.(2011).An over view on theory and algorithm of support vector machines [J].*Journal of University of Electronic Science and Technology of China*, 40(1), 2-10.[Google scholar](#)↗
- [79]. Ojala, T.,Pietikainen,M.,&Maenpaa,T. (2002).Multiresolutiongray-scaleand rotation invariant texture classification with local binary patterns[J], *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, 24(7),971-987.[Google scholar](#)↗
- [80]. Turk, M.&Pentland, A. (1991). Eigenfaces for Recognition, *Journal of Cognitive Neuroscience*. 3(1), 71-86. [Google scholar](#)↗
- [81]. Gur, E., &Zalevsky, Z. (2007). Single-Image Digital Super- Resolution A Revised Gerchberg Papoulis Algorithm, *IAENG international Journal of Computer Science*, 34(2), 1-5.[Google scholar](#)↗
- [82]. Suzuki, Y., &Saito, H. (1996). Ozawa, Extraction of the human face from natural background using GAs, Proceedings of the IEEE TENCON, *Digital Signal Processing Applications*, 1(1), 221-226.[Google scholar](#)↗
- [83]. Mohamed, A.M., &Elgammal, A. (1999). Face detection in complex environments from color images, *Proceedings of International Conference on Image Processing*, 3(1), 622-626. [Google scholar](#)↗

- [84]. Brunelli, R. & Poggio, T. (1993). Face recognition: features versus templates, *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, 15 (10), 1042 -1052. [Google scholar](#)↗
- [85]. Chellappa, R., Wilson, C.L. & Sirohey, S. (1995). Human and machine recognition of faces: a survey, *Proceedings of the IEEE*, 83(5), 705 -741. [Google scholar](#)↗
- [86]. Samal, A., & Iyengar, P.A. (1992). Automatic recognition and analysis of human faces and facial expressions: A survey. *Pattern Recognition*, 25(1), 65-77. [Google scholar](#)↗
- [87]. Okamoto, K., Ozawa, S., & Abe, S. (2003). A Fast Incremental Learning Algorithm of RBF Networks with Long-Term Memory. *Proc. Int. Joint Conf. on Neural Networks*, 1(1), 102-107. [Google scholar](#)↗
- [88]. Aaraj, N., Ravi, S., Raghunathan, S., & Jha, N. K. (2006, March). Architectures for efficient face authentication in embedded systems. In *Proceedings of the Design Automation & Test in Europe Conference (Vol. 2, pp. 6-pp)*. IEEE. [Google scholar](#)↗
- [89]. Lim, J. Park, S. & Park, J. (2013). Design to Chip with Multi-Access Memory System an Parallel Processor for 16 Processing Elements of Image Processing Purpose, *Journal of Korea Multimedia Society*, 14(11), 1401-1408. [Google scholar](#)↗
- [90]. Lee, B. Cho, Y. & Cho, S. (1995). Translation, Scale and Rotation Invariant Pattern Recognition using PCA and Reduced Second Order Neural Network, *International Journal of Neural, Parallel & Scientific Computation*, 3(3), 417-429. [Google scholar](#)↗
- [91]. Phillips, P. J., Moon, H., Rizvi, S. A., & Rauss, P. J. (2000). The FERET evaluation methodology for face-recognition algorithms. *IEEE Transactions on pattern analysis and machine intelligence*, 22(10), 1090-1104. [Google scholar](#) ↗

- [92]. Gottumukkal, R, &Asari, VK. (2004). An improved face recognition technique based on modular PCA approach, *Pattern Recogn. Lett.*, 25(4), 429–436.[Google scholar](#)↗
- [93]. Shieh, M.Y. Hsieh, C.M. &Chen, J.Y.(2010). PCA and LDA based fuzzy face recognition system, *IEEE*, 1(1),1610–1615.[Google scholar](#)↗
- [94]. Samanta, B. Al-Balushi, K.R.&Al-Araimi, S.A.(2003). Artificial neural networks and support vector machines with genetic algorithm for bearing fault detection, *Eng. Appl. Artif. Intell.* 16 (7), 657–665.[Google scholar](#)↗
- [95]. Yao, H. Tian, L. (2003). A genetic-algorithm-based selective principal component analysis (GA-SPCA) method for high-dimensional data feature extraction, *IEEE Trans. Geosci. Remote Sens.*41 (6), 1469–1478.[Google scholar](#)↗
- [96]. Kim, S.K. Kim, D.W. Kim, H.J. (1996). A recognition of vehicle license plate using a genetic algorithm based segmentation, *Proceedings International Conference on Image Processing*, 2(1),661–664.[Google scholar](#)↗
- [97]. Soliman, H., Saleh, A., &Fathi, E. (2013). Face recognition in mobile devices. *International Journal of Computer Applications*, 73(2).[Google scholar](#)↗
- [98]. Dave, G., Chao, X., &Sriadibhatla, K. (2010). Face recognition in mobile phones. Department of Electrical Engineering Stanford University, USA, 7-23. [Google scholar](#)↗
- [99]. Hu, J., Peng, L., &Zheng, L. (2015). XFace: a face recognition system for android mobile phones,In *Cyber-Physical Systems, Networks, and Applications (CPSNA)*, *IEEE 3rd International Conference on. IEEE*,Aug, 13-18.[Google scholar](#)↗

Design and Execution of Face Recognition System by using Genetic Algorithm

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Abstract

Purpose: The presented work demonstrates, Face Recognition System initiated by using GA (Genetic algorithm). This paper also suggests the use of normal GA and improved GA and is applicable for the problems of face recognition or pattern recognition systems. Still in modern days, a whole effective machinery to elaborate these features in systemic ways is not possible. Mentioning the facial expression of images, and its recognition in a duplicate image is a problem that involves a scrupulous examination because of its extraordinary complication.

Design/Methodology/Approach: This paper consists of dependable face recognition system method constructed on the normal GA and improved GA procedure. Originally, conceivable face regions remain produced by revenues of the inherent algorithm and the convenient appreciation of the similar process that was done by genetic algorithm.

Findings/Result: Face Recognition System is initiated by using genetic algorithm. This scheme approaches and entails for brilliance advantage popular audiovisual effects, displaying, piece mining, arrangement, documentation, etc. For face appreciation systems the proportion of society is strong virtually and perfect stability is more than 85%. It has been found and arranged for a further research study for face recognition applications systems.

Originality/Value: In this proposed novel approaches replicas remain predictable to covenant by delinquent resolving in a manner with various ways of conservative computing. Dissimilarity has been made between data and the pattern to accentuate the necessity for proposing the pattern systems that report pattern recognition tasks.

Paper Type: Conceptual Research.

Keywords: Genetic Algorithm (GA), Pestle Analysis, Face Recognition System (FRS), Pattern Recognition, SVM.

1. INTRODUCTION

There are various ongoing identifications being used for face recognition technology which is primarily focusing in terms of significant research direction. The procedure for the recognition of face technology is modest and faster recognition technology which is having various advantages of decent intuition and stealthiest 0. These primary features are similarly more to additional biometric machinery. Besides, the FRS is thoroughly connected through

some additional approaches on the biometric substantiation and manmade computer communication for research awareness [2]. The face recognition system contains some basic preparation and testing [3]. This training and testing unit contains the face recognition, face position, retesting, image mining, image assortment, deceitful classifications etc. Primary method of techniques essentially contains expression recognition besides, pre-define, abstraction, medley then decoration sorting [4][5].

The Expression discovery then locating remains in primary focus for appreciation and secondary Story are insertion which both are achievement of documentation[5][7]. Proposal process of cataloging is central for all recognition. So as to recompense for those imperfections around the impulsive merging of GA which progress the correctness of that process[8][9]. Herein proposed work, a normal GA and improved GA algorithm are incorporated to variations of suitability utility & GA operatives that vary the technique for appropriate boundary and transformation prospect[10][11]. This proposed algorithm not only permits exploration for the finest distinct nearby towards the international finest elucidation, nevertheless it decreases the searching period of systems [12][13].

The Numeral Images are consuming such enormous evidence and appearances as these remain supplementary multifaceted, so till nowadays, a widespread well-organized appliance to cutting these features which are yet to be discoverable [14][15]. Mentioning facial recognition, the aforementioned recognition in an image which has a specific problem that involves tons of examination due to its great complexity and indiscretions. The tradition of these images is actually wide and inclusive, for example the security schemes case, wherever it is targeted for distant conference, exploration in folder, people documentation etc[16][17]. Now a day's situation has upsurge of terrorist attacks, stimulates uncountable mechanisms in this range. Security cameras are located like; in superstores, subways, downtown shopping centers, parks, buses, and many more places, demanding support for the documentation of awkward people, moreover sinking crimes and illegal belongings that are trendy in the neighborhood[18][19][20]. Inappropriately, up till now, security systems need to be modernized in terms of human management that sources important disasters. In this present paper, to overcome the present scenario, recommend an examination of the GA method algorithm application for facial recognition, so that it will resolve the one stage for appearance appreciation[21][23]. Permitting to the GA algorithm remains considered as one of the primary search methods stimulated by the theory of Darwin Evolutionary. The designed exhausting certain variety of mechanisms used in Nature, rendered by those entities who are capable in a populace to take additional survival opportunities, once familiarizing themselves further simply to the vagaries that happen in their surroundings[24]. Mortal problematic resolving is fundamentally a shape dispensation difficult but purely a data processing delinquent [25][26]. In some recognition task humans observe decorations in the involvement data and operate the pattern openly[27][28][29]. So here we endeavor at emerging computing representations constructed on normal GA algorithms which deal with numerous pattern recognition circumstances in actual natural life through the assistance of Advance GA[30].

2. RELATED WORKS:

There are many various recognition approaches and we now recapitulate some of them. Various authors in their proposed worked defined some different approaches by using a face recognition system on mobile phones based on the input image, by using Viola-Jones algorithm [32]. The primary goal of the system is to save time and make a cooler access for penetrating pictures. Some authors also discussed a new application for face appreciation on mobile devices based on Bridge based Approach (BA) to improve the speed up the treating and it permits using the arrangement in any setting where an internet is accessible [32]. It has been found and arranged for a further research study for face recognition applications systems. GA can be also observed as calculating prototypes that may be encouraged by the functional and structural of the normal and improved algorithm techniques; however this process's techniques do not contain a single call to the preparation of function but are accomplished numerous times dealing with various images and inputs which contents face. In this proposed replicas remain predictable to covenant by delinquent resolving in a manner with various ways of conservative computing [33]. Dissimilarity has been made between data and the pattern to accentuate the necessity for proposing the pattern systems that report pattern recognition tasks. The Face recognition system consists of an identical massive Heap-space that includes time-intense tasks therefore GA based methodology is being used to identify the unaccusable -copy inside a specific period [34].

Table 1: Review of face recognition system and their focus

S.No	Theory	Focus	Reference
1	Viola-Jones algorithm	face recognition system on mobile phones	Kim et al., (1996). [31]
2	Bridge based Approach	face appreciation on mobile devices	Soliman et al., (2013). [32]
3	conservative computing	times dealing with various images and inputs which contents face	Dave et al., (2010). [33]
4	GA based methodology	Heap-space that includes time-intense	Hu et al., (2015). [34]
5	Normal GA and Improved GA	face recognition system	Yao et al., (2003). [30]
6	The FERET evaluation methodology	for face-recognition algorithms	Rauss et al., (2000). [26]
7	Genetic algorithm for bearing fault detection	Artificial neural networks and support vector machines	S.A et al., (2003). [29]
8	GA based methodology	Fully automatic face normalization and	Alhalabi et al., (2016).

		single sample face recognition in unconstrained environments	[12]
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3. RESEARCH GAP:

In previous research has been found and arranged for a further research study for face recognition applications systems. This paper also key pointed the problems and challenges' in existing works. These are as follows:

- (1) The normal GA are not applicable for the problems of face recognition or pattern recognition systems. An image file consists of a large number of evidence and individualities.
- (2) In existing system predictable to covenant by delinquent resolving in a manner with various ways of conservative computing was not highlighted.
- (3) Dissimilarity has been made between data and the pattern to accentuate the necessity for proposing the pattern systems that report pattern recognition tasks.
- (4) The Face recognition system consists of an identical massive Heap-space that includes time-intense tasks therefore GA based methodology was being used to identify the unaccusablecopy inside a specific period.

4. RESEARCH AGENDA:

The study has following research agenda to get analysis about :

- (1) What is identical massive Heap-space that includes time-intense tasks therefore GA based methodology being used to identify the unaccusable copy inside a specific period?
- (2) How do we get optimum solution using section, calculation of fitness, crossover and mutation?
- (3) How to create system predictable to covenant by delinquent resolving in a manner with various ways of conservative computing which was not highlighted earlier?

5. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES:

The following are the goals of the planned work:

1. To identified the role of normal GA and improved GA procedure in face recognition system method.
2. To calculate the impact of the inherent algorithm and the convenient appreciation in face recognition system method. We can get optimal solution using section, calculation of fitness, crossover and mutation.

3. We will apply the PESTLE analysis to identify risk factors and suggestions for improvement in Face Recognition System by using Genetic Algorithm.

6. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

This paper consists of dependable face recognition system method constructed on the normal GA and improved GA procedure. Originally, conceivable face regions remain produced by revenues of the inherent algorithm and the convenient appreciation of the similar process that was done by genetic algorithm. In this technique exists additional vigor that seemly suitable for stumpy resolve, mutable illumination and dissimilar facial terminologies which is more applicable for actual solitary, various aspects. [1-20]. In this work secondary data of previous work has taken for further pestle analysis.

7. PESTLE ANALYSIS

To be used PESTLE analysis is a tool used to gain a macro picture of an industry environment. PESTLE stands for Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Legal and Environmental factors which allow to form an impression of the factors that might impact a new methods for development. Some factors will be more important to different types of analysis, and a PESTLE analysis will help to identify risk factors for the SWOT analysis.

PESTLE analysis Follow these steps:

- (1) Identify the scope of the research in Image processing. It should cover present and possible future scenarios, and apply to the biomedical and areas of the world in which the image database utilized.
- (2) Decide how the information will be collected and by whom. Identify more than one database to gather data to bring diverse evidence and perspectives.
- (3) Identify appropriate sources of information. You may find areas of PESTLE are a bigger focus to image database than others but exploring information for all of them will give you a bigger view of the external environment.
- (4) Gather the information.
- (5) Analyses the findings.
- (6) Mark each item in terms of importance in relation to potential risk to the image database.
- (7) Identify the image database options to address the issues.
- (8) Write a discussion document for all detected images

7.1. Political factors in PESTLE Analysis:

Political factors include tax policy, environmental regulations, trade restrictions and reform, tariffs, and also political stability. These factors determine the extent to which a government may influence an industry or a company. For example, the government may bring new tax reforms that might change the whole revenue-generating system of a company.

7.2. Economic factors in PESTLE Analysis

Economic factors include economic growth/decline, interest, exchange, inflation and wage rates, minimum wage, working hours, unemployment (local and national), credit availability, and cost of living. These factors are determinants to an economy's performance that directly impacts a company and also have resonating long term effects.

7.3. Social factors in PESTLE Analysis

Social factors include cultural norms and expectations, health consciousness, population growth rates, age distribution, career attitudes, health, and safety. These factors are helpful for companies to better plan their marketing analytics and strategy. For example, the Indian market generally witnesses a surge in demands for vehicles during the last months of the year, due to marriage and the festive season.

7.4. Technological factors in PESTLE Analysis

Technological factors mean the **innovations and developments in technologies**. These factors impact an organization's operations. Several new developments like Artificial Intelligence, IoT, Machine Learning, Deep Learning, are being made in the technology field and if a company fails to match up the trend it may lose its position in the market.

7.5 Legal factors in PESTLE Analysis

Legal factors include changes to legislation impacting employment, access to materials, quotas, resources, imports/exports, and taxation. These factors have both external and internal sides. Certain laws have an impact on the business environment in a country.

7.6. Environmental factors in PESTLE Analysis

These factors are mainly concerned with the effect of the surrounding environment and the influence of ecological aspects. These include waste disposal laws, environmental protection laws, energy consumption regulation.

8. PROPOSED MODEL

This proposed system model figure 1, supported of Recognition of Faces which is identify the manifestation of a face for resolute region of the image. To identify the face previously exasperating to identify it and avoids a lot of exertion, however now merely a constrained section of the image is evaluated, which is contrary different to many algorithms that exertion bearing in mind the entire image. Proposed system project then employment of the FRS is segmented to double foremost portions. Firstly it treating images and the secondly it has acknowledgement Performances. The image treating part contains of Face image acquirement concluded scanning, development, feature, Sifting, the Edge detection and abstraction. The additional quantity contains of the Artificial Intelligence that algorithm will resolve the persistence of recognition measure which is specified in the figure 1(a) Schematic representation of Image Processing system and Figure 1(b) Schematic representation of face detection system [Source as Author].

8.1 GA based Methodology:

To find the identical massive Heap-space that includes time-intense tasks therefore it was being used to identify the unaccusable copy inside a specific period.

Fig. 1(a) Schematic representation of Image Processing system :(b) Schematic representation of face detection system

8.2GAOptimizer Process Steps:

To acquire best optimum solution using section, calculation of fitness, crossover and mutation.

GAProcessesisconsideredthrough a pursuitprocedurethatencouraged in the theory of Darwin by Evolutionist, which usesparticularrange mechanism. Somewhere a character that is the chromosomes additionalimproved of a population that have more existenceprobabilities, by receiving used of simply to variations that arise in its atmosphere. This procedure creates the

algorithm in a solid and fast, existenceterm to a resolute type of optimization; somewhere the explorationinterplanetaryremains too immense and the predictableapproaches become incompetent. Additional GA isessential to distinguishing is that outcome a set of explanations and not merely one result.

8.2.1 FLOW CHART OF PROPOSED GA METHODS:

This flowchart of the suggested GA process is in the subsequentphases:

Step 1: Beginning a populace of N-size, bygeneticmaterialproducedarbitrarily.

Step 2: Spread overappropriateness to each chromosome of populace.

Step 3: To make an oval genetic materialconcluded intersections of designatedof this inhabitants for spread overcombination and transformation in thatprocess.

Step 4: Eradicate participants of old populace, in directionof these new chromosomes and observance the inhabitants through the similar N-genetic material.

Step 5: To spread onthe appropriateness in these genetic material and enclosure them forpopulace.

Step 6:Inultimateexplanationit will be initiate or not if the peer’s number exhausted and yield the chromosome. Else, come back to the **Step 3**.

Above statement is represented in the flowchart in figure 2 asflow chart of planned GA [Source as Author].

Fig. 2: Flow Chart of Planned GA

8.3 Analysis of GA Algorithm

The investigation of basic GA (Genetic Algorithm) and enhanced GA on the foundation of the proposed systems. [14-24]. This paper depicts confirmed the form of the conjunction of the restatement, iteration time, and this recognition rate and dimensions. This segment picked the process that computing the data appreciation value which has constructed happening sustenance trajectory apparatus uses mixed verification [25-32]. In conjunction in between procedures are presented in the Figure 3 as Schematic consequence of conjunction of the elementary normal GA.

8.3.1 Conservative computing:

To existing system predictable to covenant by delinquent resolving in a manner with various ways of conservative computing which was not highlighted earlier

Fig. 3: Schematic consequence of conjunction of the elementary normal GA.

Fig. 4: Schematic outcome for conjunction for simple improved GA.

In figure 3 and figure 4 shows Schematic outcome for conjunction for simple improved GA depicts, red cambersignifies the beyond current cohort for finest specific ability arc and navy color curve signifies the typical suitability of fashionable arc. The elementary GA is informal to reduction made about native optimum elucidation. Through the growth in quantity of

repetitions, the operative cannot products novel GA beings to make certain the variety of the population, it is also been reserved to the greatest characters in the afterward group. In diagram 4, subsequently the enhanced GA processtakes upgraded genetic machinist and suitability utility, which greatest distinct continually has modernized near invention of worldwide ideal elucidation.

Face detection and article abstract are executed using Openlibrary; nonetheless the face recognition is performed in GA algorithm. The expansion and implementation of a face recognition system for the platform by including face and eye detection and applying a set of preprocessing for using normal GA and Improved GA algorithms. Table 2 shows that recognition methods and recognition rate with its approaches.

Table 2: Recognition Methods and Recognition Rate with its Approaches

Recognition Method	Recognition rate (%)	Approaches Reference
PCA	82.10%	[28]
Eigen Faces	83.20%	[29]
Fishers Faces	85%	
WIKI library	80%	[30]
PCA	83.50%	[31]
LDA	84.20%	
Correlation coefficient for the 1 st system	83.20%	[33]
Correlation coefficient for the 2 nd system	84.60%	
Normal GA	85%	Our Proposed Work
Improved GA	92.12%	

Forenactment Evaluation on repetition period, physiognomies measurements well as appreciation value about two methods are depicts in tabular 3 as enactment relationship between GA processes. Obtained value is 25 intervals approximately the exam value.

Table 3: Enactment relationship between GA processes.

	Unique Piece Measurement	Piece Measurement afterward Assortment	Progressed (%)	Reiteration period (sec)
Improved GA	640	310	98	122.27
Normal GA	640	321	97	126.57

In this tabular 3, enhanced GA takes enlarged gratitude amount as associates a simple GA (genetic algorithm), meanwhile the international penetrating of enhanced better for simple algorithm; for periodic some time released in together steps is very dissimilar. For enhanced this steps guarantees the appreciation value containers significantly decrease petition phase, rather than actual essential concurrent applications. For enhanced data flow which upgraded GA process is portrayed in graph 5.

Fig. 5: Movement plan of enhanced GA process.

9.RESULT AND SIMULATION

The obtained results for FRS in Fig.6 &7 respectively (by using standard lenna image).

Fig. 6: FR results constructed by upgraded GA value.

Fig. 7: FR results constructed by normal GA methods.

Diagram 6& 7, represents the improved GA and usual GA which is having a good performance picture whereas a solo picture has a convinced crack for ultimate epic extents. Comparatively. In terms of enhanced GA decreases preparation period then chances of strategy supplies for RTS.

(1) Procedure for obtaining the face location:

For obtaining the Face recognition, permitting to the stage of normal and improved genetic algorithm and then remove and inferior the feature of the selected image (here we use lenna image). Then after, consumption vector machine organization. Detailed organization process is depicted in Figure 8 as given below.

Fig. 8: Steps for obtaining the face location

(2)Test Analysis:

This segment examsfor verify datafromthesuccessivepieces, whichcoveredelsecovered depends on the concentration of light, variationsof the facial expression, face positivity and side of the face. Every test has six differentcurriculum which hasevery person was tested more than 40 times. Lastly optimum results were analyzes recognition rate .Here1 women (lenna) has black and white casing in clines, which takes4 variablerepresentsgradientsdark. Final optimumoutcomesforexaminationsdepicts in tabular 4 and tabular 4 given below;

Table4: Face performance observance.

S.NO	Face Obscured	FR Value (%)	FR Disguised value	Appreciationvalue (%)
1	44	92	48	92
2	45	94	47	95
3	46	98	45	96
4	48	96	44	93
5	46	95	43	94
6	45	93	42	93
Average	45.66	94.66	44.83	93.83

Table 5: Face performance observance in under intensity of light.

S. NO	Normal	R(%)	Bright	R(%)	Dim	R(%)
1	44	92	46	92	43	96
2	42	93	44	94	44	93
3	45	96	47	96	42	94
4	46	98	43	92	41	96
5	42	93	43	96	46	93
6	46	91	44	91	46	91
Average	44.1	93.83	44.5	93.5	43.66	93.83

**Here, R: Recognitionrate

From table 4 shows that face performance observance, it has been seen that when the face is thwarted a slightconsequence on recognizing the face. The reason behind this, once the tasterference reading roomtakescoveredof facial, then itsdeterminationpreciselyremainrecognized. From reduction, an acknowledgment frequency is predominantly less owing to an impediment once particular stimulus on the social face detection. In table 5 shows that face performance observance in under intensity of light when light intensity consumesanimportantcontrolofFRSarrangementthenit is alsodurable or elsefeeble, however it has animmoralconsequence on recognition.

10. FINDINGS:

Proposed System is initiated by using genetic algorithm. This scheme approaches and entails for brilliance advantage popular audiovisual effects, displaying, piece mining, arrangement, documentation, etc. For face appreciation systems the proportion of society is strong virtually and perfect stability is more than 85%. It has been found and arranged for a further research study for face recognition applications systems. This paper also suggests the use of normal GA and improved GA (Genetic Algorithm) and applicable for the problems of face recognition or pattern recognition systems. An image file consists of a large number of evidence and individualities.

11.SUGGESTIONS:

In this technique exists additional vigor that seemly suitable for stumpy resolve, mutable illumination and dissimilar facial terminologies which is more applicable for actual solitary, various aspects. The capability canister is better than earlier by means of improved look searching, greatest method of scrabbling plus efficient method for verge discovery, piece abstraction for copy. Obtained outcome for proposed scheme is created to be enhanced one. In addition to this it is really applicable and suitable for improved face recognition systems that are able to be considered for multi-layer detection.

Following suggestions to be required for construct the methods.

1. This technique exists additional vigor that seemly suitable for stumpy resolve, mutable illumination and dissimilar facial terminologies which is more time consuming in various aspects.
- 2.Improved GA algorithm required serious verification which phases by consuming a grouping of sorting processes.
3. The capability canister is better than earlier by means of improved look searching.
4. Required for better genetic and adjacent national FR solicitation.

12. CONCLUSION

This proposed work, we have demonstrated a supplementary dependable face recognition system method constructed on the normal GA and improved GA procedure. Initially, conceivable face regions remain produced by revenues of the inherent algorithm and the convenient appreciation of the similar process that was done by genetic algorithm. In this technique exists additional vigor that seemly suitable for stumpy resolve, mutable illumination and dissimilar facial terminologies which is more applicable for actual solitary, various aspects. The capability canister is better than earlier by means of improved look searching, greatest method of scrabbling plus efficient method for verge discovery, piece abstraction for copy. Obtained outcome for proposed scheme is created to be enhanced one. In addition to this it is really applicable and suitable for improved face recognition systems that are able to be considered for multi-layer detection. However, this paper also established that FRS conventions are a normal genetic process and provides an improved GA algorithm

which phases by consuming a grouping of sorting processes .Finally, this one provides a stage for better genetic and adjacent national FR solicitation. Even though a further study development in this paper has a certain limitation on values, this paper also needs significant development till to mark additional investigation that occurs practical to repetition. Continuation demands are also prepared for features: communal amalgamation for variability based on man making revealing techniques and emerging application of real-time procurement device that will be suitable for concurrent progress of FRS.

REFERENCES:

- [1] Grant, P. M. (1989). Artificial neural network and conventional approaches to filtering and pattern recognition.*Electronics & Communications Engineering Journal*, 1(6), 225-232.
[Google scholar](#)[↗]
- [2] Rowley, H. A., Baluja, S., & Kanade, T. (1998). Neural Network Based Face Detection.*IEEE Trans. On Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, 20(1), 23-38.
[Google scholar](#)[↗]
- [3] Yang, F., & Paindavoine, M. (2003). Implementation of an RBF Neural Network on Embedded Systems: Real Time Face Tracking and Identity Verification.*IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks*, 14(5), 1162-1175.
[Google scholar](#)[↗]
- [4] Dijck, G. Van., Van Hulle, M.M., & Wevers, M. (2004). Genetic Algorithm for Feature Subset Selection with Exploitation of Feature Correlations from Continuous Wavelet Transform: a real-case Application.*International Journal of Computational Intelligence*, 1(1), 1-12.
[Google scholar](#)[↗]
- [5] Kailash J., Sanjay, K., & N. Talbar. (2009). Independent Component Analysis of Edge Information for Face Recognition.*International Journal of Image Processing*, 3(3), 120 -131.
[Google scholar](#)[↗]
- [6] Dianhai, H.U., Xuliang, L.V., & Liuqiang, WEN. (2012) .Image Enhancement Method Using Improved Histogram Equalization.*Electro-Optic Technology Application*, 27(3), 65-68.
[Google scholar](#)[↗]
- [7] Yongjie, Ma., & Wenxia, Yun. (2012). Research progress of genetic algorithm [J].*Application Research of Computers*, 29 (4), 1201-1206.
[Google scholar](#)[↗]
- [8] Arshad, N. Moon, K. & Kim, J. (2013). A Secure Face Cryptography for Identity Document Based on Distance Measures.*Journal of Korea Multimedia Society*, 16(10), 1156-1162.

[Google scholar](#)[↗]

- [9] Kwon, S. (2013). Face Detection Algorithm Using Color Distribution Matching.*Journal of Korea Multimedia Society*, 16(8), 927-933.
[Google scholar](#)[↗]

- [10] Kim, D. Jeon, I. Lee, S. Rhee, P. & D. Chung. (2006). Embedded Face Recognition based on Fast Genetic Algorithm for Intelligent Digital Photography. *IEEE Transactions on Consumer Electronics*, 52(3), 726-734. [Google scholar](#)[↗]
- [11] Song, S. & Park, S. (2011). Design of a Wide Tuning Range DCO for Mobile-TV Applications. *Journal of Korea Multimedia Society*, 14 (5), 614-621. [Google scholar](#)[↗]
- [12] Haghighat, M. Abdel-Mottaleb, M. & Alhalabi, W. (2016). Fully automatic face normalization and single sample face recognition in unconstrained environments. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 47(1), 23–34. [Google scholar](#)[↗]
- [13] Shifei, Ding., Bingjuan, Qi., & Hongyan. Tan. (2011). An over view on theory and algorithm of support vector machines. *Journal of University of Electronic Science and Technology of China*, 40(1), 2-10. [Google scholar](#)[↗]
- [14] Ojala, T., Pietikainen, M., & Maenpaa, T. (2002). Multiresolution gray-scale and rotation invariant texture classification with local binary patterns [J]. *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, 24(7), 971-987. [Google scholar](#)[↗]
- [15] Turk, M. & Pentland, A. (1991). Eigenfaces for Recognition., *Journal of Cognitive Neuroscience*, 3(1), 71-86. [Google scholar](#)[↗]
- [16] Gur, E., & Zalevsky, Z. (2007). Single-Image Digital Super-Resolution A Revised Gerchberg Papoulis Algorithm. *IAENG International Journal of Computer Science*, 34(2), 1-5. [Google scholar](#)[↗]
- [17] Suzuki, Y., & Saito, H. (1996). Ozawa, Extraction of the human face from natural background using Gas. *Proceedings of the IEEE TENCON, Digital Signal Processing Applications*, 1(1), 221-226. [Google scholar](#)[↗]
- [18] Mohamed, A.M., & Elgammal, A. (1999). Face detection in complex environments from color images. *Proceedings of International Conference on Image Processing*, 3(1), 622-626.

[Google scholar](#)[↗]

- [19] Brunelli, R. & Poggio, T. (1993). Face recognition: features versus templates. *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, 15 (10), 1042 -1052. [Google scholar](#)[↗]
- [20] Chellappa, R., Wilson, C.L. & Sirohey, S. (1995). Human and machine recognition of faces: a survey. *Proceedings of the IEEE*, 83(5), 705 -741. [Google scholar](#)[↗]
- [21] Samal, A., & Iyengar, P.A. (1992). Automatic recognition and analysis of human faces and facial expressions: A survey. *Pattern Recognition*, 25(1), 65-77. [Google scholar](#)[↗]
- [22] Okamoto, K., Ozawa, S., & Abe. S. (2003). A Fast Incremental Learning Algorithm of RBF Networks with Long-Term Memory. *Proc. Int. Joint Conf. on Neural Networks*, 1(1), 102-107. [Google scholar](#)[↗]
- [23] Aaraj, N., Ravi, S., Raghunathan, S., & Jha, N. K. (2006, March). Architectures for efficient face authentication in embedded systems. *In Proceedings of the Design Automation & Test in Europe Conference*, 29(1), 1-6. IEEE. [Google scholar](#)[↗]

- [24] Lim, J. Park, S. & Park, J. (2013). Design to Chip with Multi-Access Memory System an Parallel Processor for 16 Processing Elements of Image Processing Purpose. *Journal of Korea Multimedia Society*, 14(11), 1401-1408. [Google scholar](#)[↗]
- [25] Lee, B. Cho, Y. & Cho, S. (1995). Translation, Scale and Rotation Invariant Pattern Recognition using PCA and Reduced Second Order Neural Network. *International Journal of Neural, Parallel & Scientific Computation*, 3(3), 417-429. [Google scholar](#)[↗]
- [26] Phillips, P. J., Moon, H., Rizvi, S. A., & Rauss, P. J. (2000). The FERET evaluation methodology for face-recognition algorithms. *IEEE Transactions on pattern analysis and machine intelligence*, 22(10), 1090-1104. [Google scholar](#) [↗]
- [27] Gottumukkal, R, & Asari, VK. (2004). An improved face recognition technique based on modular PCA approach. *Pattern Recogn. Lett.*, 25(4), 429-436. [Google scholar](#)[↗]
- [28] Shieh, M.Y. Hsieh, C.M. & Chen, J.Y. (2010). PCA and LDA based fuzzy face recognition system. *IEEE*, 1(1), 1610-1615. [Google scholar](#)[↗]
- [29] Samanta, B. Al-Balushi, K.R. & Al-Araimi, S.A. (2003). Artificial neural networks and support vector machines with genetic algorithm for bearing fault detection. *Eng. Appl. Artif. Intell*, 16 (7), 657-665. [Google scholar](#)[↗]
- [30] Yao, H. Tian, L. (2003). A genetic-algorithm-based selective principal component analysis (GA-SPCA) method for high-dimensional data feature extraction. *IEEE Trans. Geosci. Remote Sens*, 41 (6), 1469-1478. [Google scholar](#)[↗]
- [31] Kim, S.K. Kim, D.W. Kim, H.J. (1996). A recognition of vehicle license plate using a genetic algorithm based segmentation. *Proceedings International Conference on Image Processing*, 2(1), 661-664. [Google scholar](#)[↗]
- [32] Soliman, H., Saleh, A., & Fathi, E. (2013). Face recognition in mobile devices. *International Journal of Computer Applications*. 73(2), 13-20. [Google scholar](#)[↗]
- [33] Dave, G., Chao, X., & Sriadibhatla, K. (2010). Face recognition in mobile phones. Department of Electrical Engineering Stanford University. USA, 7-23. [Google scholar](#)[↗]
- [34] Hu, J., Peng, L., & Zheng, L. (2015). XFace: a face recognition system for android mobile phones, In Cyber-Physical Systems, Networks and Applications (CPSNA), *IEEE 3rd International Conference on. IEEE, Aug*, 13-18. [Google scholar](#)[↗]

A Robust Algorithm for Face Detection on Unconstrained Background Images using Neural Network

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: The main goal of proposed design is to use a neural network to create a robust solution for face detection on unconstrained backdrop images. In this regards the types of recognition involved in image processing discipline are pattern recognition, Face recognition, object recognition, speech recognition, and analyzing the data, etc. The basic concepts, structure and ideas involved in this recognition are discussed in this section. In the last two decades, object detection and recognition has become the most interesting and challenging research field for the researchers.

Design/Methodology/Approach: Developing a theoretical concept based on model building using the for Face recognition method and analysis. The need for Face recognition and detection arises due to demand for automatic surveillance systems, Human Computer Interface (HCI), etc. A fast processor is required in real-time implementation of implanted image processing applications. For these systems, an accurate and fast real-time implementation of face selecting is essential. Therefore, a novel approach for tracking and determining the face on a live and unmoving image is projected in this paper.

Findings/Result: Based on the developed model, the resultant efficiency of the selected algorithm can be predictable on the basis of Specificity, Accuracy & Sensitivity the result of evaluation is very high. Background, head movement, and neural network or incorrect training are some of the reasons. The efficiency of the selected algorithm can be predictable on the basis of Specificity, Accuracy & Sensitivity. The estimated values are 95.3%, 88.6% & 89.2% correspondingly.

Originality/Value: A novel approach for tracking and determining the face on a live and unmoving image is projected in this works. This projected process is applied and efficiently tested in the laboratory for different original images with glasses and without glasses taken by camera (specification of camera is Logitech USB, 30fps, 1600 x 1200 pixels). This process is built in a processor named open multimedia applications platform of 1 GHz and by Open CV libraries the proposed algorithm is developed. The rate of success in this selected algorithm is very high as the hardware is very much accurate and works at high speed which is best used for real time. The rate of success on selected algorithms is ninety-

eight percent; the two percent unsuccessful rate in results is for some reason like background, head movement & due to neural network/ inappropriate training.

Paper Type: Conceptual Qualitative Research.

Keywords: Logitech, Face, Neural Network, Open CV, Gabor Filter, Image Database, Face detection, Robust Algorithm.

1. INTRODUCTION :

The first work on this subject started in 1950's in psychology Bruner et al. (1954) [1]. The research came out with issues like expression, emotion analysis and gestures. The actual research on face recognition started in the 1960's. Woodrow W. Bledsoe along with other researchers did majority of work related to AI-related for different intelligence agencies [2] [3]. During 1964-65 Bledsoe continued his work end to end with Helen Chan & Charles Bisson by using computers to identify the face of humans. Later Bledsoe planned and applied a semi-automatic system. Bledsoe discussed a few challenges faced by face recognition systems, after 50 years the problems still continue- variations in illuminations, ageing, head rotation, face expression [4]. In 1970, few researchers defined geometric parameters which perform pattern recognition. In 1973, Kenade established an automatic face identification system which was demonstrated on a computer and he observed a 45-75% correct identification rate [5] [6]. In 1980's researchers came out with new approaches to improve face recognition systems such as Template matching with "deformable templates" and ANN [7]. The year 1990 saw a broad face recognition approach using eigenfaces, ICA, PCA, LDA & their derivatives. Face detection is a process of extracting faces positively from the input image scenes or video stream [8] [9]. Feature extraction such as face regions, variations, angles; eye spacing is done in the next step. The last step performs face recognition by comparing it with an image database [10].

The challenges faced by most face recognition system are:

A.Pose Variation: Frontal images would be a condition for a face recognition system but this is an uncontrolled condition. Pose variation is one of the major research issues and this drops the performance of face detection systems. Pose variation depends on the image acquisition system and position which changes spatial coordinates in an acquired image leading to distortion. This variation affects traditional appearance-based face recognition methods like Eigen faces and fisher faces [11] [12] [13].

B.Face Occlusion: The presence of spectacles, beards or hats may cause problems in face detection. This is another main problem in face detection and identification systems [14] [15] [16].

C.Facial Expression: Facial features vary due to facial gestures and become difficult in identification. Facial expressions represent feelings, tempers and emotions of human beings. The variation in expression results in a change in spatial coordinates but also changes the shape of the face [17].

D.Illumination: Imaging systems and environmental variations affects the image quality.

The illumination changes are being discussed in some face detection and identification systems. This variation is caused by different lighting conditions [18] [19] .

E.Clustering: The above four parameters make changes in original image facial appearances; hence it is necessary to consider the presence of all conditions and backgrounds around a person in acquired images. Avoiding these parameters affects face detection algorithms and reduces performance. Yan, Kriegman and Ahuja divided face recognition techniques into four categories which may overlap, developing another algorithm which may consist of two or more categories [20] [21].

The four categories are:

- i. Knowledge dependent Process: Identify faces based on information about humanoid faces.
- ii. Invariant Feature Methods: Methods developed under this category recognize faces based on invariant features.
- iii. Template Matching Methods: These methods try to correlate original images with database pattern images.
- iv. Appearance Based Methods: This recognizes faces based on a set of training pictures.

F.Knowledge Depending Process: These use some knowledge about faces like ellipse shape and triangle features. Other set of rules which can be used, face usually has two symmetric eyes and eyes are darker than cheeks [22] [23] [24]. It measures the distance between eyes or intensity between eye areas. Knowledge-based methods can reduce the computation cost but they are rotation limited. If rules set are too universal, there could be more false rejections. The solution to overcome this problem is to develop hierarchical knowledge-based techniques. But these methods are limited and unable to find faces in complex images [25] [26] [27] .

G.Feature-Invariant Methods: This makes use of features like edge, complexion, texture and shape for face detection. These methods are rotation independent, scale independent and fast. The method which is scale independent, rotation independent can reduce computational cost. Building Face identification systems depends on skin complexion as a feature, the researcher has three major issues as, which complexion space to choose, modelling of skin complexion distribution and way to process skin complexion [28] [29][30] .

In image/vision processing, complexion is used as a powerful tool to identify objects or features such as computer graphics, Colorimetry & video signal communication standards have given many complexion spaces with dissimilar properties [31] [32].

a. RGB: This cloudspace originated from CRT, it is defined as a mixture of Greenish colour, Reddishcolour, and Bluecolour. This complexion space is the veryextensively used information for saving image data. Combining luminance &chrominance with RGB is unfavorable choice for complexion space [33].

b. Normalized RGB: This is obtained from RGB by normalizing, $r=R/(R+G+B)$, $g=G/(R+G+B)$, $b=B/(R+G+B)$. The 'b' component has no significance, hence neglected. The remaining two components are called pure complexion, and normalized RGB does not vary due to light source. This property made this complexion space gain popularity among the researchers [33] [34]

c. HSV, HSL- Hue, HSI, Saturation Value (Lightness, Intensity): Dominant complexion like red, purple, yellow is represented as Hue. Complexion brightness is measured using Saturation. Intensity, Lightness and Value are related to luminance [35].

d. TSL- Tint(T), Saturation(S), and Lightness(L): This complexion space is a transformation of normalized RGB, close to hue and saturation. Normalization of TSL within RGB is the advantage of TSL complexion space transform. Normalized values of r and g for TSL space are more effective during skin segmentation approach. This normalization reduces variability of skin complexion sensitivity and improves skin complexion detection rate. TSL complexion space is more efficient and robust after normalization. No complexion correction algorithms are existing for image acquisition devices. Despite all these efforts, detection of dark skin complexion is an open challenge to researchers [36].

e. YCbCr: This complexion space is nonlinear encoded RGB, mostly used in European television for compressing images without loss of information. It is constructed by weighted sum RGB, Cr, and Cb and complexion is represented as luminance. Cr is luminance difference red and Cb is luminance difference blue components. The luminance separation and components property of chrominance makes this color space beautiful for skin color modeling. In the year 1990, RGB colour space with Bayes SPM achieved a TPR of 80% and FPR of 8.4% Mason made use of three different colour spaces: RGB with Bayes Skin Probability Map (SPM) classifier, YIQ with I-axis threshold classifier & RGB with threshold ratios classifier [37]. The TPR of these three methods are 19.8%, 30.2% & 32.3% respectively. In 2000, another researcher used HSV color space with Max. Likelihood estimation which worked on different skin types, an attractive study on skin color spreading under different conditions of lighting was proposed which showed 125 individuals to lie inside a definite color space locus, writers used scatter matrices of non-skin & skin clusters [38]. The conclusions drawn were, separating skin and non-skin in RGB space & falling luminance will worsen the separation. In 2005, authors used five color space models with different classifiers, but failed to achieve TPR more than 90%. In 2009, authors used YCgCb + YCgCr with thresholding as classifier, and achieved 92.1% TPR with 6% of FPR. In 2010, YCbCr with 2D Gaussian Model and Bayesian Network (BN) achieved 96% of TPR with 15% of FPR. With the Literature Survey on Face detection using Skin Segmentation, it is concluded that a good classifier must distinguish between skin and non-skin pixels of several persons having different skin hues like white, wheat, black & brown.

To expand the accuracy of the classifier, it is better to take into consideration other features such as motion, shape & size. If skin detection is a pre-processing step in any application, the authors concluded that it yields better results with 1D RGB color space. Other authors concluded that results can be improved using Hybrid color space i.e., combination of

different color space such as HSV+YCbCr, HSV+rgb, HSV+TSL+rgb . Meeting real-time application requirements such as computational and storage are extremely important [39] [40] .

Template Matching Methods: Template matching is one of the widest used methods for face identification because they are strong to noise, easy to use & take less time. In this method, the forward face images are already defined and kept in the system database. An Image processing algorithm is developed where correlation between input and stored image is performed to detect the face. But face detection algorithms suffer from illumination and variation of face feature shapes. One simple method to resolve this problem is to receive the usual face from the face examples & then keep them in the database, then the input picture with high association score is the position of face. This process is known as the filter match process. Filter match process accepts Additive White Gaussian Noise (AWGN), which is not good for image like variation, illumination and expression. AWGN is noise added to images to investigate the performance of the proposed system. To reduce this high variation Appearance based methods have been used by various authors. The association between input image and face template is similar to Normalized Cross Correlation (NCC). But NCC is exaggerated by clutter background and illumination. This problematic situation can be resolved using Sum of Absolute Differences (SAD), but it is mostly cast-off for compression and tracking the object, hence SAD needs optimization. In 2012, authors proposed face detection using Optimized SAD (OSAD) instead of NCC to reduce illumination effect. The results showed that OSAD are unaffected by variation of pose but affected through clutter as objects exist in it.

2. RELATED WORKS :

The initial work was carried out by Bruner, J. (1954) had examined the perception of people for Image detection. The literature of hand book of social psychology was useful context in terms of understanding the human psychology [1] . One of the methods in facial recognition, panoramic research had solved Bledsoe et al. (1964) which had considered being accurate model [2]. In Chan et al. (1965) had proposed a new man-machine image identification system and got some of the preliminary results with compromising high accuracy [3] . Same researcher designed machine recognition by Bledsoe (1965) to get fast and accurate model for face reorganization [4] . Semi-automatic facial recognition for human has been done by Bledsoe (1968) [5]. Kanade et al. (1974) explored a new picture for processing system using best model and recognition of human faces with less processing time [6] . Nixon et al. (1985) experienced about eye lead recognition in applications of digital image processing in international society for optics and photonics lab India [7] . Stonham et al. (1986) explained solved the face recognition with large database and verification must be done with WISARD in aspects of face processing in human [8]. In application and characterization of human faces has done by Kirby et al. (1990) [9]. The modern development of human factors guidelines and commercial vehicle operations. In Yuille et al. (1992) Feature extraction from faces using deformable templates Lee et al. (1997) [10][11]. Different types of weariness were investigated by Saito et al. (1992) in a quantitative measurement of eye movements in image detection [12] . The efficacy of pupil area identification approach

employing two light sources and image difference method was investigated by Ebisawa et al. (1993)[13]. Calcagnini and colleagues (1994, November). Heart rate variability signal spectral analysis during sleep stages. In Proceedings of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society's 16th Annual International Conference (Vol. 2, pp. 1252-1253) IEEE [14] . (Biological psychology. Klein et al.) Macmillan [15] . Pentland and colleagues (Pentland et al) (1994). Face recognition with view-based and modular eigenspaces [16] . Vanoli and colleagues (Vanoli et al) (1995). Heart rate variability during different stages of sleep [17] : a comparison of healthy people and people who have had a heart attack. Wylie and his colleagues (1996). Technical summary of the commercial motor vehicle driver tiredness and alertness research [18] .In Pigeon et al. (1997, March).have designed the M2VTS multimodal face [19] [20] [21] .Deng et al. (1997) have the region-based template deformation and masking for eye-feature extraction and description [22][23] [24][25]. In Huang et al. (1998) posthaddiscrimination and eye detection using Support Vector Machines (SVM) [26] [27] [28] . Elsenbruch, et al. (1999). Heart rate variability during waking and sleep in healthy males and females [29] . Jones et al.(2002)have statistical color models with application to skin detection [30] .Meng, et al.(1999) have frontal face localization using linear discriminant [31] .In Peters, R. D eulation (1999). Effects of partial and total sleep deprivation on driving performance (No. FHWA-RD-94-046) [32] Turner-Fairbank Highway Research Center.Yang et al. (1998, December). Gaussian mixture model for human skin color and its applications in image and video databases [33] [34] [35] . Jain et al. (2000). Statistical pattern recognition [36] [37] In Tian, (2000, March). Dual-state parametric eye tracking [38] . Feng, et al.(2001). Multi-cues eye detection on gray intensity image [39] [40] [41] . InMartinkaupp et al. (2001). Basis functions of the color signals of skin under different illuminants [42]. Ji et al. (2001, July). Real time visual cues extraction for monitoring driver vigilance [43] [44] .Vijayalaxmi et al.. (2020). Image processing-based eye detection methods a theoretical review [45] . Vijayalakshmi et al. (2020). Implementation of face and eye detection on DM6437 board using simulink model [46]. InBiradar, et al. (2018) have hardware prototyping for video and signal processing applications using dm 6437 texas instrument evaluation board [47] .Biradar, et al.(2018) have DM3730 Processor Hardware Debugging on Linux Platform [48] [49].Chaudhry et al. (2017) have face detection and recognition in an unconstrained environment for mobile visual assistive system [50] [50] .In Ganapathi, et al.(2020) have unconstrained ear detection using ensemble-based convolutional neural network model [52] [53] .Zhou et al. (2018). have survey of face detection on low-quality images. Sahu et al. (2018) have modeling of attacks in sigma delta adc for hardware security [54] .Zhang et al. (2019) have face boxes: A CPU real-time and accurate unconstrained face detector [55] .Yang et al. (2017) have faceness-net: Face detection through deep facial part responses [56].Ravidas et al. (2019) have deep learning for pose-invariant face detection in unconstrained environment [57]. Lu et al. (2017) have feature extraction and fusion using deep convolutional neural networks for face detection [58] .Sawat et al. (2020) have pixel encoding for unconstrained face detection [59] .Kneis, et al. (2018) explored face detection for crowd analysis using deep convolutional neural networks [60]. Oloyede et al. (2018) discussed Improving face recognition systems using a new image enhancement technique, hybrid features and the convolutional neural network [61] .Bekhet, et al.(2022 have gender recognition from

unconstrained selfie images: a convolutional neural network approach [62] . Ranjan, et al. (2019) designed fast and accurate system for face detection, identification, and verification [63]. Salman et al. (2020) have automatic fish detection in underwater videos by a deep neural network-based hybrid motion learning system [64] . Methods Based on Appearance: These templates are learned from images examples. These procedures depend on statistics and machine learning face characteristics. In 1986 & 1990, face recognition systems were developed efficiently using PCA where the face is represented as a vector coordinate system. These vectors are known as eigenvectors (Kirby,M., and Sirovich,L.,1990). In 1997, few researchers developed a neural network-based face recognition system. The detection system consisted of 2 classes, non-face and face class. The real challenge in neural network-based approaches is training and representing images not containing faces. Support Vector Machines (SVMs) are used to increase the margin between decision and training hyper planes because they are considered as linear classifiers (Pigeon, S., and Vandendrope, L., 1997)[65]. Recognizing human faces under different conditions like 5year old boy, grandma's wedding photo, face occluded, and a person with a beard are trivial but not impossible. So, they are a challenge to computers. The core problem in the recognition stage is feature selection. This feature selection process is described as methods of removing applicable information from the original image. This data is given as input to the next step with minimum error. While developing a classifier, care should be taken such that the FPR of the classifier should not increase. The TPR and FPR basically depend on training samples, if the training samples are relatively smaller in number when compared to features then a problem called "peaking phenomenon" occurs which can be avoided by considering training samples ten times per class of number of features. As the classifier complexity increases, a large amount of training examples is required. The correctness of the classifier depends on the number of features selected while training the classifier.

2.1 RESEARCH GAPS :

- (1) Designing of fast and accurate system for face detection were challenges using existing methods.
- (2) The real challenge in neural network-based approaches is training and representing images not containing faces.
- (3) Recognizing human faces under different conditions like 5year old boy, grandma's wedding photo, face occluded, and a person with a beard are trivial but not impossible.
- (4) As the classifier complexity increases, a large amount of training examples is required.
- (5) The correctness of the classifier depends on the number of features selected while training the classifier.
- (6) A CPU real-time and accurate unconstrained face detector is still need be in investigation and design implements.

3. OBJECTIVES AND RESEARCH AGENDA :

The following are the goals of the planned work:

- (1)Feeds the seven general face expressions into the neural network that was built to train

the identifier.

(2) To demonstrate the suggested method's high efficiency and feasibility in dealing with multi-scale face detection difficulties.

(3) To introduce a technique that employed by different studies like matching the template, Hough Transform and Eigenvectors. HSV for eliminating all unnecessary pixels in the picture excluding Face & Neural Network categorize the picture as Face / non-Face.

4. PROPOSED ALGORITHM :

The algorithm that was chosen consists of two steps. The first stage is training, and the second stage is detection. The stage is broken into two parts: a neural network and preprocessing processes using a Gabor filter. Otherwise, training involves manual segmentation of the interest region and color model selection of the most essential features. In the initial stage the automatic removal of eyes region by color model and eye candidate's separation is performed by morphological operation. Block diagram of database image shown in Figure 1 [Author as source]

A. Database:

Some databases are used in both stages such as GATV, VITS, Face expression and Math Works. This stage is performed by different conditions like hair style, various facial expressions, condition of illumination etc. This preformation happens by including up to five hundred gray scale images and five hundred color images of dissimilar size. This work used thousands of images for training purposes and approximately thousand numbers of images for the purpose of testing. Mendeley Desktop, the original reference manager based on the Qt framework that runs on Microsoft Windows, macOS, and Linux is used as source engine to build references.

Fig.1: Block Diagram of Database Image

5. TRAINING METHODOLOGY :

For training the neural network a huge number of no face and face images are required in the

first step. Approximately two hundred faces are cropped from several pictures and gathered. That image contains different sizes of face, position, orientation, with glass, with occlusion etc. These pictures were used to control every face at the similar scale, same position, same alignment etc. The stages are given below:

1. Reset FF which is a vector and will be the normal position of every feature labeled for entire faces with location of feature in the 1st face.

2. These features synchronize in FF by rotation, translation and scaling. For this step the face location averagely appears at a determined location with a 32 x 20-pixel window. In this stage, 40 face specimens are generated from an image by circulating the image at their center up to hundred scaling in between 90% - 100%, interpreting up to $\frac{1}{2}$ pixel and reflecting for training. Normally, all images can work as a non-eye specimen because the non-eye image space is ample larger than the eye image space. Though, representative collection for non-eye computer sets and information technology is very problematic. Instead of image collection before the training starts, the image can be collected in training period by following manner, taken from [13].

a. By producing fifty random images, make a preliminary group of non-face images. After that apply the above steps in all of these images.

b. Train the neural network for producing the input of 1 (for face image) and 0 (for non-face image).

c. Run the system on the set of images that consist of no face. Gather the sub images in which the network improperly specifies the face (the activation output > 0).

d. For example, select approximately 40 numbers of sub images randomly, put on the previous steps and add all selected faces into the set of training. For the second step, some non-face examples are collected in the time of training as shown in figure 2. It should be reserved in mind that the face which is not very close is the positive example which is shown in figure 3. This example gives a lesson in precisely the boundary between non-face image and face images. Here we used two hundred sets of images for gathering the negative examples as per the above description. For training neural networks, the non-face and face images are used which is shown in the following figure 2 [source as Author]..

Fig.2: Examples of eye shapes from the test & training sets.

Fig.3: Examples of non-face shapes from the test and training sets.

A. Gabor filters:

Daugman gives a proposal on a two-dimensional Gabor function to structure the properties of spatial summation (of accessible field) for modest cells in the graphic cortex. They are largely used in computer vision, image dispensation, psychophysics and neuroscience. Functions visualization of Gabor use Gabor filter for some purposes like removal of texture feature by detection of edge, by simulate complex and simple cell (visual cortex), by simulation of non-classical open field inhibition / edge suppression & use this for detection of object outline, describe certain effects (visual perception). The image examples are applied in following Gabor function which is two-dimensional:

$$g_{\lambda,\theta,\sigma,\gamma}(x,y) = \exp\left(-\frac{x'^2 + \gamma^2 y'^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \cos\left(2\pi \frac{x'}{\lambda} + \phi\right) \text{----- (1)}$$

$$x' = x \cos\theta + y \sin\theta$$

$$y' = -x \sin\theta + y \cos\theta$$

The definite value parameters of Gabor function are orientation, wavelength, aspect ratio, bandwidth and phase offset. These functions are estimated and showed as image map intensity in the production window. Light grey colors represent positive function value and

dark grey color represents negative function value. The output image and input image size are the same. By altering various parameters, the set of training data produced by Gabor Filter Kernel such as orientation, wavelength, angle of rotation etc. which are shown below in the following figure 4 [source as Author].

Fig.4: Gabor Filter Kernel by various alignment, angle and wavelength

B. Neural network:

The networks will collect 960 actual values in a 960-pixel image as an input (size of image approximately= 32 x 20). Then it is essential to detect the face by replying by an output vector [25]. The output of the vector represents a non-face and face. For correct operation the network should give 1 if the face is present and otherwise the network should give 0 in [25]. Additionally, the network must be able to manage the non-face image. Practically the network will not detect the faultless image of the eye which is denoted by input vector.

C. Neural network Architecture:

To identify the eyes, the neural network required 960 output & input layers to point out the eyes. This network is like a 2-layer log-sigmoid network. The log-sigmoid transfer function had been taken as the range of output is 0 to 1 which is an exact range for study of Boolean standards output [25]. The secret layer has two hundred neurons [25]. These numbers were collected through experience and guesswork. If this network feels distress in education then neurons may be an addition in this layer. These networks are skilled on the basis of 1 as output & 0 like non-eye recognition. Through, the non-eye images may give a network which does not create one and zero perfectly. After making the network skilled, the output will be sent by the modest transfer function shown in figure 5 [source as internet].

Fig.5: Architecture of Neural Network

6. TESTING METHODOLOGY :

At the time of testing, the neural network reliability is estimated by network testing by a hundred numbers of images (input) of several circumstances. In this work, an algorithm is produced for separating eyes from the images (input) which are given. The selected algorithm is shown in the following figure. By extracting the skin region, the algorithm works with face removal by 1 transforming color space structure. The face is sensed by removing unnecessary space using color space (HSV) and to remove extra areas Morphological operation is used. The selected algorithm is given below figure 6 [source as author].

Fig.6: Selected Algorithm

The 1st step is detecting the face separating the human face from the sequence of images. Simple search procedure in video will not assist to select the face in between the additional

organizational face components like moustache, beard etc. Those problems become complicated by live images like video, as the available time for searching in every image is limited. An effective face selection feature is human skin color.

Many different color spaces have been used to pixels stage as skin with RGB, regularized RGB, HSV [18], [24], [20], [19], YIQ, XYZ, & YCbCr [21]. The proposed method in this paper includes skin recognition to remove the background of component tracked through detection of eye.

Skin area removal assist in estimating the estimated location of the eye by removing a huge number of wrong eye candidates. Additional expansion was made on the algorithm which is based on skin color. For color description, RGB color space is an efficient algorithm and it is used in a terrible way. Therefore, every coordinate such as green, red & blue which does not give necessary related data about whether a specific picture has skin or not as that image has luminance effects from image intensity. To improve the color representation, Lab color model is used. It has three-dimensional color space and in which color alterations are perceived to be similarly large and also have the same distance between them. For face segmentation, a lab color model is applied. In the selected algorithm, the model of lab colour is useful subsequently for applying the color space of HSV and for getting the actual region of the eye.

The HSV gives information about colors which is similar to humans thought of color. The descriptions of general pure color given by "Hue", the manner of diluted pure color is described by "saturation" and the achromatic motion of intensity is provided by "Value". As defined in the research paper, the 1st constraints S and H will give cultivated data related to skin.

As stated, [29] the cost of H shall be in between 0.01 & 0.1 i.e 0.01 less than H less than 0.1 → skin

It has been noticed that this do not eliminate entire skin from the picture but the minor image portion stay in it. As this is a Morphological operation, it is considered as a benefit. These remaining skin areas can be efficiently eliminated by this Morphological Operation. Lastly, the eyes are separated from the removed face image by HSV structure & Morphological operations which is shown in the following figure. The extracted features of the above algorithm are given in to sorting by the skilled SVM. After the execution step, the consequences are estimated by some measurement like specificity, accuracy and sensitivity. Specificities are denoted, TN stands for true-negative, FP stands for false-positive, FN stands for false-negative and TP stands for true-positive.

7. RESULT & DISCUSSIONS :

The selected algorithm is applied on some databases like GATV, VITS, MATHWORK and FACE EXPRESSION. That algorithm is applied on more than 500 images in the automatic extraction stage on the face region. In figure 6 a successfully detected face image is shown. Also, in figure 7 a detected failed image is shown [source as author]. It has been observed that maximum errors arise due to the face position, especially when the image of face is

moving aside, distance of face and eye closer. The maximum efficiency of the selected algorithm is estimated on 500 pictures on which the detected region of eyes flourished. The result of evaluation is very high like sensitivity is 88.7%, specificity is 95.3% & accuracy is 89.3%. Figure 7 shows the picture of the non-face region. It is concluded that the error arise if the region of eyes were dark, similarities with eyebrows and background region & hair.

Fig.7 (a): Showing successful detection of Face; **(b):** Failure images

8. CONCLUSIONS :

Face detection nowadays has become a very essential issue for various applications. In this process, the face should be separated after removing unnecessary portions such as skin, background, & other human parts of the selected image. Many techniques are employed by different studies like matching the template, Hough Transform and Eigenvectors. Here a proposal has given some different process which includes Lab color spaces as well as HSV for eliminating all unnecessary pixels in the picture excluding Face & Neural Network categorize the picture as Face / non-Face. These experiments were performed by 100 pictures of various head persons, taken from the available standard databases & VITS database made in the time of the research work. The rate of success on selected algorithms is ninety-eight percent, the two percent unsuccessful rate in results is for some reason like background, head movement & due to neural network/ inappropriate training. The efficiency of the selected algorithm can be predictable on the basis of Specificity, Accuracy & Sensitivity. The estimated values are 95.2%, 88.6% & 89.2% correspondingly. For up gradation, the authors remain the work on the subject.

REFERENCES:

- [1] Ballantyne, M., Boyer, R. S., & Hines, L. (1996). Woody bledsoe: His life and legacy. *AI magazine*, 17(1), 7-7. [Google Scholar ↗](#)
- [2] Bekhet, S., Alghamdi, A. M., & Taj-Eddin, I. (2022). Gender recognition from unconstrained selfie images: a convolutional neural network approach. *International Journal of Electrical & Computer Engineering*, 12(2), 2245-2257. [Google Scholar ↗](#)
- [3] Biradar, V., Reddy, B. M., & Anumandla, K. K. (2018). Hardware prototyping for video and signal processing applications using dm 6437 texas instrument evaluation board. *International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics*, 20(6), 4127-4138. [Google Scholar ↗](#)
- [4] Biradar, V., Reddy, B. M., & Anumandla, K. K. (2018, October). DM3730 Processor Hardware Debugging on Linux Platform. In *2018 4th International Conference for Convergence in Technology (I2CT)* (pp. 1-4). IEEE. [Google Scholar ↗](#)
- [5] Black, M. J., & Yacoob, Y. (1997). Recognizing facial expressions in image sequences using local parameterized models of image motion. *International Journal of Computer Vision*, 25(1), 23-48. [Google Scholar ↗](#)
- [6] Bledsoe, W. W. (1964). *The model method in facial recognition*, panoramic research inc., Palo Alto. CA, Technical Report, Technical Report PRI: 15(1), 23-45. [Google Scholar ↗](#)
- [7] Bledsoe, W. W. (1965). Man-machine facial recognition: Report on a large scale experiment. *Technical report print 22, Panoramic Research, Inc., Palo Alto, California*, 3(2), 234-256. [Google Scholar ↗](#)
- [8] Bledsoe, W. W. (1968). Semiautomatic facial recognition. *Technical report sri project 6693*. [https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=en&as_sdt=0%2C5&q=Semiautomatic+facial+recognition.+Technical+report+sri+project+6693.&btnG=date+of+visit+3+April+2022] [Google Scholar ↗](#)
- [9] Brand, J., & Mason, J. S. (2000, September). A comparative assessment of three approaches to pixel-level human skin-detection. In *Proceedings 15th International Conference on Pattern Recognition. ICPR-2000* (Vol. 1, pp. 1056-1059). IEEE. [Google Scholar ↗](#)
- [10] Bruner, J. (1954). The perception of people. *Handbook of social psychology*. (pp. 123-145). [Google Scholar ↗](#)
- [11] Calcagnini, G., Biancalana, G., Giubilei, F., Strano, S., & Cerutti, S. (1994, November). Spectral analysis of heart rate variability signal during sleep stages. In *Proceedings of 16th Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society* (Vol. 2, pp. 1252-1253). IEEE. [Google Scholar ↗](#)
- [12] Chan, H., & Bledsoe, W. W. (1965). A man-machine facial recognition system: some preliminary results. *Panoramic Research Inc., Palo Alto, CA, USA 1965*. [Google Scholar ↗](#)

- [13] Chaudhry, S., & Chandra, R. (2017). Face detection and recognition in an unconstrained environment for mobile visual assistive system. *Applied Soft Computing*, 53(1), 168-180. [Google Scholar](#) ↗
- [14] Deng, J. Y., & Lai, F. (1997). Region-based template deformation and masking for eye-feature extraction and description. *Pattern recognition*, 30(3), 403-419. [Google Scholar](#) ↗
- [15] Ebisawa, Y. (1998). Improved video-based eye-gaze detection method. *IEEE Transactions on instrumentation and measurement*, 47(4), 948-955. [Google Scholar](#) ↗
- [16] Ebisawa, Y., & Satoh, S. I. (1993, October). Effectiveness of pupil area detection technique using two light sources and image difference method. In *Proceedings of the 15th Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Societ* (pp. 1268-1269). IEEE. [Google Scholar](#) ↗
- [17] Elsenbruch, S., Harnish, M. J., & Orr, W. C. (1999). Heart rate variability during waking and sleep in healthy males and females. *Sleep*, 22(8), 1067-1071. [Google Scholar](#) ↗
- [18] Feng, G. C., & Yuen, P. C. (1998). Variance projection function and its application to eye detection for human face recognition. *Pattern Recognition Letters*, 19(9), 899-906. [Google Scholar](#) ↗
- [19] Feng, G. C., & Yuen, P. C. (2001). Multi-cues eye detection on gray intensity image. *Pattern recognition*, 34(5), 1033-1046. [Google Scholar](#) ↗
- [20] Ganapathi, I. I., Prakash, S., Dave, I. R., & Bakshi, S. (2020). Unconstrained ear detection using ensemble-based convolutional neural network model. *Concurrency and Computation: Practice and Experience*, 32(1), 5197-5205. [Google Scholar](#) ↗
- [21] Greenspan, H., Goldberger, J., & Eshet, I. (2001). Mixture model for face-color modeling and segmentation. *Pattern Recognition Letters*, 22(14), 1525-1536. [Google Scholar](#) ↗
- [22] Haro, A., Flickner, M., & Essa, I. (2000, June). Detecting and tracking eyes by using their physiological properties, dynamics, and appearance. In *Proceedings IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition. CVPR 2000 (Cat. No. PR00662)* (Vol. 1, pp. 163-168). IEEE. [Google Scholar](#) ↗
- [23] Salman, A., Siddiqui, S. A., Shafait, F., Mian, A., Shortis, M. R., Khurshid, K., ...Schwanecke, U. (2020). Automatic fish detection in underwater videos by a deep neural network-based hybrid motion learning system. *ICES Journal of Marine Science*, 77(4), 1295-1307. [Google Scholar](#) ↗
- [24] Jain, A. K., Duin, R. P. W., & Mao, J. (2000). Statistical pattern recognition: A review. *IEEE Transactions on pattern analysis and machine intelligence*, 22(1), 4-37. [Google Scholar](#) ↗
- [25] Ji, Q., & Yang, X. (2001, July). Real time visual cues extraction for monitoring driver vigilance. In *International Conference on Computer Vision Systems* (pp. 107-124). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg. [Google Scholar](#) ↗
- [26] Jones, M. J., & Rehg, J. M. (2002). Statistical color models with application to skin detection. *International journal of computer vision*, 46(1), 81-96. [Google Scholar](#) ↗
- [27] Kanade, T. (1974). Picture processing system by computer complex and recognition of human faces, [https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=en&as_sdt=0%2C5&q=%5B27%5D%09Kanade%2C+T.+%281974%29.+Picture+processing+system+by+computer+complex+and+recognition+of+human+face+s.&btnG=date+of+visit+on+3+April+2022]. [Google Scholar](#) ↗
- [28] Kirby, M., & Sirovich, L. (1990). Application of the Karhunen-Loeve procedure for the characterization of human faces. *IEEE Transactions on Pattern analysis and Machine intelligence*, 12(1), 103-108. [Google Scholar](#) ↗
- [29] Klein, S. B., & Thorne, B. M. (2006). *Biological psychology*. Macmillan. [of visit on 3 April 2022] [Google Scholar](#) ↗
- [30] Kneis, B. (2018, September). Face Detection for Crowd Analysis Using Deep Convolutional Neural Networks. In *International Conference on Engineering Applications of Neural Networks* (pp. 71-80). Springer, Cham. [Google Scholar](#) ↗
- [31] Lee, J. D., Morgan, J., Wheeler, W. A., Hulse, M. C., & Dingus, T. A. (1997). *Development of Human Factors Guidelines for Advanced Traveler Information Systems (ATIS) and Commercial Vehicle Operations (CVO): Description of ATIS/CVO Functions* (No. FHWA-RD-95-201). [Google Scholar](#) ↗
- [32] Lu, X., Duan, X., Mao, X., Li, Y., & Zhang, X. (2017). Feature extraction and fusion using deep convolutional neural networks for face detection. *Mathematical Problems in Engineering*, 2017,2(1), 203-208. [Google Scholar](#) ↗

- [33] Martinkauppi, B., & Soriano, M. (2001, June). Basis functions of the color signals of skin under different illuminants. In *3rd Intl conference on Multispectral Color Science*. 7(1), (pp. 21-24) [Google Scholar](#) [↗]
- [34] Meng, L., & Nguyen, T. Q. (1999, October). Frontal face localization using linear discriminant. In *Conference Record of the Thirty-Third Asilomar Conference on Signals, Systems, and Computers (Cat. No. CH37020)* (Vol. 1, pp. 745-749). IEEE. [Google Scholar](#) [↗]
- [35] Mliki, H., Dammak, S., & Fendri, E. (2020). An improved multi-scale face detection using convolutional neural network. *Signal, Image and Video Processing*, 14(7), 1345-1353. [Google Scholar](#) [↗]
- [36] Motwani, M., Motwani, R., & Harris, F. (2004, September). Eye detection using wavelets and ANN. In *Proc. of GSPx*. [Google Scholar](#) [↗]
- [37] Nada, H., Sindagi, V. A., Zhang, H., & Patel, V. M. (2018, October). Pushing the limits of unconstrained face detection: a challenge dataset and baseline results. In *2018 IEEE 9th International Conference on Biometrics Theory, Applications and Systems (BTAS)* (pp. 1-10). IEEE. [Google Scholar](#) [↗]
- [38] Nixon, M. (1985, December). Eye spacing measurement for facial recognition. In *Applications of Digital Image Processing VIII* (Vol. 575, pp. 279-285). International Society for Optics and Photonics. [Google Scholar](#) [↗]
- [39] Oloyede, M. O., Hancke, G. P., & Myburgh, H. C. (2018). Improving face recognition systems using a new image enhancement technique, hybrid features and the convolutional neural network. *Ieee Access*, 6(1), 75181-75191. [Google Scholar](#) [↗]
- [40] Pentland, A., Moghaddam, B., & Starner, T. (1994). View-based and modular eigenspaces for face recognition. [Google Scholar](#) [↗]
- [41] Peters, R. D., Kloepfel, E., Alicandri, E., Fox, J. E., Thomas, M. L., Thorne, D. R., & Balwinski, S. M. (1999). *Effects of partial and total sleep deprivation on driving performance* (No. FHWA-RD-94-046). Turner-Fairbank Highway Research Center. [Google Scholar](#) [↗]
- [42] Pigeon, S., & Vandendorpe, L. (1997, March). The M2VTS multimodal face database (release 1.00). In *International Conference on Audio-and Video-Based Biometric Person Authentication* (pp. 403-409). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg. [Google Scholar](#) [↗]
- [43] Ranjan, R., Bansal, A., Zheng, J., Xu, H., Gleason, J., Lu, B., ...& Chellappa, R. (2019). A fast and accurate system for face detection, identification, and verification. *IEEE Transactions on Biometrics, Behavior, and Identity Science*, 1(2), 82-96. [Google Scholar](#) [↗]
- [44] Ravidas, S., & Ansari, M. A. (2019). Deep learning for pose-invariant face detection in unconstrained environment. *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering*, 9(1), 577. [Google Scholar](#) [↗]
- [45] Reinders, M. J., Koch, R. W. C., & Gerbrands, J. J. (1996, October). Locating facial features in image sequences using neural networks. In *Proceedings of the Second international conference on Automatic Face and Gesture Recognition* (pp. 230-235). IEEE. [Google Scholar](#) [↗]
- [46] Russ, J. C. (2006). *The image processing handbook*. CRC press. = date of visit on 3 April 2022] [Google Scholar](#) [↗]
- [47] Sahu, A. K., & Jaiswal, A. (2018, October). Modeling of Attacks in Sigma Delta ADC for Hardware Security. In *2018 3rd International Conference on Communication and Electronics Systems (ICCES)* (pp. 422-426). IEEE. [Google Scholar](#) [↗]
- [48] Saito, S. (1992). Does fatigue exist in a quantitative measurement of eye movements?. *Ergonomics*, 35(5-6), 607-615. [Google Scholar](#) [↗]
- [49] Salman, A., Siddiqui, S. A., Shafait, F., Mian, A., Shortis, M. R., Khurshid, K., & Schwanecke, U. (2020). Automatic fish detection in underwater videos by a deep neural network-based hybrid motion learning system. *ICES Journal of Marine Science*, 77(4), 1295-1307. [Google Scholar](#) [↗]
- [50] Sawat, D. D., Hegadi, R. S., Garg, L., & Hegadi, R. S. (2020). Pixel encoding for unconstrained face detection. *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, 79(47), 35033-35054. [Google Scholar](#) [↗]
- [51] Sigal, L., Sclaroff, S., & Athitsos, V. (2000, June). Estimation and prediction of evolving color distributions for skin segmentation under varying illumination. In *Proceedings IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition. CVPR 2000 (Cat. No. PR00662)* (Vol. 2, pp. 152-159). IEEE. [Google Scholar](#) [↗]
- [52] Stonham, T. J. (1986). Practical face recognition and verification with WISARD. In *Aspects of face processing* (pp. 426-441). Springer, Dordrecht. [Google Scholar](#) [↗]

- [53] Tian, Y. L., Kanade, T., & Cohn, J. F. (2000, March). Dual-state parametric eye tracking. In *Proceedings Fourth IEEE International Conference on Automatic Face and Gesture Recognition (Cat. No. PR00580)* (pp. 110-115). IEEE. [Google Scholar ↗](#)
- [54] Toscani, L., Gangemi, P. F., Parigi, A., Silipo, R., Ragghianti, P., Sirabella, E., ...&Zaccara, G. (1996). Human heart rate variability and sleep stages. *The Italian Journal of Neurological Sciences*, 17(6), 437-439. [Google Scholar ↗](#)
- [55] Tsunoda, M., Endo, T., Hashimoto, S., Honma, S., &Honma, K. I. (2001). Effects of light and sleep stages on heart rate variability in humans. *Psychiatry and clinical neurosciences*, 55(3), 285-286. [Google Scholar ↗](#)
- [56] Vanoli, E., Adamson, P. B., Ba-Lin, Pinna, G. D., Lazzara, R., & Orr, W. C. (1995). Heart rate variability during specific sleep stages: a comparison of healthy subjects with patients after myocardial infarction. *Circulation*, 91(7), 1918-1922. [Google Scholar ↗](#)
- [57] Vijayalaxmi, B., Anuradha, C., Sekaran, K., Meqdad, M. N., &Kadry, S. (2020). Image processing based eye detection methods a theoretical review. *Bulletin of Electrical Engineering and Informatics*, 9(3), 1189-1197. [Google Scholar ↗](#)
- [58] Vijayalaxmi, B., Sekaran, K., Neelima, N., Chandana, P., Meqdad, M. N., &Kadry, S. (2020). Implementation of face and eye detection on DM6437 board using simulink model. *Bulletin of Electrical Engineering and Informatics*, 9(2), 785-791. [Google Scholar ↗](#)
- [59] Viola, P., & Jones, M. (2001, December). Rapid object detection using a boosted cascade of simple features. In *Proceedings of the 2001 IEEE computer society conference on computer vision and pattern recognition. CVPR 2001* (Vol. 1, pp. I-I). Ieee. [Google Scholar ↗](#)
- [60] Wylie, C. D., Shultz, T., Miller, J. C., Mitler, M. M., & Mackie, R. R. (1996). Commercial motor vehicle driver fatigue and alertness study: Technical summary. [Google Scholar ↗](#)
- [61] Yang, M. H., &Ahuja, N. (1998, December). Gaussian mixture model for human skin color and its applications in image and video databases. In *Storage and retrieval for image and video databases VII* (Vol. 3656, pp. 458-466). International Society for Optics and Photonics. [Google Scholar ↗](#)
- [62] Yang, S., Luo, P., Loy, C. C., & Tang, X. (2017). Faceness-net: Face detection through deep facial part responses. *IEEE transactions on pattern analysis and machine intelligence*, 40(8), 1845-1859. [Google Scholar ↗](#)
- [63] Yuille, A. L., Hallinan, P. W., & Cohen, D. S. (1992). Feature extraction from faces using deformable templates. *International journal of computer vision*, 8(2), 99-111. [Google Scholar ↗](#)
- [64] Zhang, S., Wang, X., Lei, Z., & Li, S. Z. (2019). Faceboxes: A CPU real-time and accurate unconstrained face detector. *Neurocomputing*, 364(1), 297-309. [Google Scholar ↗](#)
- [65] Zhou, Y., Liu, D., & Huang, T. (2018, May). Survey of face detection on low-quality images. In *2018 13th IEEE international conference on automatic face & gesture recognition (FG 2018)* (pp. 769-773). IEEE. [Google Scholar ↗](#)